

C O R T E X ²

D6.3 – Open Call management from preparation to selection version 1

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Contributing Partners	Contributing to Open Call 1 offer design: all partners
Reviewer(s)	Alain Pagani (DFKI); Raquel Carro (AUS)

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Abstract

The deliverable presents a detailed overview of CORTEX² Open Call 1 documentation developed to support the management processes: from the application to the selection, covering a set of eligibility criteria, requirements from the applicants, CORTEX² offer, evaluation process, the funding programme and contracting. The report is complemented by an introduction section describing the co-creation processes of the Open Call 1 development.

This 1st version of the document targets launching the Open Call 1 on October 24, 2023 that closed on 16 January, 2024. In total **143 applications were submitted** (out of 264) for further evaluation by the external experts. The final results will be reported in deliverable D6.6.

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AWU	Annual Work Unit
AR	Augmented Reality
CORTEX ²	COoperative Real-Time experiences with EXTended reality
EC	European Commission
ESR	Evaluation Summary Report
GA	Grant Agreement
HCI	Human Computer Interaction
HMD	Head Mounted Display
IoT	Internet of things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MR	Mixed Reality
MS	Member States
NLP	Natural language processing
OC	Open Call
OCT	Overseas Countries and Territories
POC	Proof of Concept
R&D	Research and Development
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SDK	Software Development Kit
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UX	User Experience
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

The CORTEX² project

The COVID-19 pandemic pushed individuals and companies worldwide to work primarily from home or change their work model to stay in business. Today, all the signs are that remote work is here to stay. But not all organizations are ready to adapt to this new reality, where team collaboration is vital.

Existing services and applications aimed at facilitating remote team collaboration — from video conferencing systems to project management platforms — are not yet ready to efficiently and effectively support all types of activities. And extended reality (XR)-based tools, which can enhance remote collaboration and communication, present significant challenges for most businesses.

The mission of CORTEX² is to democratise access to the remote collaboration offered by next-generation XR experiences across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

To this aim, CORTEX² will provide the following:

- Full support for **augmented reality (AR) experiences** as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway platform.
- Resource-efficient **teleconferencing tools** through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarization of shared long documents.
- Easy-to-use and powerful **extended reality (XR) experiences** with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings.
- Fusion of vision and audio for **multichannel semantic interpretation**, and enhanced tools such as **virtual conversational agents** and **automatic meeting summarization**.
- Full **integration of internet of things (IoT) devices into XR experiences** to optimise interaction with running systems and processes.
- **Optimal extension possibilities and broad adoption** by delivering the core system with **open APIs** and launching **open calls** to enable further technical extensions, more comprehensive use cases, and deeper evaluation and assessment.

Overall, **we will invest a total of 4 million Euros in two open calls**, which will be aimed at

1. recruiting tech start-ups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX²
2. engaging new use cases from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths
3. assessing and validating the social impact associated with XR technology adoption in internal and external use cases

The CORTEX² consortium is formed by 10 organizations in 7 countries, which will work together for 36 months.

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1. Introduction

The project consortium with F6S as a leading partner organised its first **Open Call 1 (OC1)** investing a total of **€3.000.000** to explore, advance and demonstrate the technical features offered by CORTEX² through targeting 3rd parties (technology developers, providers, integrators and adopters) with knowledge and expertise in XR remote collaboration.

The specific **OC1 objectives** were as follows:

1. Recruiting tech start-ups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX².
2. Engaging new use cases from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths.
3. Assessing and validating the social impact associated with XR technology adoption in internal and external use cases.

The ultimate goal of the OC1 is to engage representatives in the 'Lab-To-Market' stage to support the technology transfer towards the 'Industrial Ecosystem', bridging the Open Innovation gap.

The OC1 was running for almost 3 months, attracting applications to select (i) 10 projects for co-developers with maximum funding up to €100.000 for 9 months programme, and (ii) 10 use-cases projects with maximum funding up to €200.000 for 12 months programme (Fig 1).

Figure 1: CORTEX² OC1 'must know'.

1.1 CORTEX² OC1 offer

The OC1 offer was co-designed by a series of workshops conducted with the whole Consortium. Following the definition of the project's needs, technical requirements to achieve the desired outcomes and available expertise within the CORTEX² Consortium the OC1 scope, definition and requirements were defined (Figure 2). The process and the final results of it are described in Section 2.

OPEN CALL 1 - DESIGN FOR 2 TRACKS

Figure 2: CORTEX² OC1 design.

1. 2 OC1 status - number of submitted applications

The Open Call 1 attracted the high number of applications – **146 submitted** (out of 264 started) allowing to meet the number of applications KPI for the project already in 73% (KPI=200 in two Open Calls). In terms of interest distribution, **Track 1: for co-developers attracted in total 103 started applications** out of which **49 were submitted**, and for **Track 2: use-cases 161 and 97 respectively**.

Regarding the distribution of the Topics within Track 1, 10 out of 11 Topics were successfully addressed by the applicants (Topic 6: 3D objects library being the most popular among the applicants – 10 applications) securing a wide diversity among the proposals.

Big success was achieved also in Track 2, where all 9 available Domains attracted a number of applications (Domain #1 Education received the highest number of applications – 25).

In terms of number of applications submitted per country, both Tracks attracted a variety of geographical locations with the following leaders (i) Track 1: France (7 applications), Greece and Italy (6) and Spain (5); (ii) Track 2: Greece (15), Spain (9), and Portugal (8).

TRACK 1

Figure 3 CORTEX² OC1 Track 1 – distribution per Topic of the submitted applications. N=49.

TRACK 2

Figure 4 CORTEX² OC1 Track 2 – distribution per Domain of the submitted applications. N=97.

**TRACK 1 - number of applications submitted per country distribution
N=49**

Figure 5 CORTEX² OC1 Track 1 – number of applications submitted per country distribution (21 countries).

TRACK 2 - number of applications submitted per country distribution N=97

Figure 6 CORTEX² OC1 Track 2 – number of applications submitted per country distribution (32 countries).

1.3 How to read this deliverable?

The report is divided into two parts. First part covers an introduction and the overview (Section 1), the activities performed to co-design the OC1 offer (Section 2), support services provided to the OC1 applicants (Section 3), and finally the current status of the OC1 and the next steps (Section 4).

Part two consists of nine documents attached to the deliverable as a form of original Annexes developed for the OC1 process. These documents describe in detail technical, practical and

legal terms and conditions constituting the OC1 management. They are the core part of this deliverable, particularly Annex 1.

2. Co-creation of Open Call 1

2.1 Co-design workshops

F6S as a leader of the task 6.4 *Grant definition and Open Call Management* organised eight co-design workshops guiding partners step by step in the definition of *What exactly should be funded - definition of challenges* and *What impact is expected from the 3rd parties - desired outcomes*. An OC1 strategy was formulated covering the following objectives:

- Identifying the **areas for development** by the 3rd parties
- Identifying the **domains of interest for use cases** by the 3rd parties
- Developing an OC1 **programme**: methodology, requirements, expectations, detailed programme of the selected parties and means of verification (KPIs, deliverables, demos)
- Preparing OC1 **documents** for applicants.

The first introductory workshop was held in May 2023. It presented the basic rules of shaping an Open Call under the funding tool of **Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP)**. It engaged all consortium participants to identify the target of OC1, goals, and structure. The focus was divided into (i) co-developing new features of CORTEX², and (ii) expanding the number of use-cases testing CORTEX² solution in different environments. Consequently, each partner was invited to submit an OC1 input for i and/or ii objective, covering the following:

- Identification of a Topic/Domain name (challenge)
- Justification of the above - why it is relevant and important for CORTEX²
- Challenge requirements - what condition and capacity are needed for successful addressing of the defined topic/challenge; e.g. minimum Technology Readiness Level (TRL), Open source, programming language, and other.
- What would be the ideal applicant/company profile to apply - focus on expertise and skills required.
- What would be the required deliverables as a form of controlling the progress and validating the achievements?
- What would be relevant KPIs to monitor?
- What technical support would be required from CORTEX² to the successful applicant(s)?
- Who within the consortium would be an expert evaluating the progress of the 3rd party for this specific challenge/topic/domain
- What is the expected outcome from the 3rd party at the end of the OC1 programme?

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All technical partners participated in the exercise. In total they submitted 25 proposals (13 co-developments topics and 12 use-cases proposals). These proposals were further examined in 7 workshops executing the following:

- Presenting each proposal by its author to the whole Consortium
- Challenging the proposal by the rest of Consortium with a series of questions evaluating the soundness and level of relevance for CORTEX²
- Identifying benefits, and potential risks
- Scoring the proposals
- Defining the priority of each submitted proposal
- Clarifying any doubts raised and defending the proposed topics/use-cases
- Final voting and closing the design of OC1 offer

7 out of 8 meetings were held online, where partners were engaged through dedicated surveys work. The last workshop was organised during the physical meeting of the General Assembly held in Athens on 21 September 2023. The final OC1 offer and design reflected feedback from the Project Officer and voting of the Consortium.

1. Track 1 co-development includes 10 defined Topics of highest relevance to CORTEX² advanced features and 1 Open Topic, where an applicant can propose own idea.
2. Track 2 use-case includes 8 desired Domains of interest to CORTEX² and 1 Open Domain.

Detailed Topics/ Domain profiles and requirements are described in Annex 1 (Section 2 Call for Proposals).

Figure 7 CORTEX² OC1: Track 1 co-development design.

Figure 8 CORTEX² OC1: Track 1 co-development design.

2.2 OC1 planned activities

Once the OC1 technical offer was designed, F6S defined other key management stages related to OC1 execution. These involved the following phases: (i) Application period dedicated to disseminating the call and supporting the applicants with relevant information, (ii) Evaluation processes & contracting the selected applicants, (iii) Onboarding the winners and implementing two separate OC1 Programmes one for co-developers and other for use-cases. Each activity is described in detail in the mandatory **Guidelines for Applicants** (Annex 1). This document together with additional OC1 materials was published at the project website <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/#documents>.

Figure 9 CORTEX² OC1 management plan.

The **CORTEX² Assistance Programme** covers technical, admin and on demand services. Below there is a summary of the activities planned for mentoring, monitoring and additional assistance. The tailored support will be planned in month 1 with the selected projects.

Figure 10 CORTEX² Assistance Programme.

2.3 Documentation

The OC1 design had to be supported with clear, transparent rules of applications, legal requirements and obligations, guidance on who can apply, when and how to apply. All these points were clarified in a series of nine documents constituting the legal base of OC1 activity with the public funding coming from the European Commission. These documents are the following:

- [Annex 1 Guidelines for Applicants](#) - key document exhaustive in explaining key details like: timeline of the OC1, topics and domains to apply to, eligibility criteria, obligations of applicants, evaluation process, contracting, OC1 programme and other legal aspects of the call. In brief the Applicant is guided through the document how to apply to the Call.
- [Annex 1.1 Technical Description](#) - technical description of the CORTEX² project and framework.
- [Annex 2 Application Form](#) - an online form with standard application questions that is mandatory to fill out at the F6S platform during the Open Call application.
- [Annex 2.1 Proposal Template for Track 1 co-development](#) and [Annex 2.2 Proposal Template for Track 2 use-cases](#): A mandatory word document for applicants to prepare and submit a project proposal of 10 pages.

- **Annex 3 Declaration of Honour:** a template of the declaration of no conflict of interest and that all conditions related to the CORTEX² Open Call 1 are accepted by the applying entity(ies). Upon acceptance of their proposal for funding, the signed and stamped declaration must be submitted.
- **Annex 4 SME Declaration:** a document that validates the legal status of an SME according to the EC definition. Upon acceptance of a proposal, the signed and stamped declaration must be submitted.
- **Annex 5 Sub-grant Agreement Template** - a contract between the CORTEX² consortium, represented by its coordinator (DFKI), and the leading beneficiary. The sub-grant agreement will also include the comments (if any) of the proposal's Evaluation Summary Report to the work plan, coming from the external evaluators.
- **Annex 6 Bank Account Information** - a form to indicate an account where the funds will be transferred. It must be signed by the entity, individuals, and the bank owners. The holder of the account will be the entity/ individual.

Each Applicant was obliged to study and comply with the terms and conditions described in the Guidelines for Applicants. During a series of 3 live recorded webinars, applicants were guided step by step of the scope of each of the documents and what documents are required to submit at the application stage, and which only during the contracting phase.

Figure 11 CORTEX² OC1 documents.

2.4 Launching

Following a series of co-designing processes described in Section 2, CORTEX² shaped an OC1 offer that reflects the project's mission, technical needs and expected impact coming from the 3rd parties. As a result, the OC1 design was divided into two tracks of applications (**Figure 2**), that was in line with the original plan from the Grant Agreement (GA):

Track 1 Co-development: to recruit tech Startups and SMEs to participate in the co-development of CORTEX² with the goal to build value-added services based on the CORTEX² framework leveraging Startups and SMEs expertise on specific market segments. Application page: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-1-co-development/apply>

Track 2 Use-case: to invite European technology adopters (which can work together with technology developers/providers/integrators) to address and/or propose use cases for the deployment of the CORTEX² framework and developed features in the co-development track 1. Application page: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-2-use-case/apply>

The OC1 was launched on the 24th of October 2023 and closed on the 16th of January 2024, at 17:00 CET. For the period of nearly 3 months, the OC1 was actively disseminated through mass campaigns and supported with 3 live webinars providing relevant content to the applicants and giving an opportunity to ask questions. Section 3 elaborates on these activities.

2.5 Recruitment of external evaluators

In accordance with the evaluation process outlined in the CORTEX² Grant Agreement and with the objective of ensuring a robust and transparent assessment procedure, the project initiated an Open Call to gather expressions of interest from external evaluators who will assist the selection of applicants. To facilitate this, F6S has prepared a comprehensive "Open Call for Evaluators" Information Template. This template encompassed the purpose of the Expression of Interest (Eoi), the specific types of experts sought, the remuneration and benefits offered to evaluators, and the services expected. Additionally, a draft contract template was created, so evaluators can get acquainted with the anticipated contractual arrangements. Finally, an [application page](#) and form was established on the F6S platform, providing a dedicated space for interested evaluators to submit their applications.

Figure 12 Screenshot of the F6S application page for the call of interest expression for the External Evaluators.

When completed, the information herein was uploaded to the project [website](#) by communication partner Australo.

Figure 13 Screenshot of CORTEX² website publication of the Open Call for External Evaluators.

The opportunity for external evaluators was disseminated via two means - direct F6S dissemination through the F6S platform and targeted promotion through social media

channels and personalized email campaigns managed by Australo. The EoI call was opened from the 24th of November 2023 until the 5th of January 2024. During this period a total number of 87 applications were received out of which 72 were finalised. Among the finalized applications, the gender distribution was 29% female to 71% male, comprising 21 female experts and 51 male experts.

Figure 14 Sex distribution of the External Evaluators among the submitted applications to the call of interest expression.

The evaluators were selected based on a predefined criteria - their expertise connected to the topics and domains identified by the Open Call. These criteria were organized into seven comprehensive subject areas: Extended reality (XR), virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) - based solutions; Artificial intelligence (AI); Teleconference and videoconference platforms; User experience design; Industry 4.0; Market uptake and business scalability; Ethical, legal and social implications of XR-based telecooperative work. Additional criteria were connected to understanding of XR teleconference platforms and their business and industrial applications, as well as experience in evaluating EU-funded projects, are considered an asset. The evaluators were assessed by experts of the consortium according to the criteria identified such as (i) XR, AI, and relevant tech demonstrated expertise, (ii) Tech Adopter industry expertise, and (iii) Experience in the EU evaluation. For the use-case evaluators, additional assessment has been conducted to identify experts with the business and marketing expertise. Out of these 72 finalised applications the consortium aims to contract between 16 -20 evaluators. This task is planned to be completed after the deadline of this deliverable, hence a final number of selected evaluators, including diversity in country and sex distribution will be reported in the next deliverable.

3. Support activities for Applicants

This section focuses on all support activities delivered by Open Call manager F6S to ensure comprehensive guidance and attract and retain the interest of potential third-party applicants for the Open Call opportunity. These activities are integral to the broader effort organised and executed by the communication lead partner, Australo. Specifics about the comprehensive communication plan and activities, encompassing the call promotional campaign, will be provided by Australo in the deliverable D6.5 *Impact final report*.

3.1 Informative webinars

As part of our promotional activities three webinars were organised with the aim of providing comprehensive information about the Open Call. These webinars were designed to address any queries potential applicants might have regarding the open call and the accompanying documentation. The table below outlines the structure, content, and impact of these webinars.

Table 1 CORTEX2 Open Call 1 Informative Webinars Overview

	Webinar 1	Webinar 2	Webinar 3
Topic:	XR-plore CORTEX ² €3M Funding How to apply?	CORTEX ² Breaks Essentials for Successful Applying	CORTEX ² Decodes OC#1 Topics & Domains to apply
Objective	Provide information regarding the funding opportunity coming from the CORTEX ² project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.	Provide details about the Open Call evaluation process, the program specifics for successful applicants, and the distribution and allocation of the budget.	Outline the technical areas for applicants in Track 1 (Co-development) and Track 2 (Use-cases). The CORTEX ² technical team presented each topic (Track #1) and domain (Track #2), addressing challenges, requirements, expected outcomes, deliverables, and KPIs. Technical support for successful applicants was also presented.
Speakers	-Alain Pagani, DFKI, CORTEX ² Coordinator -Ellie Shtereva, F6S - Open Call manager -Iwa Stefanik, F6S, Funding and Open Call manager -Narek Minaskan, DFKI,	-Alain Pagani, DFKI, CORTEX ² Coordinator -Ellie Shtereva, F6S, Open Call manager -Iwa Stefanik, F6S, Funding and Open Call manager	-Alain Pagani, DFKI, CORTEX ² Coordinator -Ellie Shtereva, F6S, Open Call manager -Emmanuel Helbert, Alcatel Lucent Enterprise, Tech expert -Iwa Stefanik, F6S,

	Tech expert		Funding and Open Call manager -Lydia Szymendera, Actimage, Tech expert -Marievi Xezonaki, Intracom Telecom, Tech expert -Narek Minaskan, DFKI, Tech expert -Sylvain Rivier, Alcatel Lucent Enterprise, Tech expert -Yazid Benazzouz, Linagora, Tech expert
Date and Duration	Date: 8 Nov 2023 Duration: 1 hour	Date: 6 Dec 2023 Duration: 1 hour	Date: 14 Dec 2023 Duration 1.5 h
Attendees	95	49	53
Link	Event link Recording link	Event link Recording link	Event link Recording link

3.2 Q&A Email support

In order to assist applicants with relevant inquiries related to the Open Call application process, project partner Australo established a Help Desk at opencall@cortex2.eu. The Help Desk was jointly managed by F6S open call managers and Australo. Upon receiving a query, both organisations were responsible for providing direct responses for questions related to concrete administrative matters. For inquiries of a specialised nature connected to the technology employed or the specific topics and domains of the Open Call, the query was directed to a technical expert from the technology development partners for a comprehensive response. Responses were provided within 1 to 3 working days. An average of 2 to 3 questions were received daily. As the Open Call deadline approached, the volume of questions intensified, with approximately 15 to 20 queries received in the final two weeks.

3.3 F6S public discussion board

In addition to the Help Desk a dedicated discussion board was open for applicants on the F6S page where the Open Call was managed. Each track under the open call had its own discussion board in order to filter the questions better.

- Track 1 Co-development discussion board can be accessed here: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-1-co-development/discuss>
- Track 2 Use - case discussion board can be accessed here: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-2-use-case/discuss>

Each discussion board was monitored by a designated open call manager from F6S. Response process was following a similar structure as in the help desk scenario. Administrative questions were directly handled by F6S open call managers, while technology-oriented queries were redirected to specialist partners. Once a response was received by the partner, the responsible F6S manager published it on the board. Given the interactive nature of the discussion board, responses to queries were promptly provided within 24 hours of receiving the question.

3.4 F6S scouting activities

CORTEX² Open Call made use of the F6S scouting services pertinent to the core business of the company. Specialised scouting process was applied where based on the profile of entities sought to apply for the call, the F6S scouting team performed a thorough search divided in three stages. Under stage 1 a mass mailing was sent to companies with a suitable profile - e.g. XR, AR, VR related specialists and founders. Potential applicants were pinned down out of the 5 000 000 members currently active in the platform. In the second stage, open calls with similar profiles were identified, and information about the opportunity reached suitable applicants. The final step involved a more targeted approach, where 30 companies matching the sought profile were directly approached and informed about the opportunity.

4. Next steps & conclusion

The OC1 attracted a high number of applications. In total showed interest in the call by starting the application process, while xx finalised and submitted their proposals on time. The next steps are related to the evaluation processes.

The OC1 evaluation process includes 4 main steps described in detail in Annex 1 section 3 and 5. As the very next step, F6S will be performing the eligibility check, coordinating selection of the external evaluators, and finally assigning them to the eligible applications initiating the remote evaluation.

Figure 15 CORTEX² OC1 next steps in the evaluation process.

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Once this is done, following a consensus meeting, shortlisted applicants will be invited to the interview phase. The project expects to conduct approximately 35 interviews. The best proposals will be invited to the contracting phase. Once this is done, selected parties will be onboarded to the programme through an online Kick off meeting.

These activities will be reported in the next deliverable D6.6 *Open Call Management from preparation to selection version 2*.

In conclusion the CORTEX² OC1 achieved the excellent results in terms of:

- OC1 design coordination and management of related activities
- 100% active engagement of the consortium partners
- Intense support for the applicants via numerous of services (live webinars, direct Q&A emails, public discussion boards, live promotion at the events)
- High number of interest and applications received

In order to keep the high standard achieved in OC1 for upcoming Open Call 2 a feedback session will be held with the partners to reflect what can be done differently and where there is a space to grow regarding Open Call 2. A feedback survey will also be held with the applicants.

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 1

Guidelines for Applicants

Open Call 1: Track 1 and Track 2

Submission deadline: **January 16, 2024, 17:00 CET**

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document provides a full set of information regarding the **CORTEX² 1st Open Call for Proposals**, also referred to as **Open Call #1**.

All associated Annexes must be additionally read for the submission of a Proposal.

1.1 Context

The COVID-19 pandemic pushed individuals and companies worldwide to work primarily from home or change their work model to stay in business. Today, all the signs are that remote work is here to stay. But not all organizations are ready to adapt to this new reality, where team collaboration is vital.

Existing services and applications aimed at facilitating remote team collaboration — from video conferencing systems to project management platforms — are not yet ready to efficiently and effectively support all types of activities. Extended reality (XR)-based tools, which can enhance remote collaboration and communication, present significant challenges for most businesses.

1.2 CORTEX² project

The CORTEX² project stands for **COoperative Real-Time experiences with EXtended reality**. It is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101070192.

CORTEX² is developing a highly innovative and digital XR teleconference platform specifically geared to facilitate work and social activities involving physical interaction with the environment and remote objects — from remote assistance or training to working in collaborative spaces. The project will democratise the integration of XR hardware and software into daily industrial processes for all types of operators, enabling next-generation tele-cooperation mechanisms that will accelerate the future of work and validate the scalability potential through competitive calls.

1.2.1 Team

The CORTEX² consortium is formed by 10 organizations in 7 countries, which work together for 36 months.

Table 2 CORTEX² Consortium: list of partners.

Company name	Abbreviation	Country
Actimage GmbH	ACT	Germany
ALE International	ALE	France
Commissariat A L Energie Atomique ET AUX Energies Alternatives	CEA	France
Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz GmbH	DFKI	Germany

F6S Network Ireland Limited	F6S	Ireland
Intracom Sa Telecom Solutions	ICOM	Greece
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	KUL	Belgium
Linagora Grand Sud Ouest SA	LINA	France
MTU Australo Alpha Lab	AUS	Estonia
Universitat Jaume I De Castellon	UJI	Spain

- **Two academia and research organisations** (DFKI, CEA) with outstanding scientific and technological expertise, required to deliver high-quality concepts, technologies, methods and algorithms.
- **Two academia (UJI, KUL) from the social sciences and humanities** that will contribute to making sure of the usability and exploitability of results with regard to EU legislation and values.
- **Four technical ICT providers** (ALE, LINA, ICOM, ACT) offering strong technical knowledge as well as an open-source business model and intention to exploit CORTEX² results.
- **Two SMEs with successful experience in ICT startup innovation business** (F6S, AUS), necessary to the success of the FSTP mechanism as well as the broad dissemination and exploitation of the CORTEX² results.

Figure 16 CORTEX² Consortium.

1.2.2 Ambition

The mission of CORTEX² is to democratize access to the remote collaboration offered by next-generation XR experiences across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

To this aim, CORTEX² will provide the following:

- Full support for **augmented reality (AR) experiences** as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway platform.
- Resource-efficient **teleconferencing tools** through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarization of shared long documents.

- Easy-to-use and powerful **extended reality (XR) experiences** with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings.
- Fusion of vision and audio for **multichannel semantic interpretation**, and enhanced tools such as **virtual conversational agents** and **automatic meeting summarization**.
- Full **integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices into XR experiences** to optimize interaction with running systems and processes.
- **Optimal extension possibilities and broad adoption** by delivering the core system with **open APIs** and launching **open calls** to enable further technical extensions, more comprehensive use cases, and deeper evaluation and assessment.

<p>Easy-to-use and powerful XR experiences with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings</p>	<p>Full integration of internet of things (IoT) devices into XR experiences to optimise interaction with running systems and processes</p>	<p>Full support for augmented reality (AR) experiences as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway platform</p>
<p>Resource-efficient teleconferencing tools through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarization of shared long documents</p>	<p>Fusion of vision and audio for multichannel semantic interpretation and enhanced tools such as virtual conversational agents and automatic meeting summarization</p>	<p>Optimal extension possibilities and broad adoption by delivering the core system with open APIs and launching open calls to enable further technical extensions, more comprehensive use cases, and deeper evaluation and assessment</p>

Figure 17 CORTEX² innovations.

1.2.3 Specific objectives

- **Development of an open digital workplace for generic XR experiences.** The goal is to develop an open, versatile, inclusive and scalable digital workplace — thus addressing

the challenges of the current limitation of technologies to support a large number of simultaneous users, joining with possibly heterogeneous devices.

- **Reduced environmental footprint of tele-cooperation.** The use of videoconferencing systems has a significant environmental footprint. For example, one hour of streaming or videoconferencing can emit between 150 and 1,000 grams of carbon dioxide, depending on the service used. During online calls, many documents are shared, often just to convey the general idea of their content. Another of the project's innovations will be to automatically summarise long documents before sharing them and send the full version only on demand.
- **Natural, flexible and plug-and-play XR collaborative experiences.** Extended Reality experiences should be easy to use even for occasional users without strong technical background. Our objective is to simplify the use of AR by including several technical modules in our framework:
 - a. Instantaneous 3D modelling
 - b. Natural gestures recognition and interpretation
 - c. Semantic matching of surrounding spaces
- **Semantic visual/audio fusion for enhanced functionalities.** High-level semantic understanding of visual situations and audio conversations will be beneficial to the users of remote tele-cooperation tools since it allows for the development of additional services such as automatic meeting summary, visual AR support for spoken conversation and alignment of semantic spaces.
- **Integration of IoT information for immersive video conferencing experience.** The objective is to create more immersive experiences for participants of videoconferences, by integrating rich contextual IoT information to video streams, rendered as AR annotations on top of displayed objects and persons.
- **Ethical, legal and social implications of XR-based tele cooperative work.** CORTEX² will create a novel technology to facilitate remote collaborative work, which raises ethical, legal and social challenges.

1.2.4 Pilots

The project will implement three different use cases as pilots to test the integration of all the components of the CORTEX² framework.

1.2.4.1 Pilot 1 – Industrial Remote Cooperation

The pilot will demonstrate that an XR immersive experience can be reached with heterogeneous and off-the-shelf mobile devices and with limited bandwidth conditions while improving productivity and reducing environmental footprint.

It will highlight the implementation of these services:

- Augmentation of the real environment with virtual assets in an industrial context
- Gesture analysis and scene semantics analysis to inject annotations in video streams.
- Audio transcription and voice command to control the immersive environment and document and record the intervention.
- Support and mixing of multiple videos and IoT data sources from non-immersive devices to compose an on-demand immersive collaboration space with augmented data such

as industrial data, gesture interpretation, and 3D image insertion, that will meet the front-line technician and expert needs depending on their devices involved.

- Optimization of network bandwidth usage through video and metadata stream orchestration as well as rendering distribution.

1.2.4.2 Pilot 2 – Remote Technical Training

The pilot will demonstrate that VR/AR allow for efficient knowledge transmission in one-to-many situations where the remote instructor can simultaneously help several trainees while referring to physical objects such as industrial equipment.

This pilot will explore the use case of a trainer of a technical learning session being assisted to allow him to deliver remotely a learning session using VR and showing manipulation of a machine to trainees. The immersive collaboration space will enable trainees and trainers to interact in real-time not only between them but also with the machine model.

The use case is based on the training of qualified staff in complex and technical tasks on large and complex machines. The virtualization aspect should allow both face-to-face and remote training.

The main objectives of this training aim at

- The comprehension of the main components of the machine.
- The correct operation of the vehicle in a safe way, linked with its surrounding environment.
- The improvement of the efficiency while using the machine, improvement of the skills and the tuning of the settings.
- The use of the virtual world allows for the simulation of dangerous situations, the collaborative aspect shall allow also to illustrate misuse scenarios of the machine.

1.2.4.3 Pilot 3 – Business meetings

The pilot will demonstrate that VR/MR enriched business meetings allow seamless integration of remote participants and improve productivity.

This pilot will allow us to develop an innovative business meeting support system, integrating several functionalities to improve and enrich the participants' experience. Such a tool will facilitate the integration of remote participants using VR and AR techniques on the one hand, to provide remote users with a perception of visual and auditory immersion close to real presence; on the other hand, to offer a representation of the remote person to the other participants of the meeting.

The following advanced VR features will be made available to reinforce user inclusion:

- Visual and audio immersion of the remote user.
- Modalities such as overlay display for the visualisation of information concerning both the collaboration's participants (name, function, profiles, etc.) and the interaction: subtitle, main topics discussed, recommendation of actions and any other information.
- Filmed or avatar representation of the remote user, with symbolic transcription of the non-verbal communication acts of the remote person who is provided with a panel of predefined actions that are automatically recognized: request to speak, participation in a vote, expression of agreement or disagreement, etc.

- Virtual representation of collaborative tools and artefacts such as board, projection screen and documents.
- Advance added value services will be provided, such as meeting transcription and automatic subtitling as well as document summarization and automatic minutes generation.

2. CALL FOR PROPOSALS

2.1 Objectives

In the 1st Open Call, CORTEX² will **invest a total of €3.000.000**, which will be aimed at:

1. Recruiting tech start-ups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX².
2. Engaging new use cases from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths.
3. Assessing and validating the social impact associated with XR technology adoption in internal and external use cases.

The objective is to investigate, advance and demonstrate the technical features offered by CORTEX². The project wants to engage representatives in the 'Lab-To-Market' stage to support the Technology Transfer towards the 'Industrial Ecosystem', bridging the Open Innovation gap. Special focus but not limited to is on:

- **Research-oriented institutions:** technical universities, RTOs, spin-offs
- **Business-driven organisations:** from highly risk-taking Startups to innovation units in established industry players (SMEs).

2.2 Open Call #1 design

The Open Call #1 has two tracks of applications:

- **Track 1: Co-development:** to recruit tech Startups and SMEs to participate in the co-development of CORTEX² with the goal to build value-added services based on the CORTEX² framework leveraging Startups and SMEs expertise on specific market segments.
- **Track 2: Use-case:** to invite European technology adopters (which can work together with technology developers/providers/integrators) to address and/or propose use cases for the deployment of the CORTEX² framework and developed features in the co-development track 1.

OPEN CALL 1 - DESIGN FOR 2 TRACKS

Figure 18 CORTEX² Open Call 1 design.

Table 3 Open Call 1 characteristics.

Type of application	Target and goal	Expected outcome	# funded projects	Who can apply
Track 1 Co-dev	For tech Startups/SMEs to participate in the co-development of CORTEX ² : (1) addressing the topics defined by the CORTEX ² team, or (2) open topic submitted by the applicant within the scope of the CORTEX ² objectives.	Build value-added services based on the CORTEX ² framework leveraging Startups/SMEs' expertise on specific market segments.	10	Single or 2 Startup(s)/SME(s) Tech developer(s)/provider(s)
Track 2 Use-case	For tech adopters (which can work together with tech developers) to propose use cases (1) within the desired domains, OR (2) open domain, for the deployment of CORTEX ² framework and developed features (coming from Co-development winning projects)	Ensure product-market fit and successful adoption for the developed services by including end-users at the centre of the use-cases development/validation.	10	Single or 2 organisations End-user + Tech developer/provider/integrator

2.2.1 Track 1: CO-DEVELOPMENT

CORTEX² organises its Open Call #1 with two tracks of applications.

Track 1: Co-development will fund the development, integration and validation of highly innovative XR, AR technologies. They will contribute to CORTEX² digital XR platform specifically geared to facilitate work and social activities involving physical interaction with the environment and remote objects — from remote assistance or training to working in collaborative spaces.

The selected 3rd parties will be co-building an interdisciplinary community with expertise from the areas of XR, AR, users' providers of videoconferencing, AI, psychology and ethics with the mission of building next-generation extended reality tele-cooperation solutions.

FOR WHO?

This track 1 will finance at minimum one single entity (tech Startup/SME) and maximum of two entities representing **Technology Developer(s)**: with emphasis on the XR, AR, AI Startups/SMEs serving as innovators. The inclusion of the 2nd entity must be justified.

Figure 19 CORTEX² Track 1: co-development design.

The expected **result will be 10 innovative projects** from the co-development track run by the selected Startups/SMEs, co-developing and demonstrating the value of CORTEX² technologies.

Table 4 Track 1: Co-development programme.

Track 1: CO-DEVELOPMENT				
Sprint name	Duration (months)	Activity	Means of verification	Funding ⁽³⁾ % of the project budget
SPRINT 1	3	Development	- Design and integration plan - Deliverables required per selected Topic ⁽¹⁾ - KPIs defined per selected Topic ⁽²⁾	40%
SPRINT 2	3	Integration	- Minimum demo - List of deliverables per selected Topic ⁽¹⁾ - Listed KPIs ²	35%
SPRINT 3	3	Validation	- Final product and test results - List of deliverables per selected Topic ⁽¹⁾ - Listed KPIs ⁽²⁾	25%

¹⁾ The list of deliverables required per selected Topic is available in each Topic description. In the case of the application for **Open Topic**, the applicant must define 3 deliverables, 1 per each sprint.

²⁾ The list of KPIs required per selected Topic is available in each Topic description. In the case of the application for **Open Topic**, the applicant must define a minimum of 3 KPIs, 1 per sprint.

³⁾ Associated with a positive assessment of the required deliverable(s) and KPIs.

List of available Topics for the co-development track

Please choose one of the available **Topics** to apply to the Track 1 co-development.

If no fit is found, an applicant can apply to **Open Topic**, submitting a proposal of work aligned with the Track 1 objectives and the 9-month programme distribution. Such applicant must propose own set of deliverables and KPIs (Table 3).

Table 5 Co-development Track Requirements: ethics, security and data management.

Co-development Track Requirements	
Ethics	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All Artificial Intelligence software or techniques co-developed in the course of CORTEX² must be compliant with the Assessment checklist for trustworthy AI as proposed by the High-level expert group on AI (AI HLEG). The complete document can be retrieved from the website of the European Commission to conduct a self-assessment. Hence, the applicants must conduct a self-assessment to ensure that the proposed solution adheres to the ethical requirements in the assessment list, namely. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Human Agency and oversight ii. Technical robustness and safety iii. Privacy and data protection

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> iv. Transparency v. Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness vi. Societal and environmental well-being vii. Accountability <p>2. In addition, the applicant must assess the possibility and disclose whether their proposed solutions, software or the techniques have dual use (military application) or are capable of being misused (illegal or unethical purposes or used to violate human rights or compromise the safety of humans, animals or the environment). To this end, the applicant must disclose the capabilities of all co-developed components or software.</p>
Security	The applicant must implement the appropriate privacy-preserving techniques, safeguards, security, measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data concerning the development, deployment and use phases of the co-developed software components. The applicant must disclose the possible and known risks and vulnerabilities concerning cybersecurity of the co-developed software or components.
Data management	The applicant must outline how data would be collected, generated and/or processed with details of the type of data/metadata they intend to use and the origin of such data, the quality assurance of such data. Details on how the applicant intends to comply with the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) must be provided along with storage, security, and re-use plans for such data.

Table 6 Topic#1 User representation and user avatar customization.

Topic#1 User representation and user avatar customization

Challenge	<p>When participating in a CORTEX² meeting, the users can be represented by an avatar in various modalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3D character when participating in a VR experience, • alternative 2D appearance when using the VCAA module (which can be realistic or cartoonish), or • mixed if using an AR variant of CORTEX² (e.g. real video with additional items such as a hat or virtual glasses). <p>In the current implementation of CORTEX², these representations are taken from a limited number of standard representations: (1) a limited number of pre-created 3D avatars, (2) a limited number of source images for the VCAA. In the long term, users might want to customize their appearance when participating in the experience. For example, users might want to choose their gender, their skin tone, their hair colour, their hairstyle, and the style and colour of their clothes and their accessories (glasses, hats). To this aim, a specific module for enabling the users to create easily their avatar is required. This can take the form of a special lobby in which the users can choose among different versions for selected characteristics (size, hairstyle, hair colour etc...). Ideally, it should be possible to re-use his avatar in multiple sessions, and there should be a unity among the different modes (2D, 3D), where the same person would look the same with different styles in the different modes. Once the user has selected his/her preferred representation, this can be stored in his/her settings and can be persistent over multiple sessions. This module should be reusable for the Unity and Mozilla Hubs variants of CORTEX applications.</p>
Co-development area	Scene semantics

Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL 4, Final TRL 6		
	Source code availability	The created software can be provided either as open-source code, or as proprietary code in form of a library (e.g. dll) or a service (e.g. web service with REST interface etc).		
	Standards	Not mandatory		
	Programming language	Unity (C#) / Mozilla Hubs, possibly python and/or C++		
	Other(s)	Good to have: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual design • Knowledge in Deep Learning • Knowledge in XR 		
Ideal candidate	Strong knowledge in Unity and virtual design / Knowledge in Deep Learning, Computer Vision and Image Processing			
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)	
	D1. Proof of concept and development plan A minimum editing tool with a development plan for the next sprints must be presented to the CORTEX partners	D2. First demonstrator with CORTEX integration First demonstrator demonstrating the editing tool with some connectivity to the CORTEX framework, including a report with initial documentation	D3. Final demonstrator and validation report Demonstration of the fully integrated module into CORTEX framework, and a report including full documentation and the result of a validation	
KPIs	At the end of the project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a customized avatar in 2D and 3D in less than 10 minutes • Possibility of editing at least 5 attributes of the avatar (e.g. hair color, hair style, clothes, accessories) • Ability to make avatars have a realistic appearance similar to that of the user • Demonstration of use in AR and VR within CORTEX in at least one scenario 			
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation of CORTEX² framework • An assigned contact person from CORTEX² consortium • Integration support 			
Expected final outcome	The final outcome should be a module that integrates into CORTEX ² that allows for the creation, edition, modification, storage for later use of a user-specific avatar that can be visualized in 2D and 3D. In addition, the third-party partner should provide a final report with a full documentation of the software.			

Table 7 Topic#2 Real-time object virtualizer.

Topic# 2 Real-time object virtualizer

Challenge	<p>Since CORTEX² is focusing on simplifying teleoperation, there is a need for being able to digitalise real scenes and objects in order to share them virtually with all distant partners. The reconstruction and digitalization of the user's environment are already included in the project task, however, the methods developed there do not cover the need for digitalization of small, specific objects. Therefore, we seek to develop a module/service that would allow the users to use a simple camera or smartphone to digitalize a small object (dimension range: 20cm to 100cm) and save it as a digital representation such as e.g. a textured mesh. The module can be implemented as a service running on a server. In this case, the service will receive either individual images of the object or a video stream. The module should use these images/video sequences to perform a fast 3D object reconstruction. The module should return a digital representation of the object, which will be shared among the participants of a session.</p>
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Co-development area	Scene semantics		
Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL 4, Final TRL 6	
	Source code availability	The created software can be provided either as open-source code, or as proprietary code in form of a library (e.g. dll) or a service (e.g. web service with REST interface etc).	
	Standards	Not mandatory	
	Programming language	C++, C#, or Python	
	Other(s)	Good to have: Deep learning, computer vision, computer graphics, software engineering	
Ideal candidate	A small company with expertise in 3D reconstruction using some of these technologies: Deep learning, computer vision, computer graphics, software engineering		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. Module analysis and integration plan.	D2. Minimum demo.	D3. Final product and test results.
KPIs	<p>At the end of the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reconstruction time should be less than 30 minutes – candidates should aim at shorter reconstruction times (e.g. a couple of minutes using 5-6 images). Demonstration of successful reconstruction of at least 3 different objects. Reconstruction should be possible with either one videosequence of max. 30 seconds as an input, or 50 single images as an input. 		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation of CORTEX² framework An assigned contact person from CORTEX² consortium Integration support 		
Expected final outcome	The final outcome should be a module that integrates into CORTEX ² that allows for the 3D reconstruction of objects in a live CORTEX session. It should be possible to import the 3D reconstructions of the objects into the CORTEX ² session to visualize it and share it with distant partners. In addition, the third-party partners should provide a final report with a full documentation of the software.		

Table 8 Topic#3 Collaborative Hand Object Manipulation.

Topic# 3 Collaborative Hand Object Manipulation

Challenge	<p>VR allows single or multiplayer scenarios in Cortex² for efficient knowledge transmission in one-to-many situations where the remote instructor can simultaneously help several trainees while referring to physical objects such as industrial equipment. Collaboration between users during training sessions brings more impact in learning by reproducing gestures and processes. Focus should be made on interoperability between a trainer and several trainees, a medical team or a technical team.</p> <p>Hand tracking so as movement analysis is required to reproduce the correct or perfect required hand gesture. Working together on an object (non-human or human) by passing each other instruments and parts or acting simultaneously on an object will open new VR possibilities. Applications could include zooming on very small parts needing very precise gestures and actions, gesture snippets like double-clicking, zooming, gesture recognition so as hand tracking and image processing.</p> <p>Fast geometry analysis for simple reconstruction of hand gesture and interaction with objects between people will support the users' learning session.</p>
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Co-development area	VR Collaborative interactions		
Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL 5, Final TRL 7	
	Source code availability	Yes (Repository with full code will be available) The created module can be provided either as open-source code or as a proprietary code in form of a library or a service	
	Standards	Not mandatory	
	Programming language	Unity C#	
	Other(s)	Unity 3D	
Ideal candidate	Unity expert, multi-users projects in an industrial or medical environment, 3D designer, software data integrator		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. Module analysis: object interaction on single mode Hand VR interaction.	D2. Collaboration and communication Hand VR interaction between several users being monitored by a remote trainer.	D3. Precision Adding more complex action/interaction with high precision of hand gestures.
KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The high frame rate for high-level precision and simulation during scenario (min. 80 FPS). Motion sickness as low as possible. Maximum of 30 mins to achieve the training scenario accessibility of the application to all most recent available headset. Minimum 4 VR users in the training session and one remote user. 		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training about our scene scenarization logic Connectivity to Rainbow through Unity Unity documentation Git architecture Unity collaborative space (plastic SCM) Access to all the VR project archives An assigned contact person from CORTEX² 		
Expected final outcome	The final outcome should be a Unity library that integrate a correct VR hand gesture recognition and reproduction with greater precision so as the possibility to manipulate objects in a collaborative way into Cortex ² . In addition, the third-party partner should provide a final report with a full documentation of the module. This module should be demonstrated in one application.		

Table 9 Topic#4 IoT Adaptability of Cortex2 framework.

Topic# 4 IoT Adaptability of Cortex2 framework

Challenge	In the context of Cortex2, IoT information-delivering services will be integrated into various videoconferencing XR applications in order to make the XR experience more immersive for the participants. To this end, data will be collected by a versatile IoT Platform, implemented and integrated as part of Cortex2, from multiple heterogeneous connected IoT devices. This data will be brought into a unified, IoT-protocol-agnostic format and will be exploited to generate insightful information related to smart assets of various vertical domains.
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	<p>A challenge to be addressed is the extension of the IoT device types supported in CORTEX2 with the integration a testing of new, domain-specific IoT devices and different IoT protocols in the CORTEX2 framework, in order to examine and evaluate the IoT adaptability and operation of CORTEX2. This requires the development of IoT adaptors for the newly added IoT devices and protocols, to integrate and achieve compatibility with the unified REST interfaces that will be offered by CORTEX2.</p> <p>A multitude of IoT device types and IoT protocols are expected.</p>		
Co-development area	IoT Integration		
Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL 4, Final TRL 6	
	Source code availability	Open-source, part of CORTEX ² source code repository, or provided as a library or service by the applicant.	
	Standards	Support of REST communication for interaction of the IoT devices with CORTEX2 platform	
	Programming language	N/A	
	Security	User access control to each IoT device with CORTEX2 authentication and authorization mechanisms	
	Data management	Unified IoT-protocol-agnostic format, provided by the IoT platform of CORTEX2.	
	Other(s)	The applicant should implement the necessary components (IoT adaptors) and functionalities in order to adapt to the unified IoT endpoints exposed by CORTEX ² . Also, integration with CORTEX ² authorization services would be required.	
Ideal candidate	The ideal applicant should belong to a vertical/domain which utilizes IoT for their operation. The applicant should bring a large number of IoT devices, covering a wide range of different IoT protocols, specific to their industry/domain, in order to integrate them with the CORTEX ² system. The applicant should have software development and IoT expertise, in order to implement the necessary IoT adaptors per protocol, which will enable this integration.		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. The architecture definition and adaptors development for the integration with the CORTEX ² platform.	D2. The integrated prototype.	D3. The experiments and evaluation report.
KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 5 different IoT device types and a respective set of IoT protocols • Each IoT device type accessible by 1 meeting room and its users • IoT data upload: up to 1 minute, depending on pilot nature 		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introductory workshop on uiTOP platform and its use in CORTEX² framework • Access to IoT REST interfaces exposed by CORTEX² and documentation of the interfaces • Access to CORTEX² Git repository for storage of the developed modules • Integration guidelines and technical support to resolve potential issues • An assigned contact person from CORTEX² 		
Expected final outcome	The final outcome should include a number of modules/IoT adaptors which will enable the integration of several IoT devices supporting different (domains specific) IoT protocols with the Cortex ² platform through REST communication. In addition, the third-party partner should provide a final report with a full documentation of the implemented modules and integrated prototype.		

Table 10 Topic#5 Dynamic library of personalized gestures.

Topic# 5 Dynamic library of personalized gestures

Challenge	<p>Hand tracking and gesture capture, recording for AR/VR.</p> <p>Depending on the application, different gestures can be used to perform different actions. Since CORTEX² will be open to the development of new applications, there is a need of being able to recognise very specific gestures (hand gestures or body gestures) that would have a certain semantic interpretation and trigger a specific action. In this topic, we seek the development of a module that takes a hand pose or body pose as an input and can record a certain gesture if the user does this gesture once or several times. The idea is to recognise the gesture by analysing the movements (hands, arms) robustly, even if the gesture is made slightly differently by different persons. As an input, the module will take the hand or body pose generated by CORTEX², or the hand pose captured by the hardware directly. The module should offer the possibility to store a certain gesture for future recognition in future applications. The module should also offer the possibility to link a certain gesture with a certain action. This means that when a pre-trained gesture has been recognised, this will trigger a specific action in the application. The module should show an example of an action (e.g. moving an object, switching the light on and off etc). Since applications can create any gesture for specific actions, the result will be a library of gestures, that can be extended dynamically, and that will contain personalized, i.e., application-specific gestures.</p>		
Co-development area	Gesture Analysis		
Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL 4 Final TRL 6	
	Source code availability	The created software can be provided either as open-source code, or as proprietary code in form of a library (e.g. dll) or a service (e.g. web service with REST interface etc).	
	Standards	Not mandatory	
	Programming language	C++, C#, or Python	
	Other(s)	N/A	
Ideal candidate	Expertise in AR/VR, HCI, interaction design, hand tracking and gesture recognition.		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. Module analysis and integration plan.	D2. Implementation plan and minimum demo.	D3. Documentation of the developed software module.
KPIs	<p>At the end of the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recognition of at least 10 different gestures ● Demonstration of the gestures in at least one CORTEX² scenario 		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Documentation of CORTEX² framework ● An assigned contact person from CORTEX² consortium ● Integration support 		
Expected final outcome	The final outcome should be a module that integrates into CORTEX ² and allows the user to define specific gestures for specific actions. This module should be demonstrated in one application. In addition, the third-party partners should provide a final report with a full documentation of the software.		

Table 11 Topic#6 3D objects library.

Topic# 6 3D objects library			
Challenge	<p>While developing a VR or MR application, there is always the need to integrate 3D objects and we want to make CORTEX² application look and feel astonished and ease the way for the developers to create his application.</p> <p>Make the CORTEX² proposition more unique in providing a useful graphical objects library and easy to implement in scenarios similar to the pilot's ones.</p> <p>The objects are made available to the CORTEX² users. The library can also be valued to external users.</p> <p>The Cortex Graphical charter must be respected</p>		
Co-development area	<p>- 2D/3D Scene samples: virtual room, lobby, vertical market-oriented (Healthcare, Education, crisis room ...), screen and whiteboard</p> <p>- 3D object library: table, chairs, tools or 3D objects In the form of Unity assets and Mozilla Hubs compliant</p>		
Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL6, Final TRL8	
	Source code availability	N/A	
	Standards	.obj, .fbx, ...	
	Programming language	N/A	
	Security	Should follow unity and Mozilla Hubs security rules for integration	
	Data management	Optimized data exchange, security in the case of import/export	
	Other(s)	Generate objects compliant with Unity 3D environment and Mozilla Hubs environment. High TRL	
Ideal candidate	3D Design studio, 3D modelling tool providers		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. Design specification document.	D2. Unity 2D & 3D asset/package.	D3. Unity sample code integrating those packages.
KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimum 2 Unity design packages, • 2 samples of usage • 3 3D virtual room with its associated furniture 		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An assigned mentor from CORTEX² • Unity documentation • CORTEX² graphical charter and ergonomics guidelines • Git architecture • Unity collaborative space • Access to all the VR project archives 		
Expected final outcome	Having a clearly defined set of objects that can be imported and assembled within a Unity scene.		

Table 12 Table #7 Automatic notetaking in virtual videoconference.

Topic# 7 Automatic notetaking in virtual videoconference			
Challenge	<p>Paying attention during a videoconference (meeting or learning session) isn't enough for the memorization process. That's where notetaking comes in. Its purpose is to summarize the main ideas expressed during the session. Effective note-taking saves time when re-reading and sharing key information.</p> <p>Several questions are raised for autonomous resolution of this problem i.e., having an AI process capable of doing this task for you.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is important to note? Powerful keywords, the author and source when a graph, image or quotation is used. This will help to complete the picture if further explanation is needed, • Colleagues' questions: what questions might your colleagues ask, and how important are they? • What methods can be used to transcribe relevant information? There are many ways of taking notes, so you need to experiment with different techniques and choose the one that makes it easier to reread and learn. For example, Mind mapping: reasoning in tree form, Page layout: the colour and abbreviation of the transcribed text, the Cornell method: gathering useful information in terms of General information, Notes, questions and summarization. <p>Some software solutions already exist and could help to be inspired to implement a solution for CORTEX² such as Evernote, Google keep, OneNote, Zoho Notebook</p>		
Co-development area	Speech technology and NLP in XR meetings context		
Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL6, Final TRL8	
	Source code availability	open-source	
	Standards	N/A	
	Programming language	N/A	
	Ethics	GDPR compliance	
	Security	GDPR security measures	
	Data management	Datasets and Data models	
	Other(s)	Preference for multilingual models ((English + French or German)	
Ideal candidate	R&D Labs working on speech and NLP		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. Data collection and deep learning models selection.	D2. Data pre-processing and models training source code.	D3. Notetaking models' assessment and selection
KPIs	Evaluation metrics for summarization, eg ROUGE and BERTScore		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An assigned contact person from CORTEX² • Input from CORTEX members with expertise in summarization 		
Expected final outcome	Model for note taking/extractive summarization plus data sets used for training and evaluation.		

Table 13 Topic#8 Connect Your app service to XR engine.

Topic# 8 Connect Your app service to XR engine			
Challenge	<p>How to make CORTEX² the best companion for all kinds of use.</p> <p>The challenge will bring additional features to the core XR engine to extend CORTEX² telepresence facilities to applications from other domains. It will bring existing features used in specific vertical domains to CORTEX², making the platform easier to adopt. For instance, one can think of having Servicenow or Zendesk services made directly interoperable within CORTEX².</p>		
Co-development area	New equipment integration, 3rd party application integration (i.e. project management, ticket management)		
Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL 7, Final TRL 8	
	Source code availability	N/A	
	Standards	N/A	
	Programming language	C# and Node.js	
	Ethics	External application should comply with GDPR	
	Security	Application integration should comply with security best practices	
	Other(s)	N/A	
Ideal candidate	Applicants who provide a very specific feature (for instance, connectors to agenda, to project management, to task management, etc...) or mobile devices that collect and distribute media flows (drones, embedded camera, others)		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. High-level architecture.	D2. Running prototype in lab.	D3. Running prototype in the field with assessment from users.
KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One scenario description Business Outcome: Depending on the application connected, Quantitative estimation of the benefits brought by the integration (time, financial, resources...) Validation: Assessment report from at least 10 users Allowing customization of connected applications to reduce technostress from notifications and interruptions. 		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training about SDK and API Access to sandbox (individual request to be confirmed with CORTEX² consortium), Integration bootcamp (to be confirmed and approved with CORTEX² consortium) Connectivity to Rainbow through Unity Unity and Rainbow SDK documentation Git architecture Unity collaborative space An assigned mentor from CORTEX² 		
Expected final outcome	The CORTEX ² framework will be enriched with the capability to instantiate and manipulate 2D or 3D objects representing the new integrated application by using Unity. Users will then be capable of extracting, visualizing, sharing information from these applications within the CORTEX ² collaboration scene on 2D or 3D devices as well as accessing the services of these application in XR telepresence manner.		

Table 14 Topic#9 Authoring tool for VR environment.

Topic# 9 Authoring tool for VR environment			
Challenge	<p>The CORTEX² project targets a specific category of application, focused on collaboration and cooperation in virtual environment context. Providing tools to automating the development process will facilitate the production of CORTEX² apps, increasing the user's community and taking advantage from the open-source development model.</p> <p>The aim of this call topic is to produce, from a simplistic specification such as xml or UML-like web interface, a project template that takes into account the dependencies, services and functionalities on which a developer can build his CORTEX² application.</p>		
Co-development area	scene construction; avatar generation		
Requirements	TRL	Minimum TRL6 - Final TRL7	
	Source code availability	open-source	
	Standards	N/A	
	Programming language	C#, Javascript, others	
	Other(s)	Design Patterns Methodology	
Ideal candidate	R&D development group working on open source tools		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. Authoring tool specification	D2. Authoring tool, first release and prototype source code.	D3. Authoring tool, final release with supported specification and future improvements
KPIs	Authoring tool should generate up >50% of CORTEX ² App specification.		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An assigned mentor from CORTEX² • Pilots code and demonstrators from CORTEX² members 		
Expected final outcome	A tool that allows the creation of CORTEX ² application, from a textual or visual specification, with at least a 30% of the planned developments.		

Table 14 - Topic#10 Maintaining interface engagement and usability for CORTEX² framework.

Topic# 10 Maintaining interface engagement and usability for CORTEX ² framework	
Challenge	<p>User interface design is important because it influences how users engage with CORTEX² and how it helps them create their applications and use cases.</p> <p>User engagement refers to the way in which users commit to using CORTEX² framework to build their applications. The highly competitive market makes it difficult for many products to gain market share, attract new developers and retain existing ones. An interested developer is more likely to use CORTEX² and recommend it.</p> <p>The user interface is at the heart of this commitment. CORTEX² developers need features, tools and so on to enable them to achieve a high level of usability. If the interface is easy</p>

	<p>to produce and continues to provide new features, the number of CORTEX² developers will increase at an exponential rate.</p> <p>User interface (UI) and functionalities are important elements in the way developers build a community around the CORTEX² framework. Developers will be more inclined to continue using CORTEX² if it is able to provide and integrate new user-friendly and attractive features.</p> <p>The objective is to study how to improve the user interface and integrate new features to encourage the use of CORTEX² framework. How the interface should be, so CORTEX² applications are more suited for simple users. This may even involve designing or developing new bricks or making certain functions generic to make framework more attractive.</p>		
Co-development area	scene semantics; avatar generation		
Requirements	TRL (*)	Minimum TRL6, Final TRL7	
	Source code availability	open-source	
	Standards	N/A	
	Programming language	C#, JavaScript, others	
	Other(s)	N/A	
Ideal candidate	R&D development group working on open-source tools		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	1st Sprint (M3)	2nd Sprint (M6)	3rd Sprint (M9)
	D1. interface engagement and maintaining design for CORTEX ² application	D2. interface engagement and maintaining implementation for CORTEX ² application.	D3. Validation Prototype and source code.
KPIs	Number of users approved the new features > 75% among the total number of users		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An assigned contact from CORTEX² 		
Expected final outcome	An in-depth analysis that determines the list of features that will have an impact on maintaining CORTEX ² application interface engagement and usability. Then demonstrating this through a prototype.		

2.2.2 Track 2: USE-CASE

A core part of CORTEX² is the design and implementation of three different use cases as pilots to test the integration of all the components of the teleconference framework. The three pilots (industrial remote cooperation, remote training, and business meeting) are developed by the project consortia and are thoroughly described under [Section 1.2.4](#).

The objective of **Open Call 1, Track 2 Use-case** is to address supplementary use cases extending beyond the 3 pilots developed within the project, through which to demonstrate the replicability and sustainability of CORTEX² framework covering a wide spectrum of use cases. It also aims to guarantee proper and wide external evaluation and validation of the project results, increase awareness, attract and engage key stakeholders and XR innovators, and ensure sustainability throughout and after the project ends.

The successfully selected use cases should build value added services based on the CORTEX² framework leveraging Startups and SMEs expertise on specific market segments. These use cases should fit in **one of the nine domains** shown in **Figure 20**.

In addition to successfully deploying the CORTEX² framework, the selected applicants will explore the integration of the most appropriate feature(s) developed under Track 1: co-development, best suited to their respective use cases.

Finally, it is expected that all newly suggested use cases will enable to assess in various contexts and environments the quality of the user experience when using the solution, the acceptability of the solution regarding the ecological and societal impact and the impacts of such immersive collaboration on the overall performance.

FOR WHO?

Track 2 extends an invitation to European technology adopters (which can work together with technology developers/providers/integrators) **to propose novel use cases for the deployment of CORTEX² framework and developed features** (coming from Track 1 Co-development winning projects).

Track 2 will finance an entity (maximum of 2) – mandatory organisation will serve as the technology adopter and the 2nd potential organisation will serve as technology developer/provider/integrator, where the use case will be applied.

As a rule, the following organisations are eligible: Startups, SMEs¹, Research Institutions like Foundations, Universities, Associations, NGOs, schools, etc.

¹ For-profit companies which are big enough NOT to be considered a SME are NOT eligible (ie: big corporates).

Figure 20 CORTEX² Track 2: Use-Case Design.

As an outcome of Open Call 1, Track 2 – **10 projects will be funded**. These projects will successfully implement their pilots, according to the selected Domain, validating CORTEX² product-market fit and showcasing the successful adoption of the developed services.

CORTEX² OPEN CALL 1 TRACK 2 USE-CASE PROGRAMME STRUCTURE

The selected third parties will be invited to participate in the CORTEX² Assistance programme. The programme has been designed to guide and assist each project and this way guarantee the success and impact expected from each of them.

Table 15 Track 2: Use Case programme.

Track 2: Use-Case				
Phase name	Duration (months)	Activity	Means of verification	Funding ⁽²⁾ % of the project budget
PHASE 1	3	Requirements	- Implementation plan, requirements, and roadmap - Deliverables required per Phase 1 ⁽¹⁾ - KPIs defined per Phase 1 ⁽¹⁾	40%
PHASE 2	5	Development/ Deployment	- MVP - Deliverables required per Phase 2 ⁽¹⁾ - KPIs defined per Phase 2 ⁽¹⁾	35%
PHASE 3	4	Validation	- System prototype demonstration in an operational environment (TRL7) - Deliverables required per Phase 3 ⁽¹⁾	25%

¹⁾ The list of deliverables and KPIs required is available in [Table 25](#).

²⁾ Associated with a positive assessment of the required deliverable(s) and KPIs.

List of available Domains for the use-case track

Please choose one of the available **Domains** to apply to Track 2 Use-Case.

If no fit is found, an applicant can apply to the **Open Domain**, submitting a proposal of work aligned with Track 2 objectives and the 12-month programme distribution.

Table 16 Domain #1 Education.

Domain #1 Education	
Challenge	The access and seamless adoption of a holistic teleconference platform with XR features offers the opportunity to revolutionize education, providing interactive and immersive learning for both students and educators. The deployment of such a solution can overcome resource constraints, language barriers, enable hands-on learning, for e.g. through the conduct of risk-free virtual chemical experiments, provide personalised, inclusive and world-wide accessible education. Finally, it can provide for an enhanced learning experience making complex topics more understandable and engaging through for e.g. 3D models and simulations. The deployment of XR telecooperation in education can thus enable numerous opportunities, inspire engagement, collaboration and creativity, transforming the way we learn and teach.

Table 17 Domain #2 Business.

Domain #2 Business	
Challenge	<p>An XR videoconferencing platform can significantly support the business sector through enhanced team collaboration. Such a tool will facilitate integration of remote participants using virtual and augmented reality techniques on the one hand, to provide remote users with a perception of visual and auditory immersion close to real presence; on the other hand, to offer a representation of the remote person to the other participants of the meeting, removing current limitations to standard teleconference platforms. In CORTEX2 participating people to a business meeting can be present locally or remotely using VR headset or a classical desktop environment (i.e., monitor). The CORTEX2 framework provides necessary tools allowing seamless integration of devices and meeting's participants inclusion. In addition, a variety of opportunities can be grasped within this domain. To name a few, the integration of such a platform can facilitate remote support and training allowing for remote technical support and employee training with interactive, hands-on experiences, enhancing efficiency and reducing downtime; Different live translation modules could be added in this challenge to facilitate the understanding during business negotiations or presentations. XR technologies can aid in designing and prototyping products, leading to faster development cycles and more informed decision-making; businesses can showcase products virtually, allowing customers to explore and experience them before making purchase decisions, and last but not least they can create innovative marketing campaigns using XR elements to engage customers and strengthen their brand presence.</p>

Table 18 Domain #3 Industry.

Domain #3 Industry	
Challenge	<p>In today's rapidly evolving landscape, industries face significant challenges such as increasing globalization, remote workforce management, complex technical operations and limited access to physical resources. An XR teleconference platform can transform the way the industry sector operates. It enables industries to overcome geographical barriers and connect teams worldwide effortlessly, fostering seamless collaboration and knowledge-sharing among experts from different corners of the globe. CORTEX² rises to the occasion by offering immersive and interactive solutions. Within this domain the platform aim is to showcase that XR immersive experience can be reached with heterogeneous and off-the-shelf mobile devices and with limited bandwidth condition while improving productivity and reducing environmental footprint. Applicants within this domain can develop their use cases in various segments for e.g.: remote technical support with XR technologies, technical experts can virtually inspect complex machinery and troubleshoot issues in real-time, reducing downtime and enhancing operational efficiency; remote workforce training becomes an engaging and hands-on experience, empowering employees to acquire critical skills and improve productivity; supply chain remote monitoring – industry actors can identify potential supplementation needs in operational environments through the utilization of data from IoT sensors. Within this domain all sectors and industries are welcomed to explore the benefits of CORTEX² and integrate additional features and modules as per their needs. Energy, Marine, Agriculture, Manufacturing, Construction, Automotive to name a few can heavily benefit from efficient and immersive cooperation and training. By leveraging XR capabilities,</p>

industries can innovate their operations, address challenges proactively, and stay ahead of the competition.

Table 19 Domain #4 Healthcare.

Domain #4 Healthcare

Challenge

A teleconference platform with cutting-edge XR features presents a transformative solution for addressing critical challenges in the healthcare sector. As healthcare professionals grapple with geographical barriers, limited access to specialized expertise, and the need for improved patient care, such a platform offers a revolutionary approach to health. Medical practitioners can engage in remote consultations and share real-time, immersive medical data, facilitating patients reach and reducing time to receiving crucial medical support. Young doctors can receive remote support and virtual assistance, through mixed reality wearable while facing a patient. They can perform simulations, and preoperative planning, leading to enhanced precision and patient outcomes. Furthermore, healthcare providers can conduct virtual medical conferences, disseminate knowledge, and participate in interactive workshops, thereby fostering continuous learning and professional development. In a nutshell the integration of CORTEX² will lead to elevating the standard of care and ensuring that patients receive the best medical attention regardless of geographic location or access to specialized facilities. By adopting such a transformative technology, healthcare professionals can revolutionize their practices, break down barriers, and improve healthcare outcomes for all.

Table 20 - Domain #5 Emergency and crisis.

Domain #5 Emergency and crisis

Challenge

In times of increasing risk or crisis, a teleconference platform equipped with XR features can become a lifeline. Amid challenges such as rapid response coordination, limited access to on-site expertise, and managing critical situations remotely, such a platform offers an indispensable solution. The overall challenge is to augment the risk prevention level during emergency operations (such as for e.g., a firefighter responding to a fire. The operating firefighter could wear AR HMD that will give additional information about its environment to help him make the right decision. They can as well get help from a real or virtual assistant and have the opportunity to record actions taken (gesture recognition, verify check list), order or commands (voice analysis), etc. 3D model reconstruction for indoor navigation in case of poor visibility can also be considered as an additional feature to be developed by the use-case in this situation. Use cases within this domain can instantiates all CORTEX² technical features (for e.g. 3D modelling, real-time collaboration, IoT integration, voice processing and virtual assistant) within a single application. It can be duplicated in any critical situation where the recording of the action, the remote support, and the visual augmentation of scene is necessary.

Table 21 - Domain #6 Entertainment and culture.

Domain #6 Entertainment and culture

<p>Challenge</p>	<p>In entertainment and culture, an XR teleconference platform can unleash a world of new possibilities. Utilizing CORTEX² can increase audience engagement, remove physical venue restrictions, and satisfy the need for novel and immersive experiences. It can be seen as a game-changer, redefining how entertainment and cultural events are experienced and shared. Live performances can be transformed into virtual spectacles, where audiences can participate and interact with artists in real-time, regardless of their physical location. Museums and cultural institutions can curate virtual exhibitions and experiences, transcending geographical boundaries and attracting a global audience. Storytelling can take on a whole new dimension with AR elements, where audiences become part of captivating narratives. By suggesting use-cases within this domain, applicants can aspire to revolutionize entertainment and culture, connecting artists and audiences in unprecedented ways, while preserving and promoting the essence of creativity and artistic expression. This domain aligns with the core value of the new European Bauhaus, promoting a harmonious coexistence between humans and the environment while embracing the transformative power of art, architecture, and culture in shaping a more sustainable and aesthetically pleasing future for all.</p>
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Table 22 - Domain #7 Smart cities.

<h2 style="text-align: center;">Domain #7 Smart cities</h2>	
<p>Challenge</p>	<p>In the smart city's domain, a teleconference platform empowered with XR features can emerge as a catalyst for urban innovation and sustainable development. It can boost urban planning, citizen engagement, and seamless collaboration among stakeholders. City planners and architects can immerse themselves in virtual city models, enabling collaborative and data-driven decision-making for optimal urban design and infrastructure. It can empower construction teams to virtually collaborate, visualize, and optimize infrastructure projects, leading to more safe, efficient, and sustainable urban development. City officials can conduct remote inspections and maintenance tasks using AR overlays, optimizing resource allocation, and minimizing downtime. Citizens can participate in virtual town hall meetings, offering their insights and feedback on proposed projects. By suggesting use-cases within this domain, applicants can support the European vision on smart cities, where innovation, sustainability, and citizen-centricity converge to create urban spaces that are resilient, accessible, and thriving. To this end CORTEX² presents an unparalleled opportunity to revolutionize how cities are designed, managed, and experienced.</p>

Table 23 - Domain #8 Accessibility and Social Inclusion.

<h2 style="text-align: center;">Domain #8 Accessibility and Social Inclusion</h2>	
<p>Challenge</p>	<p>CORTEX² can become a powerful tool to break barriers and foster an accessible and inclusive society. It can address and ameliorate physical limitations, geographical distances, and the need for equal access to opportunities for all individuals, regardless of their abilities or location. The innovative platform offers a unique opportunity to bridge these gaps and create an environment where everyone can actively participate and engage. People with disabilities can experience virtual environments and events as if they were physically present, removing accessibility barriers and fostering a sense of belonging. Remote communities can participate in social gatherings, workshops, and educational programs through immersive teleconferences, ensuring equal access to knowledge and resources. Moreover, businesses and institutions can design XR</p>

experiences that prioritize inclusivity, promoting empathy and understanding among diverse audiences. Applicants within this domain should suggest use cases that support the improvement of CORTEX² accessibility and usability framework. Use cases will leverage on the XR gesture module developed for AR/VR gesture recognition, and can for e.g., develop further the platform integrated vocal assistant to a chat bot for deaf individuals. By suggesting use-cases within this domain, applicants can unlock the full potential of this technology in promoting accessibility and social inclusion, creating a society where everyone's voice is heard, and opportunities are within reach for all.

Table 24 - Domain #9 Open Domain.

Domain #9 Open Domain

Challenge	If you don't see a predefined challenge that aligns with your needs, you can propose a use case within a domain of your choice. We are eager to explore new areas where CORTEX ² can foster collaboration and create new opportunities. Submit your own use case.
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Table 25 - Use-Case Track Requirements.

Use-Case Track Requirements

TRL	Minimum TRL 4 Final TRL 7
Source code availability	The created software can be provided either as open-source code, or as proprietary code.
Standards	Not mandatory; Depending on the domain it can be a specific industry standard
Programming language	C++, C#, Python, Nodejs
Ethics	<p>All Artificial Intelligence software or techniques co-developed in the course of CORTEX² must be compliant with the Assessment checklist for trustworthy AI as proposed by the High-level expert group on AI (AI HLEG). The complete document can be retrieved from the website of the European Commission to conduct a self-assessment. Hence, the applicants must conduct a self-assessment to ensure that the proposed solution adheres to the ethical requirements in the assessment list, namely.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Human Agency and oversight ii. Technical robustness and safety iii. Privacy and data protection iv. Transparency v. Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness vi. Societal and environmental well-being vii. Accountability <p>In addition, the applicant must assess the possibility and disclose whether their proposed solutions, software or the techniques have dual use (military application) or are capable of being misused (illegal or unethical purposes or used to violate human rights or compromise the safety of humans, animals or the environment). To this end, the applicant must disclose the capabilities of all co-developed components or software.</p>
Security	The applicant must implement the appropriate privacy-preserving techniques, safeguards, security, measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data concerning the development, deployment and use phases of the co-developed software components.

	The applicant must disclose the possible and known risks and vulnerabilities concerning cybersecurity of the co-developed software or components.		
Data management	The applicant must outline how data would be collected, generated and/or processed with details of the type of data/metadata they intend to use and the origin of such data, the quality assurance of such data. Details on how the applicant intends to comply with the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) must be provided along with storage, security, and re-use plans for such data.		
IPR Co-creation	The applicant or the end-user cannot become the sole operator for this use-case		
Other(s)	Participants should accept to conduct user studies and publish the results in scientific conferences/journals.		
Ideal candidate	An organisation with an interest in exploiting XR services in practice and integrating them to its standard processes. An SME/startup as a tech developer in the selected domain who relates to the proposed challenge and is interested in exploring the value brought by new technologies to them.		
Minimum deliverables required (M-month D-deliverable)	Phase 1 (M3) Requirements	Phase 2 (M8) Development/ Deployment	Phase 3 (M12) Validation
	D1. Specification and Implementation plan (including UX, requirements and detailed roadmap for CORTEX ² framework integration, development and deployment of the use-case) D2. Performance Report (End of Phase 1)	D3. Demonstration of a “Minimum Viable Product” D4. Performance Report (End of Phase 2)	D5. Evaluation report (Gathering the assessment of the use-case regarding the technical, economical, ecological and sociological impact of the solution. Need to include the user satisfaction study) D6. Video demonstrating the use-case D7. Exploitation Plan
KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Successful deployment of the use case in the selected domain (Target value – minimum 1) • KPI 2: 3 different scenarios supported for the specific domain • KPI 3: A user study with at least 10 users, when possible more than 20 users should be conducted and documented as user experience feedback in link with technical performance (accuracy, latency, speed when it applies) • KPI 4: Nb of CORTEX² services implemented in the domain app (>= 1) • KPI5 (for business related domains): Measurement of solution impact on efficiency, operational costs reduction, and customer outcomes improvement. 		
Resources provided by CORTEX ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CORTEX² Architecture (Rainbow Multimodal Collaborative Platform) • Platform administration, cloud hosting and open API • Access to developed modules and services from OC Track 1 to be integrated within the use - case • An assigned technical contact person from CORTEX² • Integration and validation support • Dissemination of achievements 		
Expected final outcome	The final outcome should be the demonstrated use of the CORTEX ² framework, including actual users in the selected domain. This should be supported by a user satisfaction study and documented in a report.		

3. Eligibility criteria

All applicants for both tracks will have to abide by all general requirements described in this section to be considered eligible for CORTEX². Eligibility check verifies that:

- Submissions are made **ONLY** through the F6S platform in the space enabled for the CORTEX² Open Call #1 within the defined deadline.
 - a. For **Track 1 Co-development** applications should be submitted using the following address: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-1-co-development/apply>
 - b. For **Track 2 Use-case** applications should be submitted using the following address: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-2-use-case/apply>
- Applicants are legal entities established in an eligible Horizon Europe Country, as indicated in section **Eligible countries**.
- The Application as well as the requested documents are provided **ONLY** in English language.
- The Proposal description is submitted according to the Guidelines for Applicants and provided templates.
- Maximum 2 entities per submitted project are accepted.
- Not exceeding the maximum budget request per application track.
- Complete application which includes the requested administrative data, and any obligatory supporting documents specified in the call (per track).

A Proposal is only considered eligible if its content corresponds specifically to the requirements of Topics/Domains available (per Track application) of the CORTEX² Open Call #1, including the specific eligibility conditions set out in the relevant parts of the Guidelines for Applicants.

The applications that do not comply with those criteria will be excluded and marked as ineligible.

3.1 **Confidentiality and deadline**

Any information regarding the proposal will be treated in a strictly confidential manner. Only proposals submitted before the deadline will be accepted. **After the call closure, no additions or changes to the received proposals will be considered.**

Submission to the CORTEX² Open Call #1 is open between the **24th of October 2023, 00:00 CET** (Brussels time) and the **16th of January 2024 at 17:00 CET** (Brussels time). Proposals must be submitted before the deadline.

The deadline hour of submission is not flexible, as the online form will be automatically disabled at the day and hour defined as the deadline - Open Call#1 deadline: 16th January 2024 17:00 CET (Brussels time).

To avoid missing the deadline, the applicants are strongly encouraged to submit the Proposal as soon as possible.

3.2 **Type of Beneficiary (Applicant)**

CORTEX² will fund third-party projects that may be from:

- a single entity or a team of 2 entities (all of them MUST be a Tech SME/Startup) **(applicable for Track 1: co-development)**
- a single entity (MUST be an end-user/tech adopter) or a consortium of a maximum of two entities (tech adopter and a tech developer/provider/integrator) **(applicable for Track 2: use-case)**

These entities are eligible under the following conditions:

- An organization based in the EU or any Horizon Europe associated member state.
- A SME following the EU definition by the [Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC](#) and in the [SME user guide](#)
- Secondary and higher education establishments, research institutes and other not-for-profit research entities like Foundations, Universities, Associations, NGOs, etc. **(applicable for Track 2: use-case)**

IMPORTANT: For-profit companies which are big enough NOT to be considered a SME are **NOT eligible** (ie: big corporates) to receive funding.

3.2.1 SME eligibility

Micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are considered eligible ONLY if complying with the European Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC and the SME user guide. In summary, the criteria which define an SME are:

- a. The headcount in the Annual Work Unit (AWU) is less than 250.
- b. Annual turnover less or equal to €50 million OR annual balance sheet total less or equal to €43 million.

Startups that do not have yet annual turnover or balance sheets are also considered eligible given that they fulfil the criteria (a) and (b) at submission time.

In addition, the following conditions apply:

- The applying SMEs should not:
 - have convictions for fraudulent behaviour, other financial irregularities, or unethical or illegal business practices.
 - have been declared bankrupt or have initiated bankruptcy procedures.
 - Be under liquidation or an enterprise under difficulty accordingly to the Commission Regulation No 651/2014, art. 2.18
 - Be excluded from the possibility of obtaining EU funding under the provisions of both national and EU law, or by a decision of both national or EU authority
- Proposals must ensure that there is no risk of double funding. The fundamental principle underpinning the rules for public expenditure in the EU states that no costs for the same activity can be funded twice from the EU budget, as defined in Article 111 of Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1605/2002 of 25 June 2002 on the Financial Regulation.

3.3 Eligible countries

Entities legally established in any of the following countries (hereafter collectively identified as the “Eligible Countries”) are eligible:

- The Member States (MS) of the European Union (EU), including their outermost regions.
- The Overseas Countries and Territories (OCT) linked to the Member States².
- Horizon Europe associated countries (Association to Horizon Europe is governed by the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695): according to the updated list published by the EC³

The UK applicants are not eligible under the conditions set by the EC for Horizon Europe participation at the time of the deadline of the call.

3.4 Proposal submission

Proposals must be submitted electronically, using the CORTEX² Online Submission Service accessible via the F6S platform at:

- www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-1-co-development/apply for Track 1 and,
- www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-2-use-case/apply for Track 2

Proposals submitted by any other means will NOT be evaluated.

3.4.1 Multiple Submissions

This call is competitive. Multiple applications are not recommended, as:

- **ONLY** one proposal per team will be accepted.
- An entity can be granted **ONLY** once.

Note that the regular functioning of the F6S platform limits to one application submission per F6S user in each call.

If an F6S user wishes to submit more than one application, for example on behalf of different legal entities, the F6S user should request support from the F6S support team support@f6s.com at **least 10 days prior the open call deadline**.

3.5 Language

English is the official language for CORTEX² Open Call. Submissions done in any other language will be disregarded and not evaluated.

English is also the only official language during the whole execution of the CORTEX² programme for both tracks. This means that it is mandatory that the submission of deliverables is done in English to be eligible.

² Entities from Overseas Countries and Territories (OCT) are eligible for funding under the same conditions as entities from the Member States to which the OCT in question is linked.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_horizon-euratom_en.pdf

3.6 Conflict of interest

IMPORTANT: To avoid conflicts of interest, applications will not be accepted from persons or organisations who are partners in the CORTEX² consortium or who are formally linked in any way to partners of the consortium. Please check the list of partners at <https://cortex2.eu/team/>

Applicants shall not have any actual or/and potential conflict of interest with the CORTEX² selection process and during the whole project. The winning applicants will be required to declare that they know of no such potential conflicts of interest by submitting **ANNEX 3 - CORTEX2 Declaration of Honour** during the contracting phase.

All suspected cases of conflict of interest will be assessed case by case. In particular, applicants must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests').

4. HOW TO APPLY?

The submission will be done through the F6S platform.

For Track 1 Co-development at: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-1-co-development/apply> and for Track 2 Use cases at: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-2-use-case/apply>

Both links are directly linked to the [project website](#). The applicants are required to register a profile at F6S to submit a proposal. The templates to the Open Call 1 documents are available [here](#). These are:

- **Annex 2 Application Form at F6S:** The form is extracted as document for reference purposes only. The Application form should be directly filled at the F6S platform.
- **Annex 2.1 Proposal Template for Track 1 co-development** or **Annex 2.2 Proposal Template for Track 2 use-cases:** a document that must be submitted in a pdf format containing the description of the proposed project and uploaded as part of the application form at the F6S platform.
- **Annex 3 Declaration of Honour:** a template of the declaration of no conflict of interest and that all conditions related to the CORTEX² Open Call #1 are accepted by the applying entity(ies). Upon acceptance of their proposal for funding, the signed and stamped declaration must be submitted.
- **Annex 4 SME Declaration:** Check section **3.2.1**. Upon acceptance of their proposal for funding, the signed and stamped declaration must be submitted.

The project proposals must strictly adhere to the F6S application form, which defines sections, required Annexes, and the overall length. Participants are requested to carefully read and follow the instructions in the form. Additional material, which has not been specifically requested in the online application form, will not be considered for the evaluation of the proposals and may be subject to withdrawal from the evaluation.

Applying to an open call takes time and dedication and we would like to make sure that you understand the crucial rules:

- **Be on time:** Make sure you submit your proposal through the F6S platform before the deadline of **16 January 2024, 17:00 CET**. If you submit the form correctly, the system will send you a confirmation of your submission (please check your SPAM folder as well). Proposals submitted by any other means are ineligible, hence will not be evaluated.
- **F6S application:** The F6S platform allows you to work flexibly on the content, which is automatically saved once you progress filling out the form. All members of your team can have access to the application form and contribute to the work.
- **Be exhaustive:** Have you answered all the sections of the form and uploaded all required Annexes? It will not be possible to add any information after you submit your application or reach the submission deadline.
- **Every question deserves your attention:** All sections of your proposal must be filled in. Make sure that the data provided is true and complete. This is crucial for us to properly assess your proposal.
- **Documentation format:** Any document requested in any of the phases must be submitted electronically in PDF format without restrictions for printing.

NOTE 1: It is strongly recommended to not wait till the last moment of submission. **Failure of the Proposal to arrive in time for any reason, including communications delays, or network issues is not acceptable as an extenuating circumstance and will automatically lead to rejection of the submission.**

The time of receipt of the proposal as recorded by the submission system will be definitive.

NOTE 2: Please note that after application submission, editing is not possible. If the applicant discovers an error in the proposal and provided the call deadline has not passed, the applicant may request the Open Call CORTEX² team to re-submit the proposal (for this purpose please contact us at opencall@cortex2.eu with a message titled: RESUBMISSION REQUEST). However, CORTEX² is not committed that resubmission in time will be feasible in case the request for resubmission is not received by the Open Call CORTEX² team at least 48 hours before the call deadline.

5. EVALUATION PROCESS

The evaluation process is shown in [Figure 21](#).

Figure 21- Evaluation process.

5.1 Step 1- Eligibility Check

Eligibility to participate in the funding programme is initially verified against several eligibility criteria. This process is carried out by the CORTEX² team. A proposal may be declared ineligible or inadmissible at any stage. The check will verify:

- **Proposals reception:** via F6S and by the defined deadline.
- **Eligibility filter:** Eligibility check will verify the existence of a legal entity in an eligible country, the uniqueness of the Proposal, the existence of the same entity in other proposals, the alignment with CORTEX² call for Proposals, and any conflict of interest. In addition, the following information will be checked:
 - All entities are eligible for EC funding under the rules of Horizon Europe [Y/N]
 - Track 1 application has a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 2 partners [Y/N]
 - Track 2 application has a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 2 partners [Y/N]
 - The proposed project is aligned to the Open Call 1 objective, specific per Track application [Y/N]
 - The Proposal is written in English [Y/N]
 - All required documentation as Annex 2.1 or 2.2, are submitted correctly [Y/N]
 - The Proposal does not exceed the maximum available funding per selected Track [Y/N]

The eligible Proposals will be given to external evaluators to initiate the remote evaluation. The non-eligible applicants will be informed by email. **No additional feedback will be given.**

5.2 Step 2 - External remote evaluation

Proposals considered eligible will move on to the external remote evaluation phase. The external evaluation will be done remotely by expert evaluators. Evaluators will be selected from a pool of experts that will be established through a call for expressions of interest. The experts will be evaluated and selected based on their knowledge of the CORTEX² challenges topics and general experience in the evaluation of proposals (e.g., Horizon 2020, HE, FSTP programmes). Expert profiles will be evaluated, and a pool of experts will be established. The top-ranked experts will be invited to evaluate proposals.

The evaluators will perform evaluations on an individual basis, not as representatives of their employer, their country, or any other entity. They are required to be independent, impartial, and objective. All evaluators are required to sign a contract, which includes a declaration of confidentiality and the absence of conflicts of interest. Any known conflict of interest will be immediately communicated to the CORTEX² Open Call team. Evaluators will also be bound by strict confidentiality regarding the evaluation process and during the evaluation process.

At least two external evaluators will evaluate each proposal and will be distributed across the proposals based on their expertise and, whenever possible, country of origin.

5.2.1 Evaluation criteria

The evaluators will follow the 4 evaluation criteria listed in [Table 26](#).

The independent experts will score each award criterion on a scale from 0 to 5 (decimal and centesimal point scores may be given):

- **0= Fail:** The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information.
- **1 = Poor:** criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
- **2 = Fair:** proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
- **3 = Good:** proposal addresses the criterion well, but a few shortcomings are present.
- **4 = Very good:** proposal addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present.
- **5 = Excellent:** proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

The final score (including for each criterion) is calculated based on the average of the scores provided by the evaluators. The **threshold for each criterion is three (3)**, therefore the overall score threshold is 12. This indicates that if a proposal scores less than 3 in any criterion or an overall score less than 12, the proposal is automatically rejected. Each evaluator will record his/her individual assessment of each proposal using an Individual Evaluation Report (IER). The evaluators will then hold a consensus meeting to prepare a single consensus Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) for each proposal, representing opinions and scores on which the evaluators agree and which they will sign.

Table 20 CORTEX2 Open Call #1 evaluation criteria.

CORTEX ² Open Call #1 evaluation criteria			
Remote Evaluation Criteria	Track 1: co-development	Track 1: use-case	Threshold
	Scope of evaluation	Scope of evaluation	
Technical Excellence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level of innovation and technological challenges addressed. Concept fit to the call track and the 9-month programme; Application must demonstrate a clear set of technical objectives per selected Topic of application. Quality, credibility, and clarity of the technical description of how to achieve the objectives. Level of integration with CORTEX² technologies to test and validate. Feasibility of the proposed work and technological contribution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Level of innovation and technological challenges addressed. Concept fit to the call track and the 12-month programme; Application must demonstrate a clear set of technical objectives per selected Domain. Quality, credibility, and clarity of the technical description of how to achieve the objectives. Level of integration with CORTEX² technologies to test and validate. Feasibility of the proposed work and technological contribution. 	3/5
Ambition & Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applicants must define their ambitions and a clear set of expectations aligned with the objectives of the Call Track 1. Proposals must demonstrate impact on the CORTEX² framework and its contribution to the XR ecosystem. Overall impact of the proposed project if successful. XR Industrial relevance and exploitation plans. Gender/accessibility/inclusion impact addressed, if applicable. Quality of the exploitation plan and market potential. Effectiveness of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate. Potential of the outcomes to be adopted/used by other entities into regular practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applicants must define their ambitions and a clear set of expectations aligned with the objectives of the Call Track 2. Proposals must demonstrate impact on the CORTEX² framework, on the industry/market that will be addressed and its contribution to the XR ecosystem. Overall impact of the proposed use case. XR industrial relevance of the proposed use case if successful. Level of engagement with the required end users and other stakeholders involved. Gender/accessibility/inclusion impact addressed. Effectiveness of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate the use-case results. Potential of the outcomes to be adopted/used by other entities in regular practices. Product concept, market. 	3/5
Team Skills & Expertise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality of the entity (ies). Clarity of each partner role, if applicable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality of the entity (ies). Clarity of each partner role, if applicable. 	3/5

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical capacity and excellence of the technology developer/provider. • Quality of the individual participants competences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical capacity and excellence of the technology developer/provider • Quality of the individual participants competences. 	
Project Planning & Value for Money	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality, effectiveness and clarity of project activities, structure, and timing. • Appropriateness of deliverables, KPIs and means of verification. • Allocation of appropriate resources to the proposed project. • Justification of the proposed resources and their deployment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality, effectiveness and clarity of project activities, structure, and timing. • Appropriateness of deliverables, KPIs and means of verification. • Allocation of appropriate resources to the proposed use case. • Justification of the proposed resources and their deployment. 	3/5

5.3 Step 3 - Intermediate ranking of proposals

At the end of the evaluation process (Step 2), all proposals will be ranked in into two lists – Track 1 and Track 2. The primary rule for ranking proposals will be based on their overall average score (summary of criterion 1 to 4), while considering the minimum and maximum number of proposals per Topic (track 1) and Domain (track 2) to be selected. In case there are an insufficient number of proposals for all Topics and Domains (total or that have not met the threshold), the top-ranked proposals from existing Topics and Domains will be selected. In the case there are proposals in the same position, tie-breaks will be addressed by giving priority to the proposals with the highest score in specific criteria, considering the following order:

- Rule 1: Proposals will be ranked based on their overall score (sum of scores for criteria 1 to 4).
- Rule 2: After applying Rule 1 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have the highest score on Ambition & Impact.
- Rule 3: After applying Rule 2 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have the highest score on Technical Excellence.
- Rule 4: After applying Rule 3 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have the highest score on Team Skills & Expertise.
- Rule 5: After applying Rule 4 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have the highest score on Project Planning & Value for Money.
- Rule 6: After applying Rule 5 and if there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to those addressing gender/accessibility/inclusion impact.

The top-ranked proposals – at least 15 of proposals to be funded per track (tentatively 10 proposals per track) – will be invited to an online interview. Furthermore, at least 2 proposals within each Topic (Track 1) and each Domain (Track 2) (if their score meet the minimum threshold) will be invited to the online interview. This applies in the case that proposals have been submitted to all tracks' Topics and Domains.

5.4 Step 4: Consensus meeting

Evaluators involved in the remote evaluation will carry out a consensus meeting with the objective of gathering their evaluations, defining a common score for the proposals, and preparing evaluation reports.

5.5 Step 5: Online interview

The objective of the interview is to better understand the proposal, particularly its quality and excellence, the expected impact and exploitation potential, quality of the workplan, and quality of the applicant(s). Any complementary material that can support the presentation of the project is acceptable during the interview. Interviews will be carried out by a selection of the internal evaluators. Members of the CORTEX² team directly involved in the selected Topic (track 1) and Domain (track 2) that each Proposal is addressing will participate in the interview and respective evaluation process. Interviews are expected to last approximately 30-45 min. The Applicants are expected to prepare and present a presentation (approximately 15 minutes) and answer any questions regarding their proposal from the evaluators. At least 2 evaluators are expected to participate in each interview.

The online interviews will evaluate proposals against the following evaluation criteria:

Table 21 Interview evaluation criteria.

Interview criteria	Description
Concept & Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment with/ contribution to CORTEX² (Topic/Domain) and its ecosystem. • Quality and novelty of the proposed project concept and innovation (technology focused).
Impact & Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact on the XR ecosystem. • Path towards exploitation/market of results.
Workplan & Applicants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rationale and ambition of the workplan. • Capacity and experience of the applicant. • Any risks and mitigation plans. • Rationale of the project budget and resources.

As with the external remote evaluation, internal evaluators will score each criterion between 0 and 5. If at any time during the interview the applicants do not commit to what was included in the submitted proposal, the proposal will be automatically disqualified. If after the interview process the evaluators still have questions, the applicant may be requested to provide additional information in writing.

5.6 Step 6: Final ranking and selection

After the online interview process, all proposals will be ranked according to the average scores obtained from (1) the external remote evaluation and (2) the online interviews. Ten proposals

will be selected for each track (total of 20). All eligible Proposals will receive an acceptance or rejection letter together with an anonymised version of their Evaluation Summary Report (ESR). Proposals not having passed to the online interview stage will receive a report with results of the external remote evaluation. Proposals that passed to the online interview will receive a report with information from both the remote evaluation and interview stages.

5.6.1 Redress process

An applicant may submit a request for redress if they believe the results of the eligibility checks have not been correctly applied, or if they feel that there has been a shortcoming in the application of the rules of the CORTEX² - Open Call #1. Requests for redress must:

- Be received within three (3) working days from the reception of (1) a rejection letter considering the proposal as non-eligible or (2) the ESR information letter.
- Indicate the subject of the complaint and clearly describe it, with arguments/ evidence that sustain the complaint.
- Be sent by the entity's legal representative that has also submitted the proposal. In case a request for redress is received, an internal review committee from CORTEX² will examine the applicant's complaint. The committee will review the complaint and recommend an appropriate course of action. If there is clear evidence of a shortcoming that could affect the eventual funding decision, it is possible that all or part of the proposal will be re-evaluated.

Please note:

- This procedure is concerned only with the eligibility/ evaluation organisation process.
- The committee will not question the scientific or technical judgement of the expert evaluators applied in evaluating the proposals.
- A re-evaluation will only be carried out if there is evidence of a shortcoming that affects the final decision on whether to fund the proposal or not.
- The evaluation score following any re-evaluation will be regarded as definitive. It may be lower than the original score.
- Anonymous or incomplete complaints will not be considered.
- Only one request for redress per Proposal will be considered by the committee. All requests for redress will be treated in confidence and must be sent to CORTEX² at: opencall@cortex2.eu

6. CONTRACTING

6.1 Sub-granted project negotiation and onboarding

At the end of the evaluation phase, ten proposals from each track will be selected. The other proposals that were invited to the interview stage will remain on a reserve list in case one of the selected proposals fails to sign the sub-grant agreement.

6.2 Contract preparation

After the Open Call evaluation conclusion and project selection, the CORTEX² coordinator will start the contract preparation in collaboration with the selected proposals' coordinators. Contract preparation will go via administrative and financial checking (and potentially into technical or ethical/security negotiations) based on evaluators' comments. On a case-by-case approach, a phone call or teleconference may be needed for clarification.

The objective of the contract preparation is fulfilling the legal requirements between CORTEX² Consortium and every beneficiary of the call. The items covered will be:

1. Inclusion of the comments (if any) in the ESR of the Proposals and mapping to the Sub-grant agreement (Contract).
2. Validation of the legal documents

The objective of the contract preparation is to fulfil the legal requirements (**Table 28**) between the CORTEX² consortium and each beneficiary of the open call.

Note: the contract as provided to the sub-grantee is final and may not be changed, including the addition or removal of any articles or other content. All documentation that requires a signature (e.g., Declaration of Honour, SME Declaration (if applicable), Bank Account, and sub-grant agreement must be signed by hand (e.g., with the same signature on the identity card) or with a valid electronic digital signature. CORTEX² reserves the right to request one or the other types of signatures for specific documentation.

Table 22 Requirements for contract preparation

Legal requirement	Description
Proof of legal existence	Company register, official journal or other official document per country showing the name of the organisation, the legal address and registration number and a copy of a document proving VAT registration (in case the VAT number does not show on the registration extract or its equivalent)
Specific to SMEs	
1. Proof of the SME condition is required:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● If the applicant has been fully validated as an SME on the Beneficiary Register Participant Portal, the PIC number must be provided. ● If the applicant has not been fully validated as an SME on the Participant Portal, the following documents will be required to prove the status as an SME: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SME Declaration (Annex 4) signed (with a valid e-signature or by hand) and stamped: In the event the beneficiary declares being non-autonomous, the balance sheet and profit and loss account (with annexes) for the last period for upstream and downstream organisations is required. ○ Status Information Form, which includes the headcount (AWU), balance, profit & loss accounts of the latest closed financial year and the relation, upstream and downstream, of any linked or partner company. 	

2. Supporting documents. In cases where either the number of employees or the ownership is not clearly identified: any other supporting documents which demonstrate headcount and ownership such as payroll details, annual reports, national regional, association records, etc.	
Declaration of Honour (Annex 3)	Signed declaration that all conditions related to the CORTEX ² Open Call #1 are accepted by the applying entity (s).
Sub-grant agreement (Annex 5)	Signed between the CORTEX ² consortium, represented by its coordinator (DFKI), and the beneficiary. The sub-grant agreement will also include the comments (if any) of the proposal's ESR to the work plan.
Bank account information (Annex 6)	The account where the funds will be transferred will be indicated via a specific form signed by the entity, individuals, and the bank owners. The holder of the account will be the entity/ individual.

It should be emphasised that each SME should provide at contract preparation time a valid VAT identification number. Failure to provide the VAT⁴ number will automatically result in proposal rejection.

The request, by CORTEX² Consortium, for the above documentation will be done within predefined deadlines. In general, the sub-project negotiation should be concluded within 2 weeks. An additional week may be provided by the CORTEX² coordinator in case of significant reasoning. In case contracting has not been concluded within the above period, the Proposal is automatically rejected and the next proposal on the reserve list is invited.

6.3 Contract signature

At the end of the contracting phase, the sub-grantee funding agreement will be signed between the CORTEX² Consortium represented by its coordinator (DFKI), and the selected beneficiary, represented by its leader.

In case of applying consortia, the consortium leader and the other consortium partners are responsible to make an agreement that shall cover the rights and obligations between them.

7. ACTIVITIES DURING THE FUNDED PROGRAMME

7.1 Track 1 co-development (9-month programme)

7.1.1 Sprint 1

Sprint 1 is associated with the starting point of each project and will have a maximum duration of 3 months. Within this phase, the beneficiary must fine-tune their planning and technology usage with CORTEX², design a detailed development plan aligned with the CORTEX² objectives and perform their technical developments.

The Development sprint should include the following:

⁴ To be checked at European Commission services such as http://ec.europa.eu/taxation_customs/vies/

- Description of how the project will be carried out.
- Description of the technologies to use.
- Reporting of the technical development.
- List of detailed milestones and KPIs to achieve (metrics and target values for how the success will be determined).

At the end of Sprint 1, Beneficiary(ies) will have to deliver the assigned deliverable as a means of verification of work performed. It must include a publishable summary of the results obtained at this stage. A specific report can be requested by the CORTEX² team.

7.1.2 Sprint 2

Within this sprint, projects will perform their integration to achieve what has been previously developed. The Beneficiary(ies) should consider the following:

- Reporting of the implementation.
- Configuration of units and software.
- Reporting of the operation initiation.
- Reporting of technology deployment by the end-user.
- Collection of relevant data.
- Project performance (in terms of quantitative KPIs identified in the previous phase).
- Proof that the CORTEX² tech offering has been used and integrated for the project purposes.
- Provide a Demo (including a video to be published on the CORTEX² YouTube channel).

At the end of the Sprint 2, Beneficiary(ies) will have to deliver the assigned deliverable as a means of verification of work performed. It must include a publishable summary of the results obtained at this stage. A specific report can be requested by the CORTEX² team.

7.1.3 Sprint 3

Sprint 3 is critical to leverage the results of the previous Sprints. The aim is to validate the co-development performed and foster the exploitation of project results. Within this phase, projects must focus on the validation, assessment, and exploitation of results/achievements. The assessment and exploitation should include the following:

- A demonstrator and a report on the developed feature.
- For exploitation: a business plan for the exploitation of the result.
- Presentation of the final module with a documentation.
- Validation of the source code of the final product, if applicable.
- Upload the source code on a repository on git, if applicable.

At the end of Sprint 3, Beneficiary(ies) will have to deliver the assigned deliverable as a means of verification of work performed. It must include a publishable summary of the project's results and feedback to the obligatory Impact Assessment that will be run by the Open Call management. A specific report can be requested by the CORTEX² team.

7.2 Track 2 Use-case (12 -month programme)

7.2.1 Phase 1 Requirements

Track 2 Phase 1 is associated with the starting point of each project and will have a maximum duration of 3 months. Within this phase, Beneficiary(ies) must set the implementation plan, including key requirements and roadmap for the development and deployment of the use – case within the selected domain. The implementation plan shall be aligned with the integration of CORTEX² and the fulfilment of the project’s objectives.

The Requirements phase should include the following:

- Description of how the project will be carried out.
- Description of the technologies to use.
- Reporting of the technical development.
- List of detailed milestones, deliverables and KPIs to achieve (metrics and target values for how the success will be determined).
- POC illustrating the use-case and the technology they will bring.
- User stories, if applicable.

At the end of the Phase 1, Beneficiary(ies) will have to deliver the assigned deliverable as a means of verification of work performed. It must include a publishable summary of the results obtained at this stage. A specific report can be requested by the CORTEX² team.

7.2.2 Phase 2 Development/Deployment

Phase 2 lasts 5 months. Projects will perform their development and deployment, based on the implementation plan developed in Phase 1. The Beneficiary(ies) should consider the following:

- Development and showcasing of an MVP.
- Provision of a Technical and Performance Report, including the collection of relevant data.
- Provision of additional deliverables and proof of achieved KPIs as per the requirements and implementation plan of the applicant.

Reports provided must include a publishable summary of the results obtained at this stage. A specific report can be requested by the CORTEX² team.

7.2.3 Phase 3 Validation

Phase 3 lasts 4 months. This phase is critical to leverage the results of the previous Phases. The aim is to validate the use case and foster the exploitation of project results. Within this phase, projects must focus on the validation, assessment, and exploitation of results/achievements. The assessment and exploitation should include the following:

- System prototype demonstration in an operational environment (TRL7).
- Deliverables and KPIs required as per Track 2 use-case.
- Materials for communication & dissemination.
- Proposal for an exploitation plan.
- Video demonstrating the use case.

Report of a user study to assess the use case, with a minimum of 10 users. Participants should accept to conduct user studies and publish the results in scientific conferences/journals.

At the end of Phase 3, Beneficiaries will have to deliver the assigned deliverable as a means of verification of work performed. It must include a publishable summary of the project's results and feedback to the obligatory Impact Assessment that will be run by the Open Call management. A specific report can be requested by the CORTEX² team.

7.3 Track 1 and Track 2 Evaluation

The milestones, KPIs and deliverables will be evaluated at the end of each Sprint/Phase. A remote review will take place after each phase to evaluate the progress of the Beneficiary(ies).

The sub-granted project must submit to the CORTEX² consortium the deliverable(s)/report(s) corresponding to each Sprint/Phase by the last calendar day of the respective Sprint/Phase, unless otherwise indicated by the CORTEX² consortium.

The review will be remote via a teleconference platform. The Beneficiary will make a presentation of the work done, analyse the progress and answer questions from the CORTEX² experts.

After the review, the Beneficiary will receive a review report, including comments and potential recommendations. The report will also state if the deliverables are accepted or not. On acceptance of the deliverables, payments will be released no later than thirty (30) natural days after the notification by the Contractor.

On rejection of any of the deliverables, or in case of not satisfactory review, the Beneficiary(ies) will be requested to re-submit improved deliverables. Based on that update, the CORTEX² experts will take decision if the project can continue to the next Phase, or if the risk of failure is too high. If the rejection of a deliverable or an unsatisfactory review happens in the last Sprint/Phase (3) the CORTEX² Consortium will consider if a short extension can be conceded to invite a project to update and resubmit deliverables, hence qualifying for its payment, if and when said deliverable is approved.

7.4 Participation in events

During the three Sprints/Phases, the selected Beneficiary(ies) should participate in various types of events (audio calls, video calls, webinars, online training, virtual conferences, etc.) organized or suggested by the CORTEX² Consortium, to support the integration of their solution in the CORTEX² framework, extend their knowledge on the CORTEX² project, XR-related technologies, and its market.

8. Resources and tailored support provided within CORTEX² Assistance Programme

Within the duration of the programme each Beneficiary will be appointed a **mentor** and a **monitor**.

The mentor is an individual, from the CORTEX² consortium with expertise in the topics and solutions being addressed within the project. The mentor will be responsible for supporting, providing feedback, motivating, and evaluating the Beneficiary.

Specifically, the mentor will:

- Organise regular calls with the assigned project (e.g., once every month or as agreed with the mentor).
- Ensure that the work plan, deliverables, and project reports are delivered on time.
- Follow the project's progress towards achievement of defined KPIs and results (sub-granted project progress).
- Provide a technical evaluation of the deliverables and reports submitted by the Beneficiary, including approval, rejection, or request for improvements.
- Engage with other CORTEX² partners to discuss needs from the sub-granted project.

The monitor acts as an administrative contact during the implementation of the project. The monitor will liaise with the sub-granted project's assigned mentor to ensure its successful implementation.

Specifically, the monitor will:

- Monitor the progress of the project with the support of a monthly survey.
- Liaise with the project's monitor about the progress of the respective project and discuss any issues arising in the monthly survey.
- Collect the deliverables and reports from the beneficiary and share them with the respective mentor for evaluation.
- Organize the reviews at the end of each Sprint/Phase.
- Report to the CORTEX² coordination with progress for reporting purposes.

In addition to the recurrent monitoring and mentoring, CORTEX² will also provide the projects with tailored support with the objective of maximising the exploitation and commercialisation potential of the projects, such as:

- CORTEX²- Rainbow Multimodal Collaborative Platform - administration, cloud hosting and open API.
- Tailored expert support depending on the selected co-development Topic/use case Domain.
- Integration and validation support.
- Dissemination of achievements.

8. FINANCIAL SUPPORT PROVIDED

8.1 Financial support

For accessing the funding, the third-party projects deployment needs to demonstrate and present proofs of their progress and achievements and the deliverables presented must be assessed positively in each of the stages. In case of missing the above, the third-parties are not paid and may be requested to not participate longer in the CORTEX² project.

The grant received by the third-parties is to finance:

- Work performed by employees of the third-party.

- Investment in software/ hardware (only the value associated with its depreciation).
- Travels associated with the project deployment or CORTEX² activities.
- Participation in events/ conferences and promotion campaigns associated with CORTEX²
- Minor (<15%) subcontracting of non-key domain expertise is allowed but must be justified.

8.1.1 Track 1 co-development

Selected 10 projects will become part of CORTEX² activities for the 9 months period composed of 3 Sprints. Payments will be done in 3 instalments (40% + 35% + 25%) based on concrete results, deliverables, and review of each Sprint. Summary of funding:

Table 23 Track 1 Co-development Budget distribution

Programme Sprint	Duration	Funding	Example of €100.000
SPRINT 1	3 months	40%	€ 40.000
SPRINT 2	3 months	35%	€ 35.000
SPRINT 3	3 months	25%	€ 25.000

Detailed payment schedule and payment conditions will be settled in [the Sub-grant \(Beneficiary\) Agreement \(Annex 5\)](#).

8.1.2 Track 2 use-case

The selected 10 projects will become part of CORTEX² activities for the 12 months period composed of 3 Phases. Payments will be done in 3 instalments (40% + 35% + 25%) based on concrete results, deliverables, and review of each phase. Summary of funding:

Table 24 Track 2 Use case Budget distribution

Programme Phase	Duration	Funding	Example of €200.000
Phase 1	3 months	40%	€ 80.000
Phase 2	5 months	35%	€ 70.000
Phase 3	4 months	25%	€ 50.000

Detailed payment schedule and payment conditions will be settled in [the Sub-grant \(Beneficiary\) Agreement \(Annex 5\)](#).

9. RESPONSIBILITY OF BENEFICIARIES

The selected third-party is indirect Beneficiary of the EC funding. As such, they are responsible for the proper use of the funding and ensure that the recipients comply with obligations under Horizon Europe specific requirements as described in Horizon Europe.

9.1 Data protection and confidentiality

During the implementation of Open Call 1 activities and for four years after the end of the programme activities, the Beneficiary(ies) must keep confidential any data, documents, or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at sub-contract signature ('confidential information').

The selected Beneficiary(ies) may disclose confidential information to the CORTEX² Consortium and to the selected reviewers, who will be bounded by a specific Non-Disclosure Agreement.

9.2 Promoting action and giving visibility to the EU funding

The selected Beneficiary(ies) must promote the programme activities, the CORTEX² project and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner and to highlight the financial support of the EC. Detailed requirements will be listed in [sub-grant Agreement \(Contract\) – Annex 5](#).

Any publicity made by selected third-party in respect of the project, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify that it reflects only the author's views and that the EC or CORTEX² project is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The EC and the CORTEX² Consortium shall be authorised to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- the name of the selected project members;
- contact address of the selected project;
- the general purpose of the project;
- the amount of the financial contribution foreseen for the project; after the final payment, and the amount of the financial contribution received;
- the geographic location of the activities carried out;
- the list of dissemination activities and/or of a patent (applications) relating to the foreground;
- the details/references and the abstracts of scientific publications relating to the foreground and, if funded within CORTEX² project, the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication;
- the publishable reports submitted to CORTEX²;
- any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the CORTEX² in the framework of the project.

10. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

When participating in the CORTEX² project, successful applicants will enter a co-creation process with the current partners of the CORTEX² consortium. In the case where the applicant produces a software, data, know-how or information independently on any other partner, the applicant will remain the sole owners of their respective IPR. In case of co-creation with multiple partners, an IPR co-creation is applied where generation IPR will be established through the joint efforts of multiple parties.

Each Beneficiary shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that its acts within the project do not knowingly infringe third party property rights. Therefore, there is no obligation to conduct research with regard to the property rights of third parties.

In [Annex 5](#), applicants shall identify their Background for the Project and should also, where relevant, inform the CORTEX² consortium that access to specific Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits.

During implementation, access rights to results of the project and Background needed for the performance of the own work of a party under the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis, unless otherwise agreed for Background in [Annex 5](#).

For the exploitation, access rights to results if needed for exploitation of a party's own results shall be granted on fair and reasonable conditions and upon prior written agreement. Access rights to results for internal research and for teaching activities shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.

The CORTEX² Consortium itself will not retain an equity stake in any applicant's company, nor will it retain any IPR. However, the CORTEX² Consortium will be granted the right to make internal use of any IPR applicants produce as part of their CORTEX² Open Call activities.

CORTEX² and the European Commission may ask participants who have received funding to present their work as part of public relations and networking events to showcase the benefits of the CORTEX² project.

11. Checklist

1) **Does your planned work fit with the call for proposals?** Check that your proposed work does indeed address the Open Call 1 objective, Track of your selection.

2) **Is your proposal eligible?** The eligibility criteria are given in chapter 3 "Eligibility Criteria". Any proposal not meeting the eligibility requirements will be considered ineligible and will not be evaluated.

3) **Budgetary limits.** Check that you comply with any budgetary limits as expressed in chapter 8 "Financial support provided".

- 4) **Is your proposal complete?** Have you completed all mandatory questions?
- 5) **Does your proposal fulfil the requested information?** Proposals should be precise, and concise and must answer to requested information, which is designed to correspond to the applied evaluation. Omitting requested information will almost certainly lead to lower scores and possible rejection.
- 6) **Have you maximised your chances?** There will be strong competition. Therefore, edit your proposal tightly, and strengthen or eliminate weak points.
- 7) **Have you submitted your proposal before the deadline?** It is strongly recommended not to wait until the last minute to submit the proposal. Failure of the proposal to arrive in time for any reason, including network communications delays, is not acceptable as an extenuating circumstance. The time of receipt of the application as recorded by the submission system will be definitive.
- 8) **Have you provided the necessary annexes?** Pdf of Annex 2.1 or 2.2. Proposal Template per selected Track.
- 9) **Do you need further advice and support?** You are strongly advised to communicate with the CORTEX² team.

12. Contact

The CORTEX² Consortium serves the following support:

- F6S Online Q&A:
 - Track 1: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-1-co-development/discuss>
 - Track 2: <https://www.f6s.com/cortex2-open-call-1-track-2-use-case/discuss>
- F6S support team: support@f6s.com
- Open Call #1 Documents: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/#documents>
- More info at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1>

For extraordinary communication need, please contact the Help Desk: opencall@cortex2.eu

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 1.1

Technical Description

Open Call 1: Track 1 and Track 2

Submission deadline: **16 January 2024, 17:00 CET**

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1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of CORTEX² Open Call 1 is to extend an opportunity to third parties to participate in the co-development of the XR and AR teleconference platform and to additionally test it in a variety of domains that are not applied within the framework of the project. This will be achieved by launching 2 rounds of open calls, each with specific objectives and expected results. Open Call 1 is divided in two tracks – Track 1 – Co-development with focus on recruiting tech startups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX² and Track 2 – Use Cases to engage new use-cases/pilots from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths. Additionally, through the open calls the project aims to assess and validate the social impacts associated with XR technology adoption. A total of 4 million Euro will be invested in CORTEX² open calls.

This document referred to as ANNEX 1.1 Technical Description, provides a detailed description of CORTEX² architecture and services available to beneficiaries under their participation in the CORTEX² Assistance Programme for Track 1 Co-development (9months duration) and Track 2 Use Cases (12-month duration).

The document shall be treated as an extension of Annex 1 – CORTEX² Guidelines for Applicants.

All associated Annexes must be additionally considered for the submission of a Proposal under CORTEX² Open Calls.

2. CORTEX² Architecture and Services

CORTEX² aims to deliver a next generation telecooperation framework based on XR and AI technologies. This section provides information on the platform architecture that shows the modules, interfaces and covered functionalities that are available within CORTEX². These shall be considered from both Track 1 and Track 2 applicants when suggesting their co-developed modules and features and extended pilots.

The architecture of the platform is described in three layers of **Figure 22**: the Cortex Client block that will work on the client side, the Cortex Core block that will work on the infrastructure or cloud side and the Third-party block that represents partner functionalities provided as a service, i.e., deployed in an external infrastructure.

The following sections provide detailed information about each of the individual components that make up the CORTEX² solution.

The description of the architecture covers modules that are currently being developed and all of them will be available only at the end of the project. Please refer to chapter 2.5 to have a clear snapshot of the available Cortex Framework when the OC1 projects are starting.

Figure 22: CORTEX2 high-level architecture

1.1. CORTEX Client components

A CORTEX² application can have several views according to the role that the user can take. We can notice that especially for an industrial use case and a learning use case, different types of users are involved in the same application but have different views depending on the role they play in the cooperation.

The components of **Figure 23** will be developed to run on the XR device, laptop or smart phone in order to provide the user with the appropriate interface for his application. They are very dependent on the application domain. Due to the vast heterogeneity of possible applications, it is not planned to develop an application authoring tool to build applications. Instead, we provide interfaces for Mozilla Hubs and Unity for creating CORTEX² applications based on these specific engines. Each application may have to use only a part of these components because the user views, for the same application, could be very different, and some components may not be necessary for another type of application. A brief description of each component is given below:

Figure 23 Architecture of the CORTEX2 Client

- **Application scenario life cycle** is the heart component of CORTEX² APP. it manages the life cycle of the application by invoking the functionalities provided by other elements of the architecture.
- **Cortex authentication** is used for access management, user role and profile.
- **Cortex scene, objects and persona** is managing the different participants avatars and scene representation.
- **Scene changes tracking and update** shares authorized changes or events in a scene between the different participants, for example, if an object is moved by a user A, this might impact the rendering of user B application.
- **Application 3D/2D scene assists** are providing necessary objects needed to the construction of scene. Some predefined objects and scenes are stored in the Cortex core Database to allow quick starting of a Cortex app.
- **Cortex Rainbow SDK media and data transport** is used to connect to the core components and data transportation including the different media.
- **Cortex speech prefabs** is managing advanced conversational features and allow voice interaction to use within the rendering framework and targeted devices. For meeting summarization, users with an organisational role should authenticate to the conversational manager service provided by LINAGORA to review the auto-generated summary.
- **Cortex IoT SDK** provides the end-user applications with the libraries/mechanisms required to enable the access to and interaction with the IoT objects, either from the Cortex Core components or directly from the uiTOP platform, provided by ICOM uiTOP

platform may have to integrate with the Cortex Core authentication mechanisms in order to handle users' access rights to IoT objects. The Cortex IoT SDK participates in the translation of the end user VR/AR "language" to an internal IoT format, readable by the Cortex Core or the uiTOP.

1.2. Core components

The core components (Cortex Core and Rainbow Core) are modules running on a server that can be used by any application. These modules are providing the core server functionalities that are necessary to run a telecooperation application. Two core components are identified and presented in **Figure 24**. They are detailed in the following sections.

Figure 24 Architecture of the CORTEX2 Core Components

1. Rainbow Core

Rainbow-core, provided by Alcatel Lucent Enterprise, is dedicated to connectivity and media transportation through its available SDK in the client side. Rainbow-core supports user authentication access using email and password, or the delegation of authority. It also includes the capability of collaboration and conferencing within “bubbles”, which are setup and monitored through the Rainbow SDK. Rainbow-core handles all communication channels for data exchange between participants in the collaborative room. It is also in charge of transporting medias, signalization and metadata to the right Mediation Gateway connected the XR services modules.

2. Cortex Core

Cortex-core brings together a set of components that are identified from the requirements and are developed within the project. They have the specificity to belong to the same deployment infrastructure, unlike some services that will be developed and deployed outside the cortex core environment.

- **Cortex-DB** is used for data persistence including 3D models, speech recognition data, users' profiles, IoT objects information, etc.
- **Management core** is made up of three components. They provide a set of utilities for user's and IoT registration, role management and authorizations. End-users'

authentication is done through Rainbow SDK. It also allows the management and provision of media streams and other data in the platform. Particularly, IoT device management connects IoT world to Cortex XR world by giving access to associated sensors data or actuators. There is no generic administration GUI and it has to be considered according to pilots' usage.

- **Scene synchronization** is used to align scenes views across multiple shared virtual (or augmented) user environment. The synchronization will be achieved via data and events routing relaying on Cortex App components (Scene changes tracking and update, Cortex Rainbow SDK media and data transport) and Rainbow core.
- **IoT Scene synchronization** has the same goal as the previous element but with sharing restrictions taking into account the user's preferences and, security and privacy reasons. In case an IoT object is visible and usable by to other users, then actions or sensors status should be synchronized across users' scenes. Regarding IoT integration, uITOP platform may be accessed either directly from the end-user application or through the Cortex core server components, also taking into account whether the information from the actuation/sensor needs to be shared or not.
- **Cortex Mediation Gateway** handles the routing of medias and metadata to the most appropriated XR and speech technologies services.
- **Rainbow-SDK** is a Rainbow Core Client simplifying the API access and management to the **Rainbow Core** APIs.
- **Mediation Gateway Remote Orchestration** is a component responsible of routing calls to external services from the Cortex Mediation Gateway.

1.3. Cortex services

Cortex services are modules provided as services and deployed outside the platform to facilitate integration. Their use is optional and dependent on the application. Incoming or outgoing media data, to these services, is driven by the Cortex Mediation Gateway via the Rainbow Core media server.

Identified services from the requirements are represented in **Figure 25** and are described in the following section.

Figure 25 Set of the CORTEX2 Services

- **Video Compression/Alternative Appearance service** is a module with two functionalities. On the one hand it can be used to save bandwidth when multiple users participate to the virtual cooperation environment. Instead of the transmitting 2D video, only metadata, low-dimension representation, is transmitted, and the video is reconstructed on the client side. On the other hand, the reconstructed video can be based on an alternative appearance, changing the physical appearance in the video of the user. DFKI will provide the encoder/decoder component.
- **Gesture Interaction service** reproduces hand poses from real user gestures and makes them available for a virtual interaction with real objects.
- **Instant 3D models service** implements and provides necessary APIs for AR scene analysis and objects recognition.
- **Voice Transcription service** provides live speech to text technology for different languages.
- **Virtual Assistant/Conversational Agent service** provides design patterns to handle live interaction between users and the Cortex app or users and the virtual assistant in cooperation environment.
- **Document Summarization service** is used to extract summaries from written documents, saved as files or stored in databases.
- **Meeting Summarization service** implements and provides discourse summarization API. In addition, a conversational tool will be made available to extend the generated summaries with annotation and NLP based tasks.
- **Cortex IoT server** is based on ICOM's uiTOP platform to implement and provide the necessary APIs for the management of IoT objects and their data including IoT objects registration/connectivity, monitoring/measurements, as well as actuation. The relevant flow goes through the Cortex core components.

1.4. CORTEX² data privacy and security

Security and privacy are two essential pillars in software development.

The following section gives a broader context of the concepts of data security, integrity, sovereignty, and privacy.

Data security is the procedure in which it is made sure that data is protected from being accessed, manipulated, or corrupted by unauthorized personnel or applications during its span of life. It includes activities such as data encryption and hashing, multi-factor authentication, access control, breach response, network security or activity monitoring.

Data integrity or often also called data quality, indicates how consistent and untampered a set of data is regardless of where and how it is stored. It ensures that data is accurate, reliable and available to authorized parties.

Data sovereignty makes sure that your data is always subject only to the laws of the country which it is located in.

Data privacy is concerned with proper handling, processing, storage and usage of personal data. According to the law, personal data means any information relating to an identified or identifiable individual; an identifiable person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly,

in particular by reference to an identification number (e.g., social security number) or one or more factors specific to his physical, physiological, mental, economic, cultural or social identity (e.g., name and first name, date of birth, biometrics data, fingerprints, DNA...) (CNIL definition). Ensuring data privacy requires scouting and applying regulation, deploying policies and practices, governing data and third-parties.

CORTEX² has a number of built-in security and privacy mechanisms:

- Users: CORTEX² handles access control to ensure that each user could only access to the data he is authorized to.
- Data governance: The user produces personal data that is transmitted and stored in CORTEX². CORTEX² handles this private data according to European regulation and policies.
- Streams: CORTEX² ensures the cyphering of media and data streams.

Security and privacy development recommendations:

New CORTEX² components or use-cases: the new CORTEX² components will be directly impacted by data privacy and data security when interacting and exchanging data with other components. Third parties must make sure that the new services:

- do not impair GDPR compliancy
- do not impair CORTEX² access control mechanisms
- ensure integrity and security of all data generated and stored either in CORTEX² framework or outside of CORTEX² framework.

1.5. Cortex Framework components available for 3rd-party integration

2.1.1. Planned status of the Cortex Framework by end of February 2024

Figure 26 CORTEX2 Framework available for OC1 third party integration

- Components and functions
 - Scene synchronisation: use of the Rainbow WebRTC Data channels available in Unity.
 - Rainbow Mediation Gateway: first iteration of orchestration with 3rd-party services. (see below Cortex SDKs)
 - User role management and IoT device management: A keycloak server instance is deployed in Cortex core that can be used by 3rd-parties
 - IoT Scene synchronisation server: This is an interactive bot with uiTOP and it drives the actuation and sensing subscription. It will use keycloak for device management and configuration of access rights to IoT devices
 - VCAA: The component supports client emitter side and client receiver side, available in Unity as prefabs
 - Voice Transcription - CoVA (Cortex Voice Assistant) - partially available : The component supports Speech to Text, Text to Speech, and Intention recognition + document search within a local repository and summarization
 - Meeting Summarization: Partially available for POC.
 - Gesture interaction: Not available (development will start after the OC1).
 - Instant 3D scene reconstruction: A client server architecture will be available with a Unity module as client, and a server service that reconstructs 3D scenes.

2.1.2. Cortex Software Development Kits (SDKs)

CORTEX² does not provide a single Software Development Kit (SDK), but rather a collection of SDKs that can be used for different purposes in the framework. The CORTEX² framework bases on the Rainbow Videoconferencing system by Alcatel Lucent Enterprise, which has a specific SDK called Rainbow SDK. CORTEX² is providing the developers with a set of SDKs going beyond only Rainbow SDK

For the Rainbow SDK please refer to <https://developers.openrainbow.com/> and notice the WebRTC data channels and the Mediation Gateway (MGW) are not described as their development is not completed when issuing the OC1 but it could already provide a lot of information regarding available features and functionalities.

Notice, we are targeting 2 different development environments: Unity 3D or Mozilla Hubs. We will rely in the capabilities of each of those environments that are not described here. The following presents the different SDKs made available to the developers for the use of the CORTEX² framework:

- **Client-Side SDK**
 - Web SDK:
 - Audio, video conferencing ...
 - C# SDK:
 - Unity package and sample Unity project showing how to set up the Rainbow Controller aiming at easing the developers' integration of Rainbow.
 - IoT SDK : an abstract layer on top of Rainbow SDK , an implementation of Cortex IoT SDK data models. The structure of the messages exchanged will be described.
 - Tracking SDK: A Unity module and accompanying dll library for 3D object recognition and tracking which allows to track an object in the received remote video
 - VCAA service SDK: integration of the VCAA module for being able to change the video transmitted in the Rainbow conversation

- **Server-Side SDK**
 - Rainbow Node SDK (Nodejs – Javascript): it is used for instance for IoT scene synchronisation bot using Instant Messaging to exchanged structured messages (IoT SDK)
 - Cortex² Virtual Assistant (Rasa SDK): CoVA is based on Rasa Open Source (<https://rasa.com/docs/rasa/>) and will later on be completed with a dedicated generative AI-based module. Currently, writing a CoVA assistant consists in implementing a Rasa bot by writing dedicated files as described in <https://rasa.com/docs/rasa/training-data-format>. This is done in a clone of a git repository that will be made available. The agent is then built and deployed using either Docker Compose or Kubernetes.

- **External services integration through Mediation Gateway**

- The MGW component will be partially available by the end of Feb 2024 and will be able to route flows. The XR Cortex service uses the Rainbow C# SDK to receive and exchange WebRTC flows.
- The MGW acts as an orchestrator and, on Service activation request, (Voice Assistant), or according to the scenario, the MGW scripting part will be triggered to activate or route the several WebRTC and chat flows to the right component. Basic scripting capabilities are available and integration use cases can be discussed with applicants.

2.1.3. How to start with developing a Cortex application or a Cortex component ?

The 3 pilots have instantiated the abstract model described in deliverable D2.1. The Virtual Business meeting use Web technologies and is based on Mozilla Hubs while the 2 other pilots are based on Unity 3D and so use C# programming.

For integrating the contributions developed in the frame of the Open Call 1 two options are possible:

- In the case of “Co-development”, the third parties are expected to use or extend the abstract model, and in this case, the 3rd-party should follow the general guidelines of CORTEX² framework development. This will be provided by mentors to guide the 3rd-party partner during the implementation of the project.

How to start developing with and for CORTEX²

Figure 27 CORTEX² OC1 Co-development process

- For the “use cases” subprojects, the third-party partners should follow the use case and development process already implemented in the development of the pilots. This implies identifying each part of the model that will be integrated by having a global view of the definition of a CORTEX² application.

How to build a collaborative virtual environment use case using CORTEX²

Figure 28: CORTEX2 OC1 Track 2 Use cases development process

Documented project samples: To help the 3rd-party partners, several samples highlighting how the consortium integrated the CORTEX² Framework components by using the different SDKs available will be provided.

In addition, **3 Pilots MVP** will present what can be achieved thanks to the CORTEX² framework.

3. Concluding remarks

In conclusion, this document serves as an informative resource detailing the architecture of the CORTEX² teleconference platform. It complements Annex 1 CORTEX² Guidelines for applicants by offering a comprehensive understanding of the fundamental platform functionalities. It is important to note that this document is a complementary resource, enhancing the understanding provided by Annex 1 rather than existing as a standalone document.

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 2 - CORTEX² Application Forms

Open call 1: Track 1 and Track 2
Submission deadline: **16 January 2024, 17:00 CET**

I. Abstract

Please note that the question forms provided here are intended for reference purposes only!

To submit your application for the call, please complete the appropriate form available on the F6S page.

- For Track 1 – Co-development: Apply [here](#).
- For Track 2 – Use-Case: Apply [here](#).

II. CORTEX² Open Call 1 - Co-development (track 1) Application Form

1.5.1. Proposal form information and documentation

This proposal form has the following mandatory sections:

Section 1: Proposal identification

Section 2: Applicants information

Section 3: Proposal information Section

Section 4: Requirements to join CORTEX² funding programme

Section 5: Additional questions

The following documents MUST be reviewed when preparing your proposal (available at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/#documents>)

- > ANNEX 1- CORTEX² Guideline for Applicants
- > ANNEX 1.1- CORTEX² Technical Description
- > ANNEX 2 - CORTEX² Application Form (current form)
- > ANNEX 2.1 - CORTEX² Proposal Template for Track 1 co-development
- > ANNEX 3 - CORTEX² Declaration of Honour
- > ANNEX 4 - CORTEX² SME Declaration
- > ANNEX 5 - CORTEX² Sub-grant Agreement

[Note: ANNEX 2.1 CORTEX² Proposal Template for Track 1 Co-development MUST be completed and uploaded within the form available on the F6S page under question 23]

Please be informed that failure to provide the required information/documentation will result in disqualification.

Good luck!

I SECTION 1: PROPOSAL IDENTIFICATION I

Proposal title*

Proposal acronym*

Proposal abstract*

Maximum length 1500 characters (including spaces).

I SECTION 2: APPLICANT INFORMATION I

According to Annex 1 - Guidelines for applicants Track 1 will finance single Startup/SME applications or a team of maximum two technology developers/providers/integrators.

Please note to justify the role of each organisation, and the capacity in terms of expertise and resources for the selected topic in the ANNEX 2.1 - CORTEX² Proposal Template for Track 1 co-development.

In case of a single entity application "Applicant 2" fields should be marked with N/A.

Applicant 1 - Lead

A1 - Organisation/Entity name*

Full legal name of company/organization

A1- Type of organisation*

Please select the type of applicant that best represents your entity.

Select One:

- Startup
- SME

A1 - VAT number

A1 - PIC Number

If you have a PIC number, please provide it. If you don't have a PIC number you can register for a PIC number here: (ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register).

Alternatively indicate N/A

A1 - Country*

A1 - Website

Provide a website, if available

A1 - Name of main contact person*

Please, provide the full name of the main contact person

A1 - Contact person's role/position in the company/organisation*

A1 - Email address*

Applicant 2

In case of a single entity application mark N/A on all A2 questions.

A2 - Organisation/Entity name*

Full legal name of company/organization

A2- Type of organisation*

Please select the type of applicant that best represents your entity.

Select One:

- Startup
- SME

A2 - VAT number

A2 - PIC Number

If you have a PIC number, please provide it. If you don't have a PIC number you can register for a PIC number here: (ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register).

Alternatively indicate N/A

A2 - Country*

A2 - Website

Provide a website, if available

A2 - Name of main contact person*

Please, provide the full name of the main contact person

A2 - Contact person's role/position in the company/organisation*

A2 - Email address*

I SECTION 3: PROPOSAL INFORMATION I

22. To which topic are you applying? *

T1 - User representation and user avatar customization

T2 - Real-time Virtualizer

T3 - Collaboration Hand Object Manipulation

- T4 - IoT Adaptability of CORTEX Framework
- T5 - Dynamic Library of Personalized Gestures
- T6 - 3D objects library T7 - Autonomic Notetaking in Virtual Videoconference
- T8 - Connect your App Service to XR Engine
- T9 - Authoring Tool for XR Environment
- T10 - Maintaining Interface Engagement and Usability for CORTEX² Framework
- T11 - Open Topic

23. Upload here pdf of filled in ANNEX 2.1 - CORTEX² Proposal Template for Track 1 co-development

The respective Annex is available at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/#documents>

Before submitting check if you have:

- (1) Respected the formatting requirements, including the page limit
- (2) Provided information for all the required sections

Proposals using another template will be disqualified. Any pages exceeding the defined limit will not be evaluated. Failure to meet the requirements will lead to proposal disqualification. (Max file size 30MB.)

[Choose a File](#)

I SECTION 4: REQUIREMENTS TO JOIN CORTEX² FUNDING PROGRAMME I

24. I accept all conditions of CORTEX² Open Call #1*

The conditions and all relevant documents to participate in CORTEX² Open Call #1 are available at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/>. By selecting "YES" you agree to the conditions described therein.

YES

25. DECLARATION OF HONOUR: I CONFIRM that I accept all conditions in ANNEX 3 - CORTEX² Declaration of Honour and information contained therein and that it will be provided signed and stamped should this proposal be accepted for funding.*

YES

26. SME DECLARATION (For SMEs): I confirm that the company I represent is a valid SME, following established EU rules, which validity will be proved by a signed and stamped declaration to be provided should this proposal be accepted for funding*.

YES

27. I CONFIRM that all information provided in this proposal is true and correct.*

YES

28. I ACCEPT that the information provided and submitted in this proposal can be shared by F6S with the CORTEX consortium and appointed external evaluators for the purposes of managing the open call.*

YES

I SECTION 5: ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS I

29. How did you hear about CORTEX² Open Call #1?

- CORTEX² website
- F6S
- CORTEX² social media
- LinkedIn
- EC communications
- Acquaintance
- Others

30. I am interested in being contacted about future funding opportunities.*

YES

NO

III. CORTEX2 Open Call 1 - Use cases (track 2) Application Form

1.5.2. Proposal form information and documentation

This proposal form has the following mandatory sections:

Section 1: Proposal identification

Section 2: Applicants information

Section 3: Proposal information

Section 4: Requirements to join CORTEX² funding programme

Section 5: Additional questions

The following documents MUST be reviewed when preparing your proposal (available at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1>)

- > ANNEX 1- CORTEX² Guideline for Applicants
- > ANNEX 1.1- CORTEX² Technical Description
- > ANNEX 2 - CORTEX² Application Form (current form)

- > ANNEX 2.2 - CORTEX² Proposal Template for Track 2 Use-case
- > ANNEX 3 - CORTEX² Declaration of Honour
- > ANNEX 4 - CORTEX² SME Declaration

> ANNEX 5 - CORTEX² Sub-grant Agreement

[Note: CORTEX² ANNEX 2.2 CORTEX² Proposal Template for Track 2 Use-case MUST be completed and uploaded within the form available on the F6S page]

Please be informed that failure to provide the required information/documentation will result in disqualification.

Good luck!

I SECTION 1: PROPOSAL IDENTIFICATION I

Proposal title*

Proposal acronym*

Proposal abstract*

Maximum length 1500 characters (including spaces).

I SECTION 2: APPLICANT(S) INFORMATION I

According to Annex 1 - Guidelines for applicants Track 2 will finance single entity applications and consortiums of 2 entities – one organisation must serve as the technology adopter and one organisation may serve as the technology developer/provider/integrator of the use-case that will be applied. Please feel in the information below accordingly for each applicant (if applicable). In case of a single entity application "Applicant 2" fields should be marked with N/A. Please take into consideration that in case of a single entity application, you need to describe the capacity of your organisation in terms of expertise and resources to develop and deploy the use case in accordance with the described implementation plan. This must be done directly in the ANNEX 2.2 - CORTEX² Proposal Template for Track 2 use-case.

Applicant 1

A1 - Organisation/Entity Name*

Please provide the official legal name of the organisation/entity

A1 - Type of applicant*

- Startup
- SME
- NGO
- Research organisation
- University
- School
- Association
- Foundation
- Other

If you chose "Other" in response to Q5, provide a definition of the applying entity.

A1 - VAT number

A1 - PIC Number

If you have a PIC number, please provide it. If you don't have a PIC number you can register for one here: (ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register).

A1 - Country*

A1 - Website

A1 - Name of main contact person*

This will be the main contact person CORTEX² project will interact with to provide results and request any information.

A1 - Contact person's role/position in the company/organisation*

A1 - Email address*

This will be the primary email to contact the consortium.

Applicant 2

A2 - Organization/Entity Name*

Please provide the official legal name of the organisation/entity

A2 - Type of applicant*

- Startup
- SME
- NGO
- Research organisation
- University
- School
- Association
- Foundation
- Other

If you chose "Other" in response to Q15, provide a definition of the applying entity.

A2 - VAT number

A2 - PIC Number

If you have a PIC number, please provide it. If you don't have a PIC number you can register for one here: (ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register).

A2 - Country*

A2 - Website

A2 - Name of main contact person*

A2 - Contact person's role/position in the company/organisation*

A2 - Email address*

I SECTION 3: PROPOSAL INFORMATION I

To which domain are you applying? *

- D1 - Education
- D2 - Business
- D3 - Industry
- D4 - Healthcare
- D5 - Emergency and Crisis
- D6 - Entertainment and Culture
- D7 - Smart Cities
- D8 - Accessibility and Social Inclusion
- D9 - Open Domain

Upload here a pdf of a filled in ANNEX 2.2 - CORTEX² Proposal Template for Track 2 use-case.

The respective Annex is available at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/#documents>

Before submitting check if you have:

(1) Respected the formatting requirements, including the page limit

(2) Provided information for all the required sections Proposals using another template will be disqualified. Any pages exceeding the defined limit will not be evaluated.

Failure to meet the requirements will lead to proposal disqualification. (Max file size 30MB.)

[Choose a File](#)

I SECTION 4: REQUIREMENTS TO JOIN CORTEX² FUNDING PROGRAMME I

I accept all conditions of CORTEX² Open Call #1*

The conditions and all relevant text to participate in CORTEX² Open Call #1 are available at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/>. By selecting "YES" you agree to these conditions.

YES

DECLARATION OF HONOUR: I CONFIRM that I accept all conditions in ANNEX 3 - CORTEX² Declaration of Honour and information contained therein and that it will be provided signed and stamped should this proposal be accepted for funding.*

YES

SME DECLARATION (For SMEs): I confirm that the company I represent is a valid SME, following established EU rules, which validity will be proved by a signed and stamped declaration to be provided should this proposal be accepted for funding*.

YES

I CONFIRM that all information provided in this proposal is true and correct.*

YES

I ACCEPT that the information provided and submitted in this proposal can be shared by F6S with the CORTEX² consortium and appointed external evaluators for the purposes of managing the open call.*

YES

I SECTION 5: ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS I

How did you hear about CORTEX² Open Call #1?

- CORTEX² website
- F6S website
- CORTEX² social media
- LinkedIn

- EC communication
- Acquaintances
- Others

I am interested in being contacted about future funding opportunities*

- YES
- NO

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 2.1 Proposal Template for Track 1: Co-development

Open Call 1: Track 1: Co-development
Submission deadline: 16 January 2024, 17:00 CET

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INSTRUCTIONS

CORTEX² – Open Call 1: Track 1 Co-development

Please use this template to prepare your proposal for Track 1: Co-development application. **The structure of this template MUST be followed when preparing your proposal.** Applicants using other kind of template/ document structure will be automatically ineligible.

Disclaimer: *Please be aware that the proposal will be evaluated as it was submitted, with no additional documents or links to add information beyond the defined hereby.* The proposal is a self-contained document. Evaluators will be instructed to ignore hyperlinks to information that is specifically designed to expand the proposal, thus circumventing the page limit.

Before submitting your application, you **MUST read the Guidelines for Applicants** to clearly understand the rules applying to the call. It is available at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/#documents>

This template has been organised to ensure that the important aspects of your planned work are clearly measurable with respect to the evaluation criteria, which are:

- Technical Excellence
- Ambition & Impact
- Team Skills & Expertise
- Project Planning & Value for Money

Rules:

- The page limit for full proposal is **10 pages** (not including cover page, table of content page and the Ethical/Security Checklist). All tables, figures, references and any other element pertaining to these sections must be included as an integral part of these sections.
- The allowed font type is “**Calibri**” and the minimum **font size is 11** points.
- It is mandatory to save the document in PDF before uploading.
- **If you attempt to upload a proposal longer than the specified limit, your proposal may not be taken into consideration by the evaluators.**
- **ENGLISH is the only eligible language of the proposal.**

Tips:

- Please take advantage of the different communication instruments offered by the CORTEX² Consortium (i.e. info webinars, online Q&A, and FAQ section in the website) to receive feedback on any questions you may have before submitting your proposal.
- It is in your interest to **keep your text as concise** as possible, since evaluators rarely view unnecessarily long proposals in a positive light.

!!!! Please delete this page when submitting the proposal !!!!

!!! Delete the guidance text in blue in each section !!!

A call for a single SME/Startup or maximum two SMEs/Startups forming a consortium.

Acronym of your proposal

Full title of your proposal

Indicate to which topic you are applying for (delete the unnecessary ones)

Topic#	Name of the Topic
1	User representation and user avatar customisation
2	Real-time object virtualiser
3	Collaborative hand object manipulation
4	IoT adaptability of the CORTEX2 framework
5	Dynamic library of personalised gestures
6	3D objects library
7	Automatic notetaking in virtual videoconference
8	Connect your app service to XR engine
9	Authoring tool for XR environment
10	Maintaining interface engagement and usability for the CORTEX2 framework
11	Open Topic

SME/Startup Organisation (1) Name, Last name, position in the organisation	SME/Startup Organisation (2) Name, Last name, position in the organisation please remove this column if only 1 organisation applies
Short Name of Organisation	Short Name of Organisation
E-mail	Email
Logo, if applicable	Logo, if applicable
Website	Website

Date of submission:

Country/city

Page count starts here

1. OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSAL (1 PAGE)

1.1. Objective(s)

Please state a clear objective/ a set of objectives of your intended work for the 9 month co-development programme.

Text style to be used

1.2. Executive summary

Describe an overview of your intended proposed work. What will be developed, why is it important, who will be involved, challenges to address, objectives to meet, expected outcome and potential impact.

Text style to be used

2. TECHNICAL EXCELLENCE (3 PAGES)

2.1. Current scenario

-Describe the challenging/problematic scenario to be addressed by your project, explaining the how does the current situation looks like, what are the limitations. Identify the technical challenges and barriers. Whenever possible quantify the aspects involved.

-Alignment with the CORTEX² challenges and vision.

Text style to be used

2.2. Envisioned scenario

Explain the adopted technology and comparison with state-of-the-art.

You can indicate:

- How will the solution approach the selected Topic /Open Topic?

- Your previous experience with this solution?

- Technical plan to achieve required TRL, technical milestones (you can include them in Table 3)

- Describe how research data will be managed.

- Alignment with the CORTEX² objectives.

Text style to be used

2.3. Technical approach

-Describe how you will reach the envisioned scenario.

-Describe your technical approach including the identification of the platforms/technologies required to be integrated/developed, the applicable standards to be used and/or updated, data to be captured for decision support systems, validation methodologies

-Identify the CORTEX² technical components/framework to be used (check Annex 1.1 from the Open Call documents).

Text style to be used

2.4. Visual description

-Include a scheme(s)/image(s)/figure(s) supporting the description of your technical work to be performed.

3. AMBITION & IMPACT (2 PAGES)

3.1. Expected benefits

- What will change thanks to your solution?
- What are the longer-term goals and how this first successful proof-of-concept will lead to there?
- Describe expected benefits for your organisation(s) partners, CORTEX², and other stakeholders involved.
- Justify your project outcomes (which should be clear, measurable, and realistic) and how they will generate added-value with respect to CORTEX² vision and objectives.
- Define the potential socio-economic impact of your solution

Text style to be used

3.2. KPIs

Table 25 Contribution to CORTEX² KPIs.

Contribution to CORTEX ² KPIs	
KPI name	Value
(take it from the specific KPIs defined by each topic in the Guidelines for Applicants. In case of the Open Topic Application please propose a set of relevant KPIs)	at the end of implementation

Add rows as needed

Additional KPIs to measure your project's success can be agreed at the 1st Sprint on the programme between the beneficiary and the CORTEX² Consortium.

3.3. Gender approach/accessibility/inclusion

- Describe the potential of your proposed solution regarding these aspects.

Text style to be used

4. TEAM SKILLS & EXPERTISE (1 PAGE)

Summarise the team involved in the project in the table below. Notice that the people included in the proposal should be later involved in the execution.

Table 26 - Proposed Team.

Entity	Name of the person	Role in the project	Link to LinkedIn profile or equivalent	Gender

Add lines as required

Below please provide a short summary of the relevant experience of each team member. When relevant include previous project references relevant to the proposal, products, publications, participation in conferences, collaborations, community projects, etc.

Describe #1 SME/Startup - leader

Please describe the competences of the company and in particular the team which will realise the results.

Include:

- Company profile and main expertise/products/services if relevant,
- Business and technical competences and
- Competences adequate to the expected role
- Participating team members competences/ skills

Describe #2 SME/Startup (if exists)

Please describe the role of the healthcare entity involved and the team of experts that will represent this partner. Include:

- Company profile and main expertise/products/services if relevant,
- Business and technical competences and
- Competences adequate to the expected role
- Participating team members competences/ skills

- In case of two organisations explain the value of fusion as a consortium and how you will be structured as a sole team
- Identify synergies, trans-disciplinary competences, cross-border dimension if exists.

Text style to be used

5. PROJECT PLANNING & VALUE FOR MONEY (3 PAGES)

5.1. Planning

Describe the activities that will take place in your project from the technical point of view. Break down your work into each of the 3 sprints (1-DEVELOPMENT; 2-INTEGRATION; 3-VALIDATION), list tasks and provide timing of the different activities and components. This section should answer the question “how are we going to implement the project to reach the defined objectives?”

Table 27 Project plan.

<p>Description: The main aim of this work....</p> <p>WORK PLAN 1st Sprint – DEVELOPMENT (3-months)</p> <p>Task 1.1 name & period of execution M=month (Mx-Mx)</p> <p>Clear objective of the task</p> <p>Clear description of the task</p> <p>Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s)</p> <p>Expected outcome(s)</p> <p>Task 1.2 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx)</p> <p>Clear objective of the task</p> <p>Clear description of the task</p> <p>Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s)Expected outcome(s)</p> <p><u>Task 1.3 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx) (if applicable)</u></p> <p>Clear objective of the task</p> <p>Clear description of the task</p> <p>Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s)</p> <p>Expected outcome(s)</p> <p><u>SPRINT 1 Deliverable proposal required ONLY for Open Topic (deliverables per each Topic are defined in the Guidelines for Applicants):</u></p>
<p>Impact and Outputs of the 1st Sprint</p> <p>List main Milestones:</p> <p>WORK PLAN 2nd Sprint – INTEGRATION (3 months)</p> <p>Task 2.1 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx)</p> <p>Clear objective of the task</p> <p>Clear description of the task</p> <p>Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s)</p> <p>Expected outcome(s)</p> <p>Task 2.2 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx)</p> <p>Clear objective of the task</p> <p>Clear description of the task</p> <p>Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s)</p> <p>Expected outcome(s)</p> <p><u>Task 2.3 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx) (if applicable)</u></p> <p>Clear objective of the task</p>

Provide a description of expected costs and the requested total contribution using the table.

Table 29 Total budget.

Item	Amount (€)		
	Entity 1	Entity 2 (if applicable)	Total
Direct personnel costs (a)			
Other direct cost (Equipment) (b) (Depreciation cost only)			
Other direct cost (Software licenses) (c)			
Other direct cost (Travel expenses) (d)			
Other direct cost (Others) (e)			
Indirect costs (0,25 x (a +b +c +d+e))			
Total			

The maximum amount of funding that a **single SME/Startup or maximum 2** may receive from CORTEX² is up to 100.000 EUROS via any mean.

ANNEX: Ethics Self-Assessment

ETHICAL ISSUES TABLE – CHECKLIST to be completed

	YES/NO
Informed Consent	
• Does the proposal involve children?	
• Does the proposal involve patients or persons not able to give consent?	
• Does the proposal involve adult healthy volunteers?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Genetic Material?	
• Does the proposal involve Human biological samples?	
• Does the proposal involve Human data collection?	
Research on Human embryo/foetus	
• Does the proposal involve Human Embryos?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Foetal Tissue / Cells?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells?	
Privacy	
• Does the proposal involve processing of genetic information or personal data (e.g. health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction)	
• Does the proposal involve tracking the location or observation of people?	
Research on Animals	
• Does the proposal involve research on animals?	
• Are those animals transgenic small laboratory animals?	
• Are those animals transgenic farm animals?	
• Are those animals cloned farm animals?	
• Are those animals nonhuman primates?	
Research Involving Developing Countries	
• Use of local resources (genetic, animal, plant etc)	
• Benefit to local community (capacity building i.e. access to healthcare, education etc)	
Dual Use	
• Research having direct military application	
• Research having the potential for terrorist abuse	
ICT Implants	
• Does the proposal involve clinical trials of ICT implants?	
I CONFIRM THAT NONE OF THE ABOVE ISSUES APPLY TO MY PROPOSAL	

Ethics

If you have entered any ethics issues in the ethical issue table, you must, once selected:

- submit an ethics self-assessment, which:
 - describes how the proposal meets the national legal and ethical requirements of the country or countries where the tasks raising ethical issues are to be carried out;
 - explains in detail how you intend to address the issues in the ethical issues table, in particular as regards:
 - research objectives (e.g. study of vulnerable populations, dual use, etc.)
 - research methodology (e.g. clinical trials, involvement of children and related consent procedures, protection of any data collected, etc.)
 - the potential impact of the research (e.g. dual use issues, environmental damage, stigmatisation of particular social groups, political or financial retaliation, benefit-sharing, malevolent use, etc.).
- provide the documents that you need under national law (if you already have them), e.g.:
 - an ethics committee opinion;
 - the document notifying activities raising ethical issues or authorising such activities

⚠ *If these documents are not in English, you must also submit an English summary of them (containing, if available, the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned).*

⚠ *If you plan to request these documents specifically for the project you are proposing, your request must contain*

Security

Please indicate if your project will involve:

- Activities or results raising security issues: _____(YES/NO)
- 'EU-classified information' as background or results: _____(YES/NO)
- Any potential “dual use” of results: _____(YES/NO)

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 2.2 Proposal Template for Track 2: Use-case

Open Call 1: Track 2: Use-case
Submission deadline: 16 January 2024, 17:00 CET

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INSTRUCTIONS

CORTEX² – Open Call 1: Track 2 Use-case

Please use this template to prepare your proposal for Track 2: Use-case application. **The structure of this template MUST be followed when preparing your proposal.** Applicants using other kind of template/document structure will be automatically considered ineligible.

Disclaimer: Please be aware that the proposal will be evaluated as it was submitted, with no additional documents or links to add information beyond the defined hereby. The proposal is a self-contained document. Evaluators will be instructed to ignore hyperlinks to information that is specifically designed to expand the proposal, thus circumventing the page limit.

Before submitting your application, you **MUST read Annex 1 Guidelines for Applicants** to clearly understand the rules applying to the call. All documents are available at: <https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/open-call-1/#documents>

This template has been organised to ensure that the important aspects of your planned work are clearly measurable with respect to the evaluation criteria, which are:

- Technical Excellence
- Ambition & Impact
- Team Skills & Expertise
- Project Planning & Value for Money

Rules:

- The page limit for the full proposal is **10 pages** (cover page, table of content page and the Ethical/Security Checklist are not included within the 10-page limit). All tables, figures, references, and any other element pertaining to these sections must be included as an integral part of the proposal.
- The allowed font type is “**Calibri**” and the minimum **font size is 11** points.
- It is mandatory to save the document in PDF before uploading.
- **If you attempt to upload a proposal longer than the specified limit, your proposal may not be taken into consideration by the evaluators.**
- **ENGLISH is the only eligible language of the proposal.**

Tips:

Please take advantage of the different communication instruments offered by the CORTEX² Consortium (i.e. info webinars, online Q&A, and the website) to receive feedback on any questions you may have before submitting your proposal.

- It is in your interest to **keep your text as concise** as possible, since evaluators rarely view unnecessarily long proposals in a positive light.

!!!! Delete this page and guidance text in blue in each section when submitting the proposal !!!!

A call for a single entity or a consortium of two entities - technological adopter (must) and a technological developer/provider/integrator (recommended but optional)⁵

Acronym of your proposal

Full title of your proposal

Mark the domain you are applying to with an “x”.

Topic#	Domain name	
1	EDUCATION	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	BUSINESS	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	INDUSTRY	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	HEALTHCARE	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	EMERGENCY AND CRISIS	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	ENTERTAINMENT AND CULTURE	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	SMART CITIES	<input type="checkbox"/>
8	ACCESSIBILITY AND SOCIAL INCLUSION	<input type="checkbox"/>
9	OPEN DOMAIN	<input type="checkbox"/>

Fill in the required information.

Organisation (1) Name, Last name, position in the organisation	Organisation (2) Name, Last name, position in the organisation
Name of Organisation	Name of Organisation
E-mail	Email
Logo, if applicable	Logo, if applicable
Website	Website

Date of submission:

Country/city

⁵ Refer to Annex 1 CORTEX² Guidelines for Applicants on the types of eligible beneficiaries

Page count starts here (remove this sentence)

1. OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSAL (MAXIMUM 1 PAGE)

1.1 Executive Summary

Describe an overview of your intended proposed work. What will be developed, why is it important, who will be involved, challenges to address, expected outcome and potential impact.

Add text here.

1.2 Objectives

Please state a clear objective/ a set of objectives of your intended work for the 12-month Track 2 Use - Case programme. Are they measurable and verifiable. Are they realistically achievable?

Add text here.

2. TECHNICAL EXCELLENCE (MAXIMUM 3 PAGES)

2.1 Current scenario

- Describe the challenging/problematic scenario to be addressed by your project, explaining how the current situation looks like, what are the existing limitations. Identify the technical challenges and barriers and how your project will address this/these. Describe the positive advancement based on your activity and how your project goes beyond the state-of-the-art. Whenever possible quantify the aspects involved.
- Briefly explain your project's alignment with CORTEX² mission and objectives.

Text style to be used.

2.2 Envisioned scenario

Describe how you will reach the envisioned scenario.

Explain the adopted technology for the application of the use - case and comparison with state-of-the-art.

You can indicate:

- How will the solution approach the selected Domain?
- Your previous experience with this solution?
- Technical plan to achieve TRL 7, technical milestones (you can include them in Table 3)
- Describe how research data will be managed.
- Alignment with CORTEX²

Add text here.

2.3 Technical approach

-Describe your technical approach including the identification of the platforms/technologies required to be integrated/developed, the applicable standards to be used and/or updated, data to be captured for decision support systems, validation methodologies.

- Identify the CORTEX² technical components/framework to be used. Please refer to Annex 1.1 Technical Description
- Applicants are expected to demonstrate and validate their use-cases. Describe your anticipated validation plan, including the context, testing scenario and number of users.

Add text here.

2.4 Visual description

- Include a scheme(s)/image(s)/figure(s) supporting the description of your anticipated work to be performed.

3. AMBITION & IMPACT (2 PAGES)

3.1 Expected benefits

- What will change thanks to your solution?
- What are the longer-term goals and how this first successful proof-of-concept will lead to there?
- Describe the expected benefits for your organisation(s), CORTEX², and other stakeholders involved.
- Justify your project outcomes (which should be clear, measurable, and realistic) and how they will generate added-value with respect to CORTEX² vision and objectives.
- Define the potential socio-economic impact of your solution
- Describe potential commercialisation and anticipated IP in the frame of CORTEX².

Add text here.

3.2 KPIs

CORTEX² has identified two sets of KPIs for the Open Call applicants. The first set is connected to the CORTEX² predefined KPIs described in Table 1. The second set of KPIs is connected to the additional KPIs you have identified to use to measure your project’s success. Please fill in both tables accordingly.

Table 30 Contribution to CORTEX2 KPIs

Contribution to CORTEX ² KPIs	
KPI	Value at the end of implementation
KPI01: Successful deployment of the use case in the selected domain (Target value – minimum 1)	
KPI02: N of different scenarios supported for the specific domain (Target value – 3)	
KPI03: User study with at least 10 users (target number 20) conducted and documented as user experience feedback in link with technical performance (accuracy, latency, speed when it applies)	

KPI04: N of CORTEX ² services implemented in the domain app (>= 1)	
KPI05 (for Domain #2 Business and Domain #4 Industry, remove in non-applicable for your domain): Measurement of solution impact on efficiency, operational costs reduction, and customer outcomes improvement.	

Additional KPIs to measure your project’s success can be agreed at the 1st Phase on the programme between the beneficiary and the CORTEX² Consortium.

3.3 Deliverables

Table 31 List of deliverables

CORTEX ² Mandatory Deliverables	Month (M) of delivery
DEL01 Specification and Implementation plan (including UX, requirements and detailed roadmap for CORTEX2 framework integration, development and deployment of the use-case)	M3
DEL02 Performance Report (End of Phase 1)	M3
DEL03 Demonstration of a “Minimum Viable Product”	M8
DEL04 Performance Report (End of Phase 2)	M8
DEL05 Evaluation report (Assessment of the use-case regarding the technical, economical, ecological and sociological impact of the implemented solution. A user satisfaction study should be included within the report)	M12
DEL06 Video demonstrating the use-case	M12
DEL07 Exploitation Plan	M12

3.4 Gender dimension/accessibility/inclusion

- Describe the potential of your proposed solution regarding these aspects. Describe how the gender/inclusion and accessibility dimensions are considered in your project.

Add text here.

4 TEAM SKILLS & EXPERTISE (1 PAGE)

Describe the team involved in the project in the table below. Please enter the details of the persons who are expected to be involved in the execution. In case of a single entity application remove the section for organisation #2

Table 32 - Proposed Team

Entity	Name of the person	Role in the project	Link to LinkedIn profile or equivalent	Gender

--	--	--	--	--

Add lines as required

Below please provide a short summary of the relevant experience of each team member. When appropriate include previous project references pertinent to the proposal, products, publications, participation in conferences, collaborations, community projects, etc.

Organisation #1 - leader

Please describe the competences of the organisation and in particular the team which will realise the results.

Include:

- Company profile and main expertise/products/services if relevant
- Business and technical competences and
- Competences adequate to the expected role
- Participating team members competences/ skills
- Specify whether your organisation will serve as a technological adopter or technological developer. In case of a single entity application, you need to describe the capacity of your organisation in terms of expertise and resources to develop and deploy the use case in accordance with the described plan

Organisation #2

Please describe the role of the entity involved (technology adopter or technology developer/provider/integrator) and the team of experts that will represent this partner.

Include:

- Company profile and main expertise/products/services if relevant,
- Business and technical competences and
- Competences adequate to the expected role
- Participating team members competences/ skills

Additionally, explain the value of the overall consortium (when applicable) and how you will be structured as a sole team.

Identify synergies, trans-disciplinary competences, cross-border dimension if exists.

Add text here.

5 PROJECT PLANNING & VALUE FOR MONEY (3 PAGES)

5.1 Planning

Describe the activities that will take place in your project from the technical point of view. Break down your work into each of the 3 phases (1-REQUIREMENTS; 2-DEVELOPMENT/DEPLOYMENT; 3-VALIDATION), list tasks and provide timing of the different activities and components. This section should answer the question “how are we going to implement the project to reach the defined objectives?”

Table 33 Project Plan

Description: The main aim of this work...
1. WORK PLAN Phase 1 – REQUIREMENTS (3-months) Task 1.1 name & period of execution M=month (Mx-Mx)

<p>Clear objective of the task Clear description of the task Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s) Expected outcome(s) Task 1.2 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx) Clear objective of the task Clear description of the task Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s) Expected outcome(s) Expected outcome(s)</p> <p>Add more tasks as needed</p>
<p>Impact and Outputs of Phase 1 List main Milestones:</p>
<p>2. WORK PLAN Phase 2 – Development/Deployment (5 months) Task 2.1 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx) Clear objective of the task Clear description of the task Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s) Expected outcome(s)</p> <p>Task 2.2 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx) Clear objective of the task Clear description of the task Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s) Expected outcome(s) Add more tasks as needed.</p>
<p>Impact and Outputs of Phase 2 List main Milestones:</p>
<p>3. WORK PLAN Phase 3 – VALIDATION (4 months) Task 3.1 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx) Clear objective of the task Clear description of the task Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s) Expected outcome(s)</p> <p>Task 3.2 name & period of execution (Mx-Mx) Clear objective of the task Clear description of the task Clear contribution to the task of the organisation(s) Expected outcome(s)</p> <p>Add more tasks as needed.</p>
<p>Impact and Outputs of Phase 3 List main Milestones:</p>

5.2 Budget

Please indicate the number of person-months (full-time equivalent) of people involved in the project in the table below for the 12 months of project:

ANNEX: Ethics Self-Assessment

ETHICAL ISSUES TABLE - CHECKLIST to be completed.

Table 36 Ethical Issue Table

	YES/NO
Informed Consent	
• Does the proposal involve children?	
• Does the proposal involve patients or persons not able to give consent?	
• Does the proposal involve adult healthy volunteers?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Genetic Material?	
• Does the proposal involve Human biological samples?	
• Does the proposal involve Human data collection?	
Research on Human embryo/foetus	
• Does the proposal involve Human Embryos?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Foetal Tissue / Cells?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells?	
Privacy	
• Does the proposal involve processing of genetic information or personal data (e.g. health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction)	
• Does the proposal involve tracking the location or observation of people?	
Research on Animals	
• Does the proposal involve research on animals?	
• Are those animals transgenic small laboratory animals?	
• Are those animals transgenic farm animals?	
• Are those animals cloned farm animals?	
• Are those animals nonhuman primates?	
Research Involving Developing Countries	
• Use of local resources (genetic, animal, plant etc)	
• Benefit to local community (capacity building i.e. access to healthcare, education etc)	
Dual Use	
• Research having direct military application	
• Research having the potential for terrorist abuse	
ICT Implants	
• Does the proposal involve clinical trials of ICT implants?	
I CONFIRM THAT NONE OF THE ABOVE ISSUES APPLY TO MY PROPOSAL	

Ethics

If you have entered any ethics issues in the ethics self-assessment table, you must, once selected submit:

- how the proposal meets the national legal and ethical requirements of the country or countries where the tasks raising ethical issues are to be carried out;
- explain in detail how you intend to address the issues in the ethics self-assessment table, in particular as regards:
 - research objectives (e.g. study of vulnerable populations, dual use, etc.)
 - research methodology (e.g. clinical trials, involvement of children and related consent procedures, protection of any data collected, etc.)
 - the potential impact of the research (e.g. dual use issues, environmental damage, stigmatisation of particular social groups, political or financial retaliation, benefit-sharing, malevolent use, etc.).

provide the documents that you need under national law (if you already have them), e.g.:

- an ethics committee opinion;
- the document notifying activities raising ethical issues or authorising such activities
- If these documents are not in English, you must also submit an English summary of them (containing, if available, the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned).
- If you plan to request these documents specifically for the project you are proposing, your request must contain an explicit reference to the project title.

Security

Please indicate if your project will involve:

- Activities or results raising security issues: _____(YES/NO)
- 'EU-classified information' as background or results: _____(YES/NO)
- Any potential “dual use” of results: _____(YES/NO)

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 3 Declaration of Honour

Open Call 1: to submit ONLY once selected
Submission deadline: 16 January 2024, 17:00 CET

Beneficiary/Consortium Declaration of Honour

[remove "Beneficiary" if two entities apply to the Call; remove "Consortium" if only one entity applies to the Call]

Proposal Title: _____

Proposal Acronym: _____

BETWEEN *[remove "BETWEEN" if only one entity applies to the Call]*

_____ [Company/ organisation name] established in _____, [Official address], VAT number _____, represented for the purposes of signing and submitting the proposal and the Declaration of Honour by _____ [Name of legal representative];

AND *[remove the below block if only one entity applies to the Call]*

_____ [Company/ organisation name] established in _____, [Official address], VAT number _____, represented for the purposes of signing and submitting the proposal and the Declaration of Honour by _____ [Name of legal representative];

CONSORTIUM SECTION

In case you apply as 2 entities – CONSORTIUM you must fill out the below section.

In case you apply as 1 entity – BENEFCIARY you must remove this section and move to the BENEFCIARY SECTION on page 7.

It is hereby agreed that:

- All information provided is true and legally binding.
- Entity 1 _____ [leader name] is acting on behalf the following partner(s) as the consortium leader:
 - Entity 2: _____ [Company/ organisation name]
[remove block below – Partner 3 – and this text if only two entities participate in the consortium]
- The consortium entities have agreed on their roles and budget shares.
- The consortium leader is solely responsible for distributing the budget shares to the other consortium partners in accordance with this Consortium Declaration of Honour.
- The CORTEX² consortium bears no responsibility in case a partner of this project consortium violates the mutual agreement set in this Consortium Declaration of Honour.
- The CORTEX² consortium bears no responsibility in the case of dispute among consortium partners regarding intellectual property rights.
- By signing this Consortium Declaration of Honour, all consortium partners declare that any entity, applying as part of a consortium, may only be funded for one project.
- By signing this Consortium Declaration of Honour, all consortium partners declare that they are not members of CORTEX².

- By signing and submitting this Consortium Declaration of Honour, the consortium partners accept all the rules explained in CORTEX² Annex 1: Guidelines for Applicants.
- All partners declare not being in one of the following situations:
 - a) it is bankrupt or being wound up, is having its affairs administered by the courts, has entered into an arrangement with creditors, has suspended business activities, is the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, or is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations;
 - b) it or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgement which has the force of res judicata;
 - c) it has been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organisations;
 - d) it is not in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed;
 - e) it or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgement which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organisation or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests;
 - f) is subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget.
- Each partner declares that:
 - g) is not subject to a conflict of interest;
 - h) has not made false declarations in supplying the information required as a condition of participation in the CORTEX² Open Call 1;
 - i) is not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the above mentioned points a) to f).
 - j) Is aware and fully accepts all CORTEX² conditions and rules as expressed in CORTEX² Open Call documents.
- Each partner certifies that:
 - is committed to participate in the above mentioned project;
 - has stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain its activity throughout its participation in the above-mentioned project and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;
 - has or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out its involvement in the above-mentioned project.

▪ **Consortium leader (Entity 1)**

Company/organisation name	
Full address	
Country	
Name of legal representative	
Position in the company/organisation	
Project budget share	_____ EUR
I have the power of legally binding the abovementioned company/organisation on submitting this proposal	
Legal representative signature and stamp (stamp if applicable)	
Done at (place)_____	
The (day)_____ (month)_____ (year)_____	

▪ **Consortium partner no. 2 (Entity 2)**

Company/organisation name	
Full address	
Country	
Name of legal representative	
Position in the company/organisation	
Project budget share	_____ EUR
I have the power of legally binding the abovementioned company/organisation on submitting this proposal	
Legal representative signature and stamp (stamp if applicable)	
Done at (place)_____	
The (day)_____ (month)_____ (year)_____	

BENEFICIARY SECTION

*In case you apply as 1 entity – BENEFICIARY you **MUST** fill out the below section.*

In case you apply as 2 entities – CONSORTIUM you must remove this section and move to the CONSORTIUM SECTION on page 4.

It is hereby agreed that:

- All information provided is true and legally binding.
- By signing this Beneficiary Declaration of Honour, the Beneficiary declares that it is not a member of CORTEX².
- By signing and submitting this Beneficiary Declaration of Honour, the Beneficiary accepts all the rules explained in CORTEX² Annex 1: Guidelines for Applicants.
- The Beneficiary declares not being in one of the following situations:
 - k) it is bankrupt or being wound up, is having its affairs administered by the courts, has entered into an arrangement with creditors, has suspended business activities, is the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, or is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations;
 - l) it or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgement which has the force of res judicata;
 - m) it has been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organisations;
 - n) it is not in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed;
 - o) it or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgement which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organisation or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests;
 - p) is subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget.
- The Beneficiary declares that:
 - q) is not subject to a conflict of interest;
 - r) has not made false declarations in supplying the information required as a condition of participation in the CORTEX² Open Call 1;
 - s) is not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the above mentioned points a) to f).

- t) Is aware and fully accepts all CORTEX² conditions and rules as expressed in CORTEX² Open Call documents.
- The Beneficiary certifies that:
 - is committed to participate in the above mentioned project;
 - has stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain its activity throughout its participation in the above-mentioned project and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;
 - has or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out its involvement in the above-mentioned project.

Company/organisation name (Beneficiary)	
Full address	
Country	
Name of legal representative	
Position in the company/organisation	
Project budget share	_____ EUR
I have the power of legally binding the abovementioned company/organisation on submitting this proposal	
Legal representative signature and stamp (stamp if applicable)	
Done at (place)_____	
The (day)_____ (month)_____ (year)_____	

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 4 SME Declaration

Open Call 1: to submit ONLY once selected
Submission deadline: **16 January 2024, 17:00 CET**

SME Declaration (information on the SME qualification)

Precise identification of the applicant enterprise

Name or Business name

Address (of registered office)

Registration / VAT number

Names and titles of the principal director(s).....

Type of enterprise (see explanatory note)

Tick to indicate which case(s) applies to the applicant enterprise:

- Autonomous enterprise In this case the data filled in the box below result from the accounts of the applicant enterprise only. Fill in the declaration only, without annex.
- Partner enterprise Fill in and attach the annex (and any additional sheets), then complete the declaration by copying the results of the calculations into the box below.
- Linked enterprise

Data used to determine the category of enterprise

Calculated according to Article 6 of the Annex to the Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC on the SME definition.

Reference period (*)		
Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)

(*) All data must be relating to the last approved accounting period and calculated on an annual basis. In the case of newly-established enterprises whose accounts have not yet been approved, the data to apply shall be derived from a reliable estimate made in the course of the financial year

(**) EUR 1 000.

Important:

Compared to the previous accounting period there is a change regarding the data, which could result in a change of category of the applicant enterprise (micro, small, medium-sized or big enterprise).

- No
- Yes (in this case fill in and attach a declaration regarding the previous accounting period).

Signature

Name and position of the signatory, being authorised to represent the enterprise:

.....

I declare on my honour the accuracy of this declaration and of any annexes thereto.

Done at

Signature

EXPLANATORY NOTE ON THE TYPES OF ENTERPRISES TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT FOR CALCULATING THE HEADCOUNT AND THE FINANCIAL AMOUNTS

I. TYPES OF ENTERPRISES

The definition of an SME⁶ distinguishes three types of enterprise, according to their relationship with other enterprises in terms of holdings of capital or voting rights or the right to exercise a dominant influence⁷.

Type 1: Autonomous Enterprise

This is by far the most common type of enterprise.

It applies to all enterprises which are not one of the two other types of enterprise (partner or linked).

An applicant enterprise is autonomous if it:

- does not have a holding of 25%⁸ or more in any other enterprise,
- and is not 25%³ or more owned by any enterprise or public body or jointly by several linked enterprises or public bodies, apart from some exceptions⁹,

⁶ Henceforth in the text, the term "Definition" refers to the Annex to Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC on the definition of SMEs.

⁷ Definition, Article 3

⁸ In terms of the share of the capital or voting rights, whichever is higher is applied. To this percentage should be added the holding in that same enterprise of each enterprise, which is linked to the holding company (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2)

⁹ An enterprise may continue being considered as autonomous when this 25% threshold is reached or exceeded, if that percentage is held by the following categories of investors (provided that those are not linked with the applicant enterprise):

- a) public investment corporations, venture capital companies, individuals or groups of individuals with a regular venture capital investment activity who invest equity capital in unquoted businesses ("business angels"), provided the total investment of those business angels in the same enterprise is less than EUR 1 250 000,
- b) universities or non-profit research centres,
- c) institutional investors, including regional development funds,
- d) autonomous local authorities with an annual budget of less than EUR 10 million and less than 5000 inhabitants.

(Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2, second sub-paragraph)

- and does not draw up consolidated accounts and is not included in the accounts of an enterprise which draws up consolidated accounts and is thus not a linked enterprise¹⁰.

Type 2: Partner Enterprise

This type represents the situation of enterprises which establish major financial partnerships with other enterprises, without the one exercising effective direct or indirect control over the other. Partners are enterprises which are not autonomous, but which are not linked to one another.

The applicant enterprise is a partner of another enterprise if:

- it has a holding or voting rights equal to or greater than 25% in the other enterprise, or the other enterprise has a holding or voting rights equal to or greater than 25% in the applicant enterprise,
- the enterprises are not linked enterprises within the meaning defined below, which means, among other things, that the voting rights of one in the other do not exceed 50%,
- and the applicant enterprise does not draw up consolidated accounts which include the other enterprise by consolidation, and is not included by consolidation in the accounts of the other enterprise or of an enterprise linked to it⁵.

Type 3: Linked Enterprise

This type corresponds to the economic situation of enterprises which form a group through the direct or indirect control of the majority of the voting rights (including through agreements or, in certain cases, through natural persons as shareholders), or through the ability to exercise a dominant influence on an enterprise. Such cases are thus less frequent than the two preceding types.

In order to avoid difficulties of interpretation for enterprises, the Commission has defined this type of enterprise by taking over – wherever they are suitable for the purposes of the Definition – the conditions set out in Article 1 of Council Directive 83/349/EEC on consolidated accounts¹¹, which has been applied for many years.

An enterprise thus generally knows immediately that it is linked, since it is already required under that Directive to draw up consolidated accounts or is included by consolidation in the accounts of an enterprise which is required to draw up such consolidated accounts.

¹⁰ - If the registered office of the enterprise is situated in a Member State which has provided for an exception to the requirement to draw up such accounts pursuant to the Seventh Council Directive 83/349/EEC of 13 June 1983, the enterprise should nevertheless check specifically whether it does not meet one or other of the conditions laid down in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition.

- There are also some very rare cases in which an enterprise may be considered linked to another enterprise through a person or a group of natural persons acting jointly (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 3).

- Conversely, there are very few cases of enterprises drawing up consolidated accounts voluntarily, without being required to do so under the Seventh Directive. In that case, the enterprise is not necessarily linked and can consider itself only a partner.

To determine whether the enterprise is linked or not, in each of the three situations it should be checked whether or not the enterprise meets one or other of the conditions laid down in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition, where applicable through a natural person or group of natural persons acting jointly.

¹¹ Seventh Council Directive 83/349/EEC of 13 June 1983, based on Article 54(3)(g) of the Treaty and concerning consolidated accounts (OJ L 193, 18/7/1983, p. 1), as last amended by Directive 2001/65/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L 283, 27/10/01, p. 28).

The only two cases, which are however not very frequent, in which an enterprise can be considered linked although it is not already required to draw up consolidated accounts, are described in the first two indents of endnote 5 of this explanatory note. In those cases, the enterprise should check whether it meets one or other of the conditions set out in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition.

II. THE HEADCOUNT AND THE ANNUAL WORK UNITS¹²

The headcount of an enterprise corresponds to the number of annual work units (AWU).

Who is included in the headcount?

- The employees of the applicant enterprise,
- persons working for the enterprise being subordinate to it and considered to be employees under national law,
- owner-managers,
- partners engaging in a regular activity in the enterprise and benefiting from financial advantages from the enterprise.

Apprentices or students engaged in vocational training with an apprenticeship or vocational training contract are not taken into account in the headcount.

How is the headcount calculated?

One AWU corresponds to one person who worked full-time in the enterprise in question or on its behalf during the entire reference year. The headcount is expressed in AWUs.

The work of persons, who did not work the entire year, or who worked part-time - regardless of its duration - and seasonal work is counted as fractions of AWU.

The duration of maternity or parental leaves is not counted.

ANNEX TO THE DECLARATION CALCULATION FOR THE PARTNER OR LINKED TYPE OF ENTREPRISE

Annexes to be enclosed if necessary

- Annex A if the applicant enterprise has at least one partner enterprise (and any additional sheets)
- Annex B if the applicant enterprise has at least one linked enterprise (and any additional sheets)

Calculation for the partner or linked type of enterprise¹³ (see explanatory note)

¹² Definition, Article 5.

¹³ Definition, Article 6 paragraphs 2 and 3

Reference period¹⁴:

	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
1. Data ⁹ of the applicant enterprise or consolidated accounts (copy data from box B(1) in annex B ¹⁵)			
2. Proportionally aggregated data ⁹ of all partner enterprises (if any) (copy data from box A in annex A)			
3. Added up data ⁹ of all linked enterprises (if any) – if not included by consolidation in line 1 (copy data from box B(2) in annex B)			
Total			

(*) EUR 1 000.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in the box "Data used to determine the category of enterprise" in the declaration.

¹⁴ All data must be relating to the last approved accounting period and calculated on an annual basis. In the case of newly-established enterprises whose accounts have not yet been approved, the data to apply shall be derived from a reliable estimate made in the course of the financial year (Definition, Article 4).

¹⁵ The data of the enterprise, including the headcount, are determined on the basis of the accounts and other data of the enterprise or, where they exist, the consolidated accounts of the enterprise, or the consolidated accounts in which the enterprise is included through consolidation.

ANNEX A

Partner enterprises

For each enterprise for which a 'partnership sheet' has been completed (one sheet for each partner enterprise of the applicant enterprise and for any partner enterprises of any linked enterprise, of which the data is not yet included in the consolidated accounts of that linked enterprise), the data in the 'partnership box' in question should be entered in the summary table below:

BOX A

Partner enterprise (name / identification)	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			
7.			
Total			

(*) EUR 1 000.

(attach sheets or expand the present table, if necessary)

Reminder:

This data is the result of a proportional calculation done on the 'partnership sheet' for each direct or indirect partner enterprise.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 2 (regarding partner enterprises) of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

PARTNERSHIP SHEET

1. Precise identification of the applicant enterprise

Name or Business name.....
 Address (of registered office)
 Registration/VAT number¹⁶
 Names and titles of the principal director(s)¹⁷

2. Raw data regarding that partner enterprise

Reference period

	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
Raw data			

(*) EUR 1 000.

Reminder: These raw data are derived from the accounts and other data of the partner enterprise, consolidated if they exist. To them are added 100% of the data of enterprises which are linked to this partner enterprise, unless the accounts data of those linked enterprises are already included through consolidation in the accounts of the partner enterprise¹⁸. If necessary, add “linkage sheets” for the enterprises which are not yet included through consolidation.

3. Proportional calculation

a) Indicate precisely the holding¹⁹ of the enterprise drawing up the declaration (or of the linked enterprise via which the relation to the partner enterprise is established) in the partner enterprise to which this sheet relates:

.....

Indicate also the holding of the partner enterprise to which this sheet relates in the enterprise drawing up the declaration (or in the linked enterprise):

.....

b) The higher of these two holding percentages should be applied to the raw data entered in the previous box. The results of this proportional calculation should be given in the following table:

‘Partnership box’

¹⁶ To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

¹⁷ Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

¹⁸ Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, first sub-paragraph

¹⁹ In terms of the share of the capital or voting rights, whichever is higher. To this holding should be added the holding of each linked enterprise in the same enterprise (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2 first sub-paragraph).

Percentage:	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
Proportional results			

(*) EUR 1 000.

These data should be entered in Box A in Annex A.

ANNEX B
 Linked enterprises

DETERMINE THE CASE APPLICABLE TO THE APPLICANT ENTERPRISE:

Case 1: The applicant enterprise draws up consolidated accounts or is included by consolidation in the consolidated accounts of another enterprise. (Box B(1))

Case 2: The applicant enterprise or one or more of the linked enterprises do not establish consolidated accounts or are not included in the consolidated accounts. (Box B(2)).

Please note: The data of the enterprises, which are linked to the applicant enterprise, are derived from their accounts and their other data, consolidated if they exist. To them are aggregated proportionally the data of any possible partner enterprise of that linked enterprise, situated immediately upstream or downstream from it, unless it has already been included through consolidation²⁰.

CALCULATION METHODS FOR EACH CASE:

In case 1: The consolidated accounts serve as the basis for the calculation. Fill in Box B(1) below.

Box B(1)

	Headcount (*)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)
Total			

(*) Where in the consolidated accounts no headcount data appears, the calculation of it is done by adding the data from the enterprises to which the enterprise in question is linked.

(**) EUR 1 000.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 1 of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

²⁰ Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, second sub-paragraph

Identification of the enterprises included through consolidation

Linked enterprise (name / identification)	Address (of registered office)	Registration / VAT number (*)	Names and titles of the principal director(s) (**)
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			
7.			
Total			

(*) To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

(**) Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

Important: Partner enterprises of such a linked enterprise, which are not yet included through consolidation, are treated like direct partners of the applicant enterprise. Their data and a 'partnership sheet' should therefore be added in Annex A.

In case 2: For each linked enterprise (including links via other linked enterprises), complete a "linkage sheet" and simply add together the accounts of all the linked enterprises by filling in Box B(2) below.

Box B(2)

Enterprise No.:	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)
1. (*)			
2. (*)			
3. (*)			
Total			

(*) attach one "linkage sheet" per enterprise

(**) EUR 1 000.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 3 (regarding linked enterprises) of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

LINKAGE SHEET

(only for linked enterprises not included by consolidation in Box B)

1. Precise identification of the applicant enterprise

Name or Business name.....
 Address (of registered office).....
 Registration/VAT number²¹.....
 Names and titles of the principal director(s)²².....

2. Data on enterprise

Reference period				
	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance total (*)	sheet
Total				

(*) EUR 1 000.

These data should be entered in Box B(2) in Annex B.

Important: The data of the enterprises, which are linked to the applicant enterprise, are derived from their accounts and their other data, consolidated if they exist. To them are aggregated proportionally the data of any possible partner enterprise of that linked enterprise, situated immediately upstream or downstream from it, unless it has already been included through consolidation²³.

Such partner enterprises are treated like direct partner enterprises of the applicant enterprise. Their data and a 'partnership sheet' have therefore to be added in Annex A.

²¹ To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

²² Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

²³ If the data of an enterprise are included in the consolidated accounts to a lesser proportion than the one determined under Article 6 paragraph 2, the percentage rate according to that article should be applied (Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, second sub-paragraph).

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 5 Sub-grant Agreement Template

(*) subject to change

Open Call 1: to be signed ONLY once selected
Submission deadline: **16 January 2024, 17:00 CET**

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Contracting parties

This **Agreement** ('the Agreement') is **between** the following parties:

On the one part,

_____ [Organisation name/ Individual name]
established in _____, [Official address], VAT
number _____, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by
_____ [Name of legal representative],
_____ [Position in the organisation], acting as Coordinator of
the _____ [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium.

Hereinafter referred to as the “Coordinator”,

_____ [Organisation name/ Individual name]
established in _____, [Official address], VAT
number _____, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by
_____ [Name of legal representative],
_____ [Position in the organisation], acting as **Treasurer** of the
_____ [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium. [IF RELEVANT]

Hereinafter referred to as the “Treasurer”,

And, on the other part,

_____ [Organisation name/ Individual name]
established in _____, [Official address], VAT
number _____, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by
_____ [Name of legal representative],

Hereinafter referred to as the “Beneficiary”.

Hereinafter, all parties above are collectively referred to as the “Contracting Parties”

The Contracting Parties **HAVE AGREED** to the following terms and conditions including those in the following Annexes, which form an integral part of this Sub-Grant Agreement (hereinafter referred as the “Contract”).

General Provisions

The European Commission (hereinafter referred as the “EC”) and the Coordinator, as partner and representative of the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium, have signed the Grant Agreement no. XXXXXX for the implementation of the [%PROJECT_NAME%] project – [%PROJECT FULL TITLE%] – within the framework of the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The [%PROJECT_NAME%] project is implemented by the Coordinator, as coordinator of the [%PROJECT_NAME%] project, in collaboration with the other [%PROJECT_NAME%] partners. The [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners have among themselves entered into a written agreement detailing their respective rights and obligations towards each other for carrying out the [%PROJECT_NAME%] project and exploiting the results thereof (“the Consortium Agreement” or “CA”).

The objective of [%PROJECT_NAME%] is to [provide description of the project] (...).

The Beneficiary has been selected for funding under the [%PROGRAMME_NAME_NUMBER%] based on the positive evaluation of external evaluators.

This Contract aims at defining the framework of rights and obligations of the Contracting Parties with respect to the Beneficiary’s participation in the [%PROGRAMME_NAME_NUMBER%].

The funding to be received by the Beneficiary is property of the EC. The Coordinator and Treasurer (IF APPLICABLE) are mere holders and managers of the funds.

Article 1 - Entry into force and termination of the contract

1.1. Entry into force

This Contract will enter into force on the day of its signature by the last Contracting Party. The Coordinator and Treasurer will sign this contract only after all the following documents have been received from the Beneficiary:

- The original signed Declaration(s) of Honour (as provided in Annex X or Annex Y, depending on type of applicant).
- SMEs Declaration form (as provided in Annex Z).
- Bank Account Information form (as provided in Annex XX).

All documents, properly signed and stamped (if applicable), shall be sent to the Coordinator and Treasurer, to the following e-mail: XXXX. The Beneficiary is requested to send all requested documents in a single e-mail and with adequate identification (e-mail subject): [%PROGRAMME_NAME_NUMBER%] – [%Sub-project Acronym%] documentation. All original should be sent to the following address:

[Address]

After receipt and validation of the documentation, the Beneficiary will receive a sub-grant agreement (contract) for signature. The Beneficiary is solely responsible for the accuracy of all data provided.

The contact details of the Beneficiary for notices and communication under this contract are:

Name of contact person	
Address	
E-mail	
Telephone/ mobile phone	

1.2. Contract termination

This Contract will automatically terminate at the end of (...), which will happen when the Beneficiary has fulfilled all obligations in Article 2, except for those obligations that according to their content are intended to remain in effect, which keep their full force and effect (e.g., reporting on exploitation activities).

The Coordinator shall be entitled to terminate this Contract by written notice with immediate effect if the Beneficiary does not fulfil its obligations (see Article 3 - Breach of Contractual obligations).

Irrespective of the automatic termination of this Contract under present Article 1.2 or any early termination under Article 4, all obligations that according to their content are intended to be in effect for longer shall remain in effect.

Article 2 - Obligations and responsibilities of the Beneficiary

The obligations and responsibilities are defined in detail in [Annex X - Guidelines for Applicants](#).

Additionally, the Beneficiary shall take every necessary precaution to avoid any risk of conflict of interest relating to economic interests, political or national affinities, personal or any other interests liable to influence the impartial and objective performance of the sub-project. In case the Beneficiary is involved in a conflict of interest or in a risk of conflict of interest, the Beneficiary must formally notify this situation to the Coordinator without delay and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

Furthermore, the Beneficiary shall provide true and accurate documentation and declarations as defined in Article 1.1.

Article 3 - Breach of contractual obligations

In the event of a breach of the contractual obligation's representations or warranties by the Beneficiary under this Contract, the Coordinator, in coordination with the [%PROJECT_NAME%] Consortium, reserves the right to terminate the Contract by written notice with immediate effect, even if such non-fulfilment is due to Force Majeure.

In the event of the breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary, the Treasurer with the agreement of the Coordinator reserves the right of not fulfilling the respective payment to the Beneficiary.

The Coordinator also reserves the right to claim a refund of any already paid funds, both in case of breach of contract and/or in case the work/costs are not approved by the EC.

The Coordinator will give written notice requiring that such breach to be remedied within 30 days.

In case the Beneficiary has not brought remedies from the notice, the Coordinator may decide to terminate the contract unilaterally.

Article 4 – Financial contribution and financial provisions

4.1 Maximum financial contribution

The maximum financial contribution to be granted to the Beneficiary shall not exceed the amount of xxxxxxxxxxxx euros (xxx.xxx,00) EURO.

4.2 Distribution of the financial contribution

The financial contribution to be granted to the Beneficiary will be calculated and distributed in accordance with the provisions set in Annex X - Guidelines for Applicants.

The financial grant to be paid will always be subject to:

- Provision of a report and a favourable review by the [%PROJECT_NAME%] internal evaluation team responsible for assessing the sub-project in each of the stages.
 - Sprint 1 – xxx % of the budget.
 - Sprint 2 – xxx % of the budget.
 - Sprint 3 – xxx % of the budget.

Note: A non-favourable review of the work carried out at the end of any stage may lead to the early termination of the contract and suspension of payments.

- The prior notice to the Beneficiary of the date and amount to be transferred to its bank account (Annex 8 - Bank account information form), providing the relevant references.
- Payments to the Beneficiary will be made by the Treasurer. In particular:
 - The Treasurer, with the agreement of the Coordinator, reserves the right to withhold the payments in case the Beneficiary does not fulfil its obligations and tasks as per Annex x - Guidelines for Applicants.

- Banking and transaction costs related to the handling of any financial resources made available to the Beneficiary will be covered by the Beneficiary.
- Payments will be released no later than thirty (30) calendar days after the notification by the Coordinator to the Beneficiary that the work and deliverable associated to a particular stage has been approved.

The Beneficiary is responsible for complying with any tax and legal obligations that might be attached to this Contract.

4.3 Payments schedule

The payment schedule is directly linked to the relevant **stages** of the sub-project according to **Annex X - Guidelines for Applicants**. The payment in each stage will be disbursed once all work related to a specific **stage** has received positive assessment, supported on the report submitted to the [%PROJECT_NAME%] team.

The financial contribution will be made to the Beneficiary by the **Treasurer**. During the contractual procedure, the Beneficiary will be asked to provide the respective bank account information to which the payments will be made (as provided in **Annex X**).

The payment schedule (**Table X**) is linked to the successful completion of specified milestones and KPIs established by the Beneficiary in its project proposal, which will be evaluated through a report (deliverable) submitted to [%PROJECT_NAME%] at the end of each **stage** as identified in **Annex x – Guidelines for Applicants**.

Checking the consistency between the estimated costs and resources and the expected work of the project will also be included in the evaluation process. If requested, the Beneficiary will have to present any documentation for the costs claimed.

[Table with the payments schedule]

The Beneficiary should submit to [%PROJECT_NAME%] the deliverable corresponding to each stage no later than ten (10) calendar days after the end of the respective stage, providing sufficient time for the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium to review it. **A review will be held between fifteen (15) to thirty (30) calendar days after the end of the stage** so that the Contracting Parties can present their work and provide answers to questions from the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners.

The payments will be made to the Beneficiary subject to the receipt of an invoice or a filled out Financial Identification Form (FIF).²⁴ If the Beneficiary chooses to send an invoice, the invoice must include the following information:

Project **xxx** – Grant no. **xxx**

[%PROGRAMME_NAME_NUMBER%]

The Stage to which the payment is associated [*Sprint 1, Sprint 2, Sprint x*]

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/about_the_european_commission/eu_budget/fich_sign_ba_gb_en_0.pdf

Beneficiary information (e.g. sub-project acronym and beneficiary name)

The invoice or the FIF is to be sent to **e-mail**. Payments will only be initiated once the work has been approved. Payments will be made no later than thirty (30) calendar days after receipt of the invoice or FIF to the bank account of the Beneficiary as provided in **Annex 8**. All payments will be made in Euros.

NOTE: If at any of the payment stages the [%PROJECT_NAME%] team considers that the quality of work demonstrated and/or reported does not correspond to what has been agreed, the two parties may agree to a resubmission of a deliverable and respective reassessment. If significant improvements are not delivered after the reassessment and the sub-project is therefore considered to be in breach of their contractual obligations, [%PROJECT_NAME%] reserves the right to terminate the contract as outlined in *Article 3 – Breach of contractual obligations*.

Article 5 - Liability

5.1 Liability of the Beneficiary

The Beneficiary shall fully and exclusively bear the risks in connection with the fulfilment of its tasks and obligations under this Contract. Except in case of force majeure (Article 8), the Beneficiary must compensate the Coordinator, the **Treasurer** and the EC for any damage they sustain because of the implementation of the obligations of the Beneficiary under this Contract or because the tasks and obligations of the Beneficiary were not implemented in full compliance with this Contract.

Accordingly, neither [%PROJECT_NAME%] Consortium nor the EC can be held liable for any damage caused to the Beneficiary or to third parties because of implementing this Contract, including for gross negligence. At the same time, neither [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium nor the EC can be held liable for any damage caused by the Beneficiary or third parties, because of implementing this Contract.

The Beneficiary shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that its acts within the framework of this Contract do not infringe third parties' rights. There is no joint liability between the Contracting Parties. For this purpose, the Beneficiary shall indemnify and hold the Coordinator, the **Treasurer** and the EC harmless from and against all repayments, loss, liability, costs, charges, claims or damages which the Coordinator, the **Treasurer** or the EC as a result thereof would incur or suffer or must pay to the EC or any third parties. In addition, should the EC have a right of recovery against [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium regarding any or all the financial support granted under this Contract, the Beneficiary shall repay the sums in question in the terms and on the date specified by the Coordinator.

5.2 Exclusions of liability

To the extent acceptable under applicable law, in no event shall the Coordinator or other [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners be liable to the Beneficiary for loss or damage caused

by the Coordinator or the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners, their employees, agents and subcontractors in connection with this Contract for any of the following, however caused or arising, on any theory of liability, and even if the Coordinator and/or any other [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partner were informed or aware of the possibility thereof:

- Loss of profits, revenue, income, interest, savings, shelf-space, production, and business.
- Opportunities; lost contracts, goodwill, and anticipated savings.
- Loss of or damage to reputation or to data.
- Costs of recall of products.
- Any type of indirect, incidental, punitive, special, or consequential loss or damage.

In respect of any information or materials from the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium made available to the Beneficiary under this Contract, no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given, or implied as to the sufficiency, error-free performance, or fitness for purpose, nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of third parties. Therefore, in particular, but without limiting the foregoing:

- The Beneficiary shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials, and the consequences of such use, and
- Neither the Coordinator, the EC nor the other [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners shall be liable vis-à-vis the Beneficiary in case of infringement of proprietary rights of a third party resulting from the Beneficiary's use of the information and material.

The exclusions and limitations stated in this Article and any other clause of this Contract that has as its object or effect the exclusion or limitation of liability, shall not apply in respect of any: fraud; death, injury to natural persons or damage to real or immovable property caused by the negligence or wilful act, wilful misconduct, wilful breach; or otherwise in so far as mandatory applicable law overrides such exclusions and limitations.

Article 6 - Confidentiality

6.1 Principles

Regarding all information of whatever nature or form as is disclosed between the Contracting Parties in connection with the Sub-project and identified in writing as confidential, the terms of this Article shall apply.

6.2 Obligations

All information, in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Contracting Party (the “Disclosing Party”) to the other Contracting Party (the “Recipient”) in connection with the implementation of the [%PROGRAMME_NAME_NUMBER%] and which has been explicitly marked as “confidential” at the time of disclosure, or, when disclosed orally, has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated

in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure (at the latest) as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is “Confidential Information”.

The Recipient hereby accepts, in addition and without prejudice to any commitment on nondisclosure towards the EC, for a period of 5 (five) years after the end of the Contract:

- Not to use Confidential Information other than for the purpose for which it was disclosed.
- Not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party.
- To ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis.
- To return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on demand, all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipient, including all copies and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipient may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive, or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy for as long as the copy is retained.

The Recipient shall be responsible for the fulfilment of the above obligations on the part of their employees or third parties involved in the implementation of [%PROGRAMME_NAME_NUMBER%] and shall ensure that they remain so obliged, as far as legally possible, during and after the end hereof and/or after the termination of the contractual relationship with the employee or third party. The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care regarding the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care. Each Contracting Party shall promptly advise the other Contracting Party in writing of any unauthorized disclosure, misappropriation, or misuse of Confidential Information after it becomes aware of such unauthorized disclosure, misappropriation, or misuse.

6.3 Exceptions to the obligation of confidentiality

The information above (Article 6.2) shall not apply for disclosure or use of Confidential Information, if and in so far as the Recipient can show that:

- The Confidential Information has become or becomes publicly available by means other than a breach of the Recipient’s confidentiality obligations.
- The Disclosing Party subsequently informs the Recipient that the Confidential Information is no longer confidential.
- The Confidential Information is communicated to the Recipient without any obligation of confidentiality by a third party who is to the best knowledge of the Recipient in lawful possession thereof and under no obligation of confidentiality to the Disclosing Party.
- The disclosure or communication of the Confidential Information is foreseen by provisions of the Grant Agreement.

- The Confidential Information, at any time, was developed by the Recipient completely independently of any such disclosure by the Disclosing Party.
- The Confidential Information was already known to the Recipient prior to disclosure.
- Disclosure of the Confidential Information follows mandatory applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order.

6.4 Authorised disclosure(s)

If any Party becomes aware that it will be required, or is likely to be required, to disclose Confidential Information to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, it will, to the extent it is lawfully able to do so under the laws and legislation applicable to said Party, prior to any such disclosure:

- Notify the Disclosing Party, and
- Comply with the Disclosing Party's reasonable instructions to protect the confidentiality of the information.

The [%PROJECT_NAME%] Coordinator's disclosure of Confidential Information to the EC and/or the other [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners shall be governed exclusively by the terms of the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement.

Accordingly, nothing in this Contract shall prevent the [%PROJECT_NAME%] Coordinator from complying with its obligations, including its reporting obligations, towards the EC and the other [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners, and any such disclosures shall be subject to the terms of the Grant Agreement or Consortium Agreement.

Likewise, the Beneficiary agrees and acknowledges that the EC shall be entitled to disclose Confidential Information to its staff, other EU institutions and bodies or third parties, if:

- This is necessary to implement the Grant Agreement or safeguard the EU's financial interests.
- The recipients of the information are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

Article 7 - Intellectual property rights

The Beneficiary acknowledges that all tools, modules and similar of the [%PROJECT_NAME%] partners are proprietary and owned by the respective [%PROJECT_NAME%] partner or applicable third party.

Nothing in this Contract shall transfer to the Beneficiary or other partners it represents any license or other rights for the use of the tools, modules and similar that are property of an [%PROJECT_NAME%] partner, unless a specific agreement is established.

The results developed during the sub-project shall be exclusively the property of the Beneficiary. This does not exclude the possibility for specific agreements to be made between the Beneficiary and one or more of the partners of [%PROJECT_NAME%].

Article 8 - Force Majeure

“Force Majeure” means any unforeseeable exceptional situation or event beyond the Contracting Parties control, which prevents either of them from fulfilling any of their obligations under the Agreement, which was not attributable to error or negligence on their part and which proves to be inevitable despite the exercising of all due diligence.

Any default of a service, defect in equipment or material or delays in making them available, unless they stem directly from a relevant case of force majeure, as well as labour disputes, strikes or financial difficulties cannot be invoked as Force Majeure.

The Contracting Parties shall take the necessary measures to limit any damage due to Force Majeure. They shall do their best to resume the implementation of the action as soon as possible.

No Contracting Party shall be in breach of its obligations and tasks if such a breach is caused by Force Majeure. A Contracting Party will notify the other Contracting Party of any Force Majeure as soon as possible. In case the Beneficiary is not able to overcome the consequences of Force Majeure within thirty calendar (30) days after such notification, the [%PROJECT_NAME%] Coordinator will decide accordingly, including the termination of the Contract.

Included background: Background is defined as “data, know-how or information that is needed to implement the Action or exploit the results”. Because of this need, Access Rights have to be granted in principle, but Parties must identify and agree amongst them on the Background for the Project. The Beneficiary has identified and agreed on the Background for the Project and has also, where relevant, informed the consortium that Access to specific Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits.

Anything not identified in the following table shall not be the object of Access Right obligations regarding Background.

Describe Background	Specific restrictions and/or conditions for implementation	Specific restrictions and/or conditions for Exploitation

--	--	--

Article 9 - Information and communication

9.1 Information and communication towards the EC

The Beneficiary shall, throughout the duration of the sub-project, take appropriate measures to engage with the public and the media about the sub-project and **to highlight the financial support of the EC and the [%PROJECT_NAME%] project.**

Unless the EC requests otherwise, any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), and any infrastructure, equipment, and major results must:

- Specify that the sub-project has received research funding from the EC through the [%PROJECT_NAME%] project.
- Display the European emblem along with the [%PROJECT_NAME%] logo. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use. It is subject to general third-party use restrictions which do not permit the appropriation of the emblem, or of any similar trademark or logo, whether by registration or by any other means. Under these conditions, the Beneficiary is exempt from the obligation to obtain prior permission from the EC to use the emblem.
- Specify that it reflects only the author's views and that the EC and the [%PROJECT_NAME%] Consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The following text should be used:

"The [%sub-project acronym] has indirectly received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation action programme, via the [%PROGRAMME_NAME_NUMBER%] issued and executed under the [%PROJECT_NAME%] project (Grant Agreement no. XXXXXX)."

The Coordinator, the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium, and/or the EC shall be authorised to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- The name of the Beneficiary.
- Contact address of the Beneficiary.
- The general purpose of the sub-project (publishable summary, etc.)
- The amount of the financial contribution of the EC foreseen for the sub-project. after the final payment, the amount and rate of the financial contribution of the EC accepted by the EC.

- The estimated amount and rate of the financial contribution of the EC foreseen for the Beneficiary in the table of the estimated breakdown of budget.
- The geographic location of the activities carried out.
- The list of dissemination activities and/or of patent (applications) relating to foreground.
- The publishable reports submitted (technical reports are excluded, since they are confidential).
- Any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the EC in the framework of the Sub-project.

The Beneficiary shall ensure that all necessary authorisations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the [%PROJECT_NAME%] Coordinator, the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners, or EC does not infringe any rights of third parties.

Upon a duly supported request by the Coordinator on behalf of the Beneficiary, the EC may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary's security, academic or commercial interests.

9.2 Information and communication among the Contracting Parties

Any notice to be given under this Contract shall be in writing to the addresses and recipients listed above. Any change of persons or contact details shall be notified immediately to the [%PROJECT_NAME%] Coordinator. The address list shall be made accessible to all parties concerned.

Article 10 - Checks and reviews

The EC may, at any time during the implementation of the sub-project and up to five years after the end of the sub-project, arrange for a check and review to be carried out, by external auditors, or by the EC services themselves, including the European Anti-Fraud office (OLAF). The procedure shall be deemed to be initiated on the date of receipt of the relevant letter sent by the EC.

There will be no financial checks, reviews, or audits to check costs, since beneficiaries have no obligation to document the costs incurred for the action. Checks, reviews, and audits will focus on the technical implementation of the action.

The Beneficiary shall make available directly to the EC all information and data that may be requested by the EC or any representative authorised by it, in view of verifying that the Grant Agreement is properly managed and performed in accordance with its provisions.

The Beneficiary shall keep the originals or, in exceptional cases, duly authenticated copies (including electronic copies) of all documents related to the Grant Agreement for up to five years from the end of the sub-project. These shall be made available to the EC when requested during any check under the Grant Agreement.

To carry out these checks, the Beneficiary shall ensure that the EC's services and any external body(ies) authorised by it have on-the-spot access at all reasonable times, notably to the Beneficiary's offices, to its computer data, and to all the information needed to carry out those checks. They shall ensure that the information is readily available on the spot during an audit and, if so requested, that data be handed over in an appropriate form.

Based on the findings made during the check, a provisional report shall be drawn up. It shall be sent by the EC or its authorised representative to the Beneficiary concerned, which may make observations thereon within one month of receiving it. The EC may decide not to take into account observations conveyed or documents sent after that deadline. The final report shall be sent to the Beneficiary concerned within two months of expiry of the aforesaid deadline.

Based on the conclusions of the check, the EC shall take all appropriate measures which it considers necessary, including the issuing of recovery orders regarding all or part of the payments made by it and the application of any applicable sanction.

The European Court of Auditors shall have the same rights as the EC, notably right of access, for the purpose of checks and audits, without prejudice to its own rules.

In addition, the EC may carry out on-the-spot checks and inspections in accordance with Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/96 of 11 November 1996 concerning on-the-spot checks and inspections carried out by the EC to protect the European Communities' financial interests against fraud and other irregularities.

Article 11 – Data protection

The Contracting Parties have the obligation to abide by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

Each Contracting Party shall each be considered a separate and independent data controller, as defined in the GDPR, to every other Contracting Party. The processing of personal data shall be carried out lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner, collected for specific purposes and adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is processed. Where it might be designated by a relevant Supervisory Authority or through agreement between Contracting Parties that the [%PROJECT_NAME%] Coordinator and any other [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners are appointed as data processors, parties shall enter into appropriate data processing agreements as required by the GDPR.

The Beneficiary acknowledges that the [%PROJECT_NAME%] Coordinator and any other [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners, if appointed as data processors, are not responsible for the Beneficiary's compliance with any data protection or privacy law applicable to the Beneficiary. Each of the Contracting Parties, in their respective roles as data controllers, will be

responsible for their own compliance with any data protection or privacy law applicable to them as data controller.

Article 12 - Obligations imposed by the Grant Agreement to the Beneficiary

The Beneficiary receives funding from the European Commission for carrying out the sub-project [REDACTED] [sub-project acronym]. Under the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement, some of the obligations must be imposed on the Beneficiary. Those obligations are reflected in this Agreement. The specific obligations that the Beneficiary must ensure are described in the Multi-Beneficiary General Model Grant Agreement²⁵ (H2020 General MGA – Multi), in articles 22, 35, 36, 38 and 46. These articles are included in this Contract and are fully applicable to the Beneficiary.

The Beneficiary acknowledges and agrees that these obligations comprised in this Agreement and the above-mentioned obligations of the Multi-Beneficiary General Model are fully applicable to it.

Article 13 - Miscellaneous

Should any provision of this Contract be or become invalid, illegal, or unenforceable, it shall not affect the validity of the remaining provisions of this Contract. In such a case, the Contracting Parties shall be entitled to request that a valid, legal, enforceable, and practicable replacement provision be negotiated which fulfils the purpose of the original provision.

The Beneficiary shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of the Coordinator or any other [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partner, and nothing in this Contract shall be deemed to constitute a joint venture, agency, partnership, interest grouping or any other kind of formal business grouping or entity between the Contracting Parties or between the Beneficiary and any [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partner.

No rights or obligations of the Beneficiary arising from this Contract may be assigned or transferred, in whole or in part, and no obligations of the Beneficiary may be sub-contracted, without the Coordinator's prior formal written approval; and such approval shall not exempt the Beneficiary from any of its obligations hereunder.

Although (with exception to the Coordinator and the Treasurer) the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners and their affiliated entities are not Contracting Parties to this Contract, they are intended by the Contracting Parties to be third party beneficiaries under this Contract and accordingly shall be entitled to enforce the terms of this Contract against the Beneficiary and (without limitation) shall be entitled to the benefit of, and to enforce any exclusion of limitation of liability of the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners contained in this Contract

²⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

and any indemnity in favour of the [%PROJECT_NAME%] consortium partners contained in this Contract.

Amendments and modifications to the text of this Agreement require a separate written agreement to be signed between all Parties. Although this Contract refers to the provisions of the CA and GA, the Beneficiary is not a party to the CA or GA but only bound towards the Coordinator by the CA and GA provisions as referred or reproduced in this Contract.

This Contract is drawn up in English language which shall govern all documents, notices, meetings, and processes relative thereto.

Article 14 - Applicable Law

This Contract shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Ireland.

Article 15 - Settlement of disputes

If the Contracting Parties are unable to resolve a dispute amicably, such dispute will be finally settled under the Rules of Arbitration of the International Chamber of Commerce by three (3) arbitrators in Dublin.

Each of the Contracting Parties to the dispute shall appoint one (1) arbitrator and the two (2) arbitrators so appointed shall elect the presiding arbitrator. Should a Party to the dispute which should appoint an arbitrator fails to do so within fourteen (14) days of the delivery of the written notice to do so from the other Party to the dispute or should the appointed arbitrators fail to reach agreement on the presiding arbitrator within fourteen (14) days after their appointment, such arbitrator shall be appointed in accordance with the Rules upon request of any of the Parties to the dispute.

The seat of arbitration shall be Dublin.

The Contracting Parties agree that the language of the arbitration, including oral hearings, written evidence, and correspondence shall be English.

A duly rendered arbitration award shall be final and binding on the Contracting Parties to the dispute. Each Contracting Party to the arbitration conducted in accordance with this section hereof shall bear its own expenses incurred in connection with such arbitration, including fees of its legal counsels. All other costs and expenses shall be apportioned between the Contracting Parties to the arbitration in accordance with the decision of the arbitrators.

Nothing in this Contract shall limit the Contracting Parties right to seek injunctive relief or to enforce an arbitration award in any applicable competent court of law.

Article 16 – No double funding

By signing this Agreement, the Beneficiary declares to be aware of the fundamental principle underpinning the rules for public expenditure in the EU that no costs for the same activity be

funded twice from the EU budget, as defined in the Article 111 of Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No. 1605/2002 of 25 June 2002 on the Financial Regulation, and confirms that all the work performed under [%PROJECT_NAME%] (Grant Agreement no. XXXXXX) will be done exclusively in the scope of this programme, not being supported or funded by any other European Commission programme.

AS WITNESS:

The Contracting Parties have caused this Contract to be duly signed by the undersigned authorized representatives **in three (3) copies** the day and year first above written:

<p>For XXX ([%PROJECT_NAME%] Coordinator) Mr/Ms [NAME SURNAME] [POSITION_IN_ORGANISATION] Signature</p> <p>Done at _____ on DD/MM/202Y</p>	<p>For XXXX (Treasurer) Mr/Ms _____ [NAME SURNAME] _____ [POSITION_IN_COMPANY] Signature</p> <p>Done at _____ on DD/MM/202Y</p>
<p>For _____ [organization/ individual name] (the Beneficiary) Mr/Ms _____ [NAME SURNAME] _____ [POSITION_IN_ORGANISATION] Signature</p> <p>Done at _____ on DD/MM/202Y</p>	

ANNEXES

[Annex XXX: Technical Proposal](#)

[Annex XXX: Declaration of Honour](#)

[Annex XXX: SME Declaration \(if applicable\)](#)

[Annex XXX: Bank account](#)

C O R T E X ²

ANNEX 6 Bank Account Information

Open Call 1: To submit ONLY once selected
Submission deadline: **16 January 2024, 17:00 CET**

ACCOUNT HOLDER INFORMATION

Account Name Holder <i>The name or title under which the account has been opened and NOT the name of the authorized agent.</i>	
Holder's Address	
Postcode	
Town/City	
Country	

Contact Person <i>Does not need to be an authorised agent.</i>	
Telephone	
Mobile phone	

BANK ACCOUNT INFORMATION

Bank Name	
Branch Address	
Postcode	
Town/City	
Country	
IBAN number / Account number <i>Format example: ES76 2077 0024 0031 0257 5766</i>	
SWIFT code <i>8 to 11 characters</i>	

BANK STAMP + SIGNATURE OF BANK REPRESENTATIVE	DATE + SIGNATURE OF ACCOUNT HOLDER (MANDATORY)
<i>The bank stamp + signature of the bank representative can be replaced with the attachment of a recent bank statement (less than 2 months).</i>	